

SMSS

2024

A scientific glimpse into the past, present and future

Official program and book of abstracts for the first

Seychelles Marine Science Symposium

Eden Bleu, Mahe, 22 -23 May 2024

Address from UniSey Vice-Chancellor – Ms Joëlle Perreau

Ladies and Gentlemen,

Distinguished guests, esteemed colleagues, students, and friends, it is with great honour and pleasure that I welcome you to the inaugural Seychelles Marine Science Symposium. This event holds special significance as it forms part of the University of Seychelles' 15th-anniversary celebrations. Today, we gather to celebrate not only our university's remarkable journey and achievements but also to underscore the critical importance of marine science in preserving the natural heritage of our beautiful islands.

For the past 15 years, the University of Seychelles has grown in leaps and bounds becoming a shining beacon for knowledge creation, innovation, and sustainability for our region. Our commitment to excellence in education and research has fostered a generation of scholars and professionals dedicated to advancing understanding and stewardship of the marine environment – many of whom are present in the audience today.

As we confront the pressing challenges of climate change, overfishing, and pollution, the role of marine science becomes ever more critical. Through rigorous research, innovative solutions, and collaborative efforts, we can ensure the resilience and vitality of our marine environments for generations to come. This symposium brings together a dynamic community of scientists, researchers, policymakers, and advocates from around the world. Over the next few days, we will engage in meaningful dialogue, share groundbreaking research, and forge new partnerships. Let us embrace this opportunity to learn from one another, to inspire and be inspired, and to reaffirm our collective commitment to marine conservation.

As we celebrate our university's 15-year legacy, let us also look forward with hope and determination. Together, we can and we will make a difference. Thank you for being here, and I wish you all a productive and enlightening symposium.

Joëlle Perreau
Vice-Chancellor
University of Seychelles

BRUV still from research undertaken at to assess fish diversity at Denis Island, Seychelles – Photo: Stuart Laing & Kaylee Smit, (UniSey OceanLifeScience)

Address from acting director of BERI – Dr. Jermone Harlay

It is my absolute pleasure to extend a heartfelt welcome to each and every one of you to the “Seychelles Marine Science Symposium”, on behalf of the *James Michel* Blue Economy Research Institute (BERI). Set against the backdrop of the breathtaking Seychelles archipelago, our symposium promises to be a celebration of marine exploration, conservation, sustainability and innovation.

The Seychelles, with its turquoise waters, vibrant coral reefs, and rich biodiversity, serves as an unparalleled natural laboratory for the study of marine ecosystems. We are not only drawn together by our shared fascination with the wonders of the ocean but also by our collective commitment to protecting, preserving its delicate balance and that of the people who rely on its healthiness.

The BERI has been at the forefront of marine research, Blue Economy advocacy and literacy, and education, for the last 9 years and it is our privilege to host this symposium in partnership with the Save our Seas Foundation (SOSF) and the Western Indian Ocean Marine Science Association (WIOMSA). With your participation, we embark on a journey of discovery, guided by the principles of sustainability, stewardship, and scientific excellence.

Over the next two days, we will have the opportunity to listen to keynote speakers and engage with researchers from around the world, as they share their insights and experiences gained in our playground. From exploring new frontiers in oceanography to addressing the impacts of climate change on marine ecosystems, our program is as diverse and dynamic as the seas themselves.

I am convinced that each of you will embrace this symposium as a platform for collaboration, learning, and inspiration. Let us seize this opportunity to forge new partnerships, exchange ideas, and catalyse positive change for the future of our oceans and the coastal communities that rely on them.

Thank you for joining us at the “Seychelles Marine Science Symposium”, we have laid the foundation of what, we hope, will become a *rendez-vous incontournable*.

Dr. Jérôme Harlay
Acting Director of BERI
James Michel Blue Economy Research Institute
University of Seychelles

Address from HOD of Dept. Environment at UniSey – Dr. Nulette Gordon

It is our great pleasure to welcome you to the first ever “Seychelles Marine Science Symposium”, an event dedicated to advancing the frontiers of marine science, and to share scientific research and findings over the last few decades in the Seychelles.

We extend a special welcome to our keynote speakers, whose contributions to marine science have been truly inspirational, as well as to all our distinguished guests and participants who have travelled from near and far to be here. Your presence enriches this symposium and underscores the global commitment to understanding and preserving our marine environments.

We would also like to express our deepest gratitude to our sponsors, organizers, and volunteers. Without their tireless efforts and unwavering support, this symposium would not be possible. In particular, we acknowledge the Save our Seas Foundation (SOSF) and the Western Indian Ocean Marine Science Association (WIOMSA) for their generous contributions and ongoing support for marine science initiatives.

This symposium centres on the theme “A scientific glimpse into the past, present, and future,” featuring presentations on various fields of marine research in the Seychelles addressing the challenges and opportunities in marine research. Our goal is to foster meaningful dialogue, share groundbreaking research, and inspire collaborative solutions that will drive forward our understanding and stewardship of the oceans. The significance of this gathering cannot be overstated. Marine science plays a crucial role in addressing global environmental challenges, from climate change and biodiversity loss to sustainable fisheries and pollution control. By coming together, we can leverage our collective expertise to make significant strides in these areas.

It is also a significant event for the University of Seychelles as we celebrate our 15th anniversary this year and also highlights the impact the University and its Blue Economy Research Institute (BERI) have made in not only training the next generation of marine researchers but also driving the Blue Economy agenda for Seychelles and merging sound scientific investigation with knowledge generation towards sound decision making and support of sustainable use of marine resources.

Over the next two days, you will have the opportunity to engage over 150 participants with a diverse array of sessions, including keynote addresses, panel discussions, special sessions, and poster presentations. We are particularly excited about our keynote presenters, who promise to deliver invaluable insights and spark innovative discussions.

We encourage each of you to take full advantage of this unique opportunity. Engage actively, network with your peers, and share your knowledge and ideas. It is through our collective effort and collaboration that we can achieve lasting impact.

In closing, we want to leave you with a thought: The ocean connects us all, and its health is intrinsically linked to our future. Let us use this symposium as a platform to advance our understanding, to inspire action, and to drive positive change for the benefit of our planet and future generations.

Thank you, and we wish you all a productive and inspiring symposium.

Dr Nulette Gordon
Head of Department
Environmental Sciences
University of Seychelles

Address from main sponsor – Save our Seas Foundation

The Save Our Seas Foundation was born more than 20 years ago out of a pure passion for our oceans, especially sharks and rays, and a realisation that these majestic, enigmatic, but overexploited creatures really need our help.

We were one of the first to facilitate shark conservation projects at a global scale and have long had very deep roots here in Seychelles, which we consider to be the blue heart of the foundation.

One of our very first projects tracked the movements of whale sharks here around Mahe, and not long after we started supporting Jeanne Mortimer's work on turtles. We have since partnered with Terence Vel at UniSey to bring environmental education into the community, and in 2012 assumed the management of the D'Arros Research Centre. The centre is an outstanding observatory for scientific research and discovery, and since its inception in 2004 has carried out a combination of long-term monitoring projects and focused research on things like turtles, sharks, rays and seabirds.

The D'Arros Research Centre has cemented our commitment to building local research capacity, providing internships and projects for local students, but also hosting the immersive D'Arros Experience for younger students, where they get to experience the projects and wild nature of D'Arros. We are delighted that many participants of the experience have gone on to pursue their own careers in marine science.

As such we are especially proud to be the primary sponsor of the first Seychelles Marine Science Symposium, and thank the UniSey team for making such a landmark meeting a reality. This is a fantastic opportunity for the whole marine science community within Seychelles and the broader region to come together and share their insights, learn from each other, and find solutions to some of the challenges our marine ecosystems face. Building a strong, collaborative network of scientists within Seychelles will provide an excellent platform for the marine science community to grow and flourish, and this is something we are delighted to facilitate.

Enjoy the symposium!

Photo: Christopher Vaughan-Jones

DEVELOPMENT OF A **SEYCHELLES NATIONAL RESEARCH AGENDA** FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF OCEAN SCIENCE

Summary

The Development of a Seychelles National Research Agenda for Sustainable Development of Ocean Science aims at prioritising and streamlining research efforts in marine science, directly aligned with Seychelles' strategic interests in its Blue Economy. Key objectives of this consultancy include determining priority research areas, identifying capacity development needs in marine research, and developing a management-oriented National Marine Research Agenda. The agenda will be shaped through extensive stakeholder engagement to ensure it addresses both current and future needs. By establishing clear research priorities, the agenda will support informed decision-making and policy development, which is essential for managing the Blue Economy sustainably. This initiative is vital for strengthening Seychelles' position as a leader in ocean science and sustainable marine resource management.

Help shape the future of marine science in Seychelles by providing your insights by participating in our brief survey — your expertise is invaluable to developing a comprehensive National Research Agenda for sustainable ocean development.

TAKE A SURVEY to help us shape Seychelles' future for Marine research.

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Brief agenda

Day 1 – 22nd May 2024

- 07:00 - Registration desk open (all day)
- 08:30 - Welcome (room 1)
- 08:45 - Opening by VIP
- 09:00 - Keynote – Jose Borrero
- 09:30 - Scientific sessions (Climate change & SIOFISH3 special session)
- 10:40 - tea
- 11:10 - Scientific sessions (Turtles & SWIOFISH3 special session)
- 12:30 - Lunch
- 13:40 - Keynote – Helena Sims
- 14:10 - Scientific sessions (Blue Economy + MSP & Seabirds)
- 15:20 - tea
- 16:00 - Scientific sessions (Aquaculture + coral restoration & SWIOFISH3 special session)
- 16:50 - End of day

Day 2 – 23rd May 2024

- 08:30 - Welcome
- 08:45 - Opening by VIP
- 09:00 - Keynote – James Lea
- 09:30 - Scientific sessions (Sharks & TOP special session)
- 10:30 - tea
- 11:00 - Scientific sessions (Marine Ecology & TOP special session)
- 12:30 - Lunch
- 13:40 - Keynote – Sheena Talma
- 14:10 - Scientific sessions (Cetaceans & Fisheries)
- 15:20 - Interlude
- 15:30 - Scientific sessions (Aquaculture + coral restoration & Management)
- 16:20 - Scientific closing
- 16:40 - Poster session & cocktail event

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TWO-DAY EVENT

ORGANISED BY A GROUP OF YOUNG OCEAN ADVOCATES

**IN COLLABORATION WITH THE SEYCHELLES MARINE
SCIENCE SYMPOSIUM (SMSS)**

**AIMS: SHOWCASE THE WONDERS AND CHALLENGES OF
OUR COASTAL AND MARINE ENVIRONMENTS & ENHANCE
THE PUBLIC'S AWARENESS AND ENGAGEMENT IN OCEAN
DISCOVERY INITIATIVES**

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Keynote Speakers

Dr Jose Borrero

Jose Borrero is a founder and director of newly formed ORCAS Consulting based in New Zealand (www.orcas-coastal.com). He is a coastal engineer and scientist with a Ph.D. in civil, environmental, and coastal engineering from the University of Southern California in Los Angeles. With more than 20 years in consulting, he specialises in the modelling and assessment of coastal hazards and has extensive experience in tropical small island developing states (SIDS). He has led numerous projects that combine field data collection, wave, hydrodynamic and sediment transport modelling, and engineering design to arrive at effective and workable solutions for dealing with coastal problems. He has a keen interest in the design of nature-based solutions including submerged and multipurpose

reefs for coastal protection and amenity enhancement, coastal plantings, dune management, beach rehabilitation, sea grass restoration and living shorelines. In the area of submerged reefs, he has worked on designs aimed at enhancing recreational amenities such as snorkelling or diving trails as well as for the creation of surf breaks. He also has extensive experience in surf break science including the characterisation and preservation of natural surf breaks and when possible, enhancement of surfing resources. In his talk, Dr. Borrero will discuss a recent World Bank funded project that looked at the causes, effects and potential solutions for erosion and coastal flooding at several sites in Seychelles. He will also discuss ongoing efforts to work with nature to preserve, protect and enhance Seychelles beaches, one of its most important and valuable assets.

Helena Sims

Helena is a marine biologist and conservation practitioner with 20 years of experience in the conservation of tropical ecosystems and MPA network expansion in the Western Indian Ocean region. She has a strong understanding of Small Island Developing States' environmental issues and development challenges with recognised capacity to develop and lead programs in alignment with national priorities. She has over a decade of experience in Marine Spatial Planning and in the management of national, regional and international projects with the capacity to replicate and scale them

up. She is currently board member of multiple non-government organisations. Some of the highlights of her career include being part of the team to finalise Seychelles' and the World's first debt restructuring for a marine area, to lead the operationalisation of

the Seychelles Conservation and Climate Adaptation Trust (SeyCCAT) in 2015-2016 and to develop the first and largest Marine Spatial Plan in the WIO, which includes meeting a 30 % marine protection goal. Ms Sims is currently the Project manager of the Seychelles Marine Spatial Plan (SMSP) initiative, at the International Non- Profit organisation, The Nature Conservancy (TNC) and she works very closely with SeyCCAT.

Sheena Talma

Sheena Talma is a marine biologist from the Seychelles, her work focusses on deep-sea ecosystems, fisheries and genetics. As a freelance consultant she works with several organizations both within her home country and internationally. Sheena is a NatGeo Explorer, an Ocean Voices Fellow and is currently pursuing a DPhil in deep-sea ecosystems. Sheena finds the most joy in working within the science to policy nexus and highlighting the relationship between nature and humans. She aspires to work with collaborators to garner more deep-sea scientists within the Western Indian Ocean Region and to further highlight the need for science to be led by a diverse group of partners.

James Lea

James is the chief executive officer of the Save Our Seas Foundation. He gained a first-class Honours degree in biological sciences from the University of Oxford and then volunteered as a shark researcher at the Bimini Biological Field Station. At Bimini he cut his teeth catching, tagging and tracking sharks, and working with them so closely consolidated his passion for sharks and motivated him to fight for marine conservation. James then moved to work as a research scientist for the Save Our Seas Foundation, before completing a PhD in marine biology at the University of Plymouth in collaboration with the D'Arros Research Centre. His primary research focus was a comprehensive tagging programme tracking almost 200 sharks of seven different species in Seychelles, aiming to determine the factors that drive their movement behaviour and use this knowledge to inform effective conservation strategies. He continues his research as part of the Evolutionary Ecology Group at the University of Cambridge. He is honoured to speak at the inaugural Seychelles Marine Science Symposium, where he will provide an overview of the work of the D'Arros Research Centre.

DEEP-SEA AND OCEAN SCIENCE MOOC 2024

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Special Session

What is SWIOFish3: South West Indian Ocean Fisheries Governance and Shared Growth 3 (SWIOFish3) is a 6-year program aiming to improve management of marine areas and fisheries in targeted zones and strengthen fisheries value chains in Seychelles. Developed by the World Bank and owned by the Ministry of Fisheries and the Blue Economy, SWIOFish3 supports the Seychelles' ambitions in marine conservation and long-term sustainable development.

What SWIOFish3 does: It provides robust scientific research, offers training to the community and government employees, brings additional financing to the public and private sectors, and helps develop management frameworks. In other words, SWIOFish3 supports activities that help to create a favourable business environment for the Seychelles' Blue Economy with sustainable fisheries at its core.

Why 3? SWIOFish3 is part of a wider regional program supporting the South West Indian Ocean countries in sustainably developing their fisheries. Within the SWIOFish Program, the first project, SWIOFish1 (2015), promoted regional cooperation for sustainable management of the region's fisheries. It also included national investments in the Comoros, Mozambique, and Tanzania. The second project, SWIOFish2 (2017), supported regional cooperation with a specific focus on the Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC), the Indian Ocean Artisanal Fishers Federation, and the group of African and Indian Ocean Developing Island States. SWIOFish2 included national investments in Madagascar.

The Republic of Seychelles is already part of the regional components of the first two SWIOFish projects through its active role in the IOTC and other regional organizations.

Why fisheries value chain? Value chain includes every service that creates value on the way towards the final product. In case of fisheries, it includes transportation, cold storage, packaging, processing, research, laboratory services and testing, marketing, distribution and more. All these links in the value chain offer commercial opportunities to the local community, yet they do not directly add pressure on the Seychelles' marine environment. Developing the value chain of fisheries can help promote local entrepreneurship, generate more business, and create a full-circle domestic service industry for the needs of local and international fishers.

What are the accomplishments of the SWIOFish3? SWIOFish3 created a wealth of knowledge and lessons learned to inform the future development of the Blue Economy in Seychelles and beyond. It also piloted some brand-new fundraising approaches. For example, the world's first Sovereign Blue Bond was issued by the government of Seychelles under the SWIOFish3 program in 2018. The Blue Bond raised US\$15 million from investors, which was split between the Development Bank of Seychelles (DBS) and the Seychelles Conservation and Climate Adaptation Trust (SeyCCAT). The DBS channelled its \$12 million into the Blue Investment Fund to provide affordable loans to local entrepreneurs looking to develop services for the fisheries sector; SeyCCAT channelled its \$3 million into a sister facility, the Blue Grants Fund, to offer grants to climate and marine conservation projects led by the community.

What the special session will achieve? Overall, the main aim of this special session is to disseminate information on what scientific research has been funded by the project and what has been the results.

Special Session

Marine plastic pollution in Seychelles: research results, education perspectives, and ways forward to continuously address this increasing threatening issue.

Marine plastic pollution is a well-known global threat to the ocean and the marine ecosystems. In Small Island Developing States (SIDS), such as the Seychelles, this issue has become an increasing threat for the marine and coastal environment and the communities that depend on the ocean for sustenance, tourism, and other social and economic activities (Newman et al., 2015; Werner et al., 2016). Actions towards mitigating this pollution, as well as research on the abundance of plastic debris and their impacts have gained momentum in the last eight years in the country, leading to many awareness activities, clean-ups, and research. The Ocean Project Seychelles has been one of the leading organisations working in that field, creating and implementation advocacy and awareness campaigns, educational activities, and several research projects since 2016. This special session on Marine plastic pollution in Seychelles wishes to showcase the research and work done in the country on this matter by The Ocean Project Seychelles and many other stakeholders and organisations, as well as highlight the importance of continuously addressing the issue through more research, education, policy implementation, and waste management. It aims to bring together local speakers to share their research and experience on this topic with each other and with the Symposium participants.

The Venue

EDEN BLEU
HOTEL
EDEN ISLAND • SEYCHELLES

The symposium is hosted by Eden Bleu conference facilities on Eden Island - <https://www.edenbleu.com/>. A centrally located venue that can accommodate hybrid and parallel sessions. There is a bus stop nearby and several taxi services outside the venue.

The conference room will be split in two for parallel sessions. Keynotes and welcomes will occur in room 1. In both rooms talks will be broadcast over zoom for online participants. The poster session will happen in Room 2. Zoom links will be sent in an email.

Lunches will be in the Eden Bleu restaurant. Tea and the cocktail evening will be based around the talk venue

Detailed agenda day 1

22nd May	Room 1	Room 2
07:00	registration open (all day)	
08:30	Welcome	
08:45	Opening by VIP	
09:00	Keynote 1 (20 minutes) - Jose Borrero (11)	
	Climate Change	SWIOFISH special session 1
09:30	Low average shoreline change rate in 51 years on the low-lying Aldabra Atoll - Annabelle Constance (63)	Blue Carbon Assessment for Mangrove Systems in Seychelles - Ameer Ebrahim (24)
09:40	Blue carbon stocks of Seychelles' largest mangroves - Laura Montano (104)	Processes and lessons learned from the development of Management Plans for sustainable use areas (MSP Zone 2) - Jude Bijoux (25)
09:50	Nitrogen isotope constraints on southwestern Indian Ocean variability in the 20th century - Alan Foreman (online) (74)	Gender assessment of the Blue Economy – Terence Crea (26)
10:00	Coastal Erosion: Coastal development and climate change in Seychelles - Jean Luc Mondon (103)	Employment Study and Capacity Needs Assessment for the Fisheries Sector in Seychelles - Sharif Antoine (27)
10:10	Sea-level rise could cause severe damages in the Seychelles - Dorothee Fehling (online) (73)	Economic and social importance of the Seychelles recreational fishery - Thomas Hecht (29)
10:20	questions	questions
10:40	tea	
	Turtles	SWIOFISH special session 2
11:10	Long term conservation proves that long lived species can be saved: the case of the Hawksbill turtle population on Cousin Island Special Reserve - Chris Tagg (125)	Perception survey of ocean governance, fisheries management and blue economy – Stuart Laing (UniSey team) (30)
11:20	Decades of declining trends in body size of nesting hawksbill and green turtles in Seychelles - Jeanne Mortimer (107)	Assessing Key Fish Stocks of Seychelles' Artisanal Trap and Line Fishery - James Robinson (online) (31)
11:30	Migration routes of hawksbill turtles (<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>) nesting on Sainte-Anne and Mahe, with location characterisation of their feeding grounds - Vinita Singaïny (122)	Seychelles sea cucumber survey 2021/22 – sample design, analysis of survey data and management recommendations - Tomothy Skewes and SFA (hybrid) (33)
11:40	Comparison of migrations of post-nesting hawksbill and green turtles satellite tracked from Alphonse and Saint Francois Atolls, Seychelles - Josep Nogués (online) (110)	Development of a Fishing Fleet Management and Licensing System – Jan Robinson (35)

11:50	Sea turtle nesting patterns in the Seychelles MPAs - Sophie Berlouis (52)
12:00	Understanding early reproductive failure in turtles and tortoises - Alessia Lavigne (95)
12:10	questions
12:30	Lunch
13:40	Keynote 2 (20 minutes) - Helena Sims (11)
	Blue Economy + MSP
14:10	Principles for transformative ocean governance - Amanda Lombard (96)
14:20	Red alert for southern Africa's Blue Economy: The need for regional cooperation for sustainable development - Donald Sparks (124)
14:30	Seychelles blue bond: Indebting ecological restructuring of fisheries - Arinç Kılıç (online) (90)
14:40	Marine spatial planning in South Africa: Algoa Bay, a pilot study - Tegan Carpenter-Kling (60)
14:50	Blue carbon in Seychelles' Blue Economy - Jerome Harlay (85)
15:00	questions
15:20	tea
	Aquaculture + coral restoration 1
16:00	Using farm-scale modelling to assess the feasibility of a commercial scale recirculating aquaculture system integrating sea urchins (<i>Tripneustes gratilla</i>) and seaweed (<i>Ulva</i>) - Bas de Vos (68)
16:10	Using photography to assess coral restoration success in the Cousin Island Special Reserve, Republic of Seychelles - Luca Saponari (118)
16:20	Moving towards regenerative aquaculture for coral conservation - Lize Fourie (75)
16:30	questions
16:40	questions
16:50	End of day

Developing the Seychelles fisheries value chain – Thomas Hecht (36)
Determination of post-harvest fish losses (PHFL) in Seychelles' fisheries value chains – Margaret Ally (38)
questions
Seabirds
Seabirds and mangroves on Aldabra Atoll, Seychelles - Jennifer Appoo (47)
Breeding Success monitoring of the Red-footed booby on Farquhar atoll, Seychelles - William McNeely (102)
Differences in foraging range between white-tailed tropicbirds breeding on inner and outer Seychelles islands - Orphéo Ensanayor-Volle (online) (70)
Marked differences in foraging area use and susceptibility to predation between two closely-related tropical seabirds - Annette Fayet (online) (72)
Dispersive migration and interbreeding distribution of White-tailed tropicbirds nesting on Aride Island, Seychelles - Gérard Rocamora (116)
questions
SWIOFISH special session 3
Evaluation of ecosystem services – The Nature Conservancy (online) (39)
Study on the Conservation Status of Threatened (IUCN criteria) and Protected Sharks and Rays to inform the Management of Seychelles Protected Area Network - Ashley Dias (41)
Socio-economic impact assessment of the Mahe Plateau trap and line fishery co-management plan - Jude Bijoux (43)
questions
questions

Detailed agenda day 2

23rd May	Room 1
08:30	Welcome
08:45	Opening by VIP
09:00	Keynote 3 (20 minutes) - James Lea (12)
	sharks
09:30	In the end it all comes down to poop: Diet assessment of two reef associated shark species at a remote tropical nursery site in the Indian Ocean - Ellie Moulinie (108)
09:40	Plankton soup: Investigating reef manta ray feeding ecology at an important aggregation site in Seychelles - Dillys Pouponeau (114)
09:50	The predator, the prey, and the polyp - Nico Fassbender (online) (71)
10:00	Effectiveness of coral reef restoration on shark and predatory fish communities in the Cousin Island Special Reserve, Republic of Seychelles - Charlotte Dale (65)
10:10	questions
10:20	questions
10:30	tea
	Marine Ecology
11:00	Integration of population genetics with oceanographic models reveals strong connectivity among coral reefs across Seychelles - April Burt (online) (57)
11:10	A glimpse of the macro and megafauna diversity and distribution in the Joint Management Area (JMA), Saya de Malha Bank - Gilberte Gendron (78)

Room 2
TOP special session 1
WIOMSA Marine Litter Monitoring Programme: Investigating the Abundance, Composition, and Seasonality of Marine litter in Seychelles. – Karine Young & Zara Pardiwalla (44)
Questions and Answers
Marine plastic pollution in the Inner Islands: Presentation of TOP Seychelles & MACCE pilot project for micro and macro plastic monitoring in rivers. - Bianca Marzocchi (44)
Marine plastic pollution in the Inner Islands: Beached plastic and other anthropogenic debris in the inner Seychelles islands - Alvania Lawen (44)
Marine plastic pollution in the Inner Islands: National Inventory on Chemicals and Hazardous Waste in Seychelles: Plastic pollution focus - Clifford Gonzalves (44)
Marine plastic pollution in the Inner Islands: Plastic pollution policies and waste management in Seychelles: state of the art and challenges – Estelle Lau Tee (44)
TOP special session 2
Marine plastic pollution in the Outer Islands: The Outer islands clean up - Karine Young & Natasha Burian (45)
Marine plastic pollution in the Outer Islands: Marine plastic debris & FADs in the Outer islands – Island Conservation Society (45)

11:20	A baseline assessment of fish diversity patterns within the Denis Island Zone 2 sustainable use marine protected area - Annia Marengo (98)
11:30	Rapid assessment of fish biodiversity in shallow water habitats of the Alphonse Group - Chris Mason-Parker (101)
11:40	Seabirds boost primary and secondary productivity on coral reefs - Casey Benkwitt (online) (50)
11:50	Increased resilience and a regime shift reversal through repeat mass coral bleaching - Nicholas Graham (online) (82)
12:00	Acoustic telemetry: conservation, questions, and collaboration in the outer islands - Eleanor Brighton (54)
12:10	questions
12:20	questions
12:30	Lunch
13:40	Keynote 4 (20 minutes) - Sheena Talma (12)
	Cetaceans
14:10	The last dugongs of Seychelles - population assessment at Aldabra Atoll - Caulvyn Bristol (55)
14:20	Influence of oceanographic features on habitat suitability of a tropical baleen whale species in a newly identified 'hotspot' off Seychelles - Michelle Caputo (59)
14:30	Into the shallows: atypical behaviour of the Risso's dolphin around the atoll of St. Joseph, Amirantes - Rachel Pool (113)
14:40	Unravelling the importance of the Republic of Seychelles for Whales and dolphins: implications for capacity building and conservation efforts - Jeremy Kiszka (online) (91)
14:50	Distribution and drivers of phytoplankton along the Saya de Malha Bank in the Western Indian Ocean - Nuette Gordon (81)

Marine plastic pollution in the Outer Islands: Marine plastic pollution on Aldabra and its surrounding area – Seychelles Islands Foundation (45)
Questions & Answers
Free time for room displays and outreach activities
Case study: A regional education programme: Captain Fanplastic - Seychelles implementation - Alice Mascarenhas, Magali Rocamora, Ruben Hazelet (45)
Questions & Answers
Free time for room displays and outreach activities
Free time for room displays and outreach activities
Fisheries
Effects of climate variability on tuna fisheries in the Indian Ocean - Francis Marsac (99)
Methods to identify and solutions to prevent dFAD impacts on coral reefs - Maria Uyarra (online) (127)
Climate change affects multiple coral reef fisheries ecosystem services - Sarah Martin (online) (100)
Implications of degraded coral reef habitats for artisanal fisheries in Seychelles - Mark Hamilton (online) (84)
Co-created mitigation solutions on the tropical tuna purse seiner FAD fishery - Inigo Krug (online) (93)

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	Aquaculture + coral restoration 2
15:30	Uncovering the relationship between light intensity and <i>Tripneustes gratilla</i> : implications for aquaculture - Shamira Payet (111)
15:40	Evaluation of an experimental grow-out protocol aimed at optimizing food conversion ratio to minimize the impact of aquaculture utilizing mangrove snapper (<i>Lutjanus argentimaculatus</i>) as a model organism - Lawrence Grant (83)
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- Development of a protocol for transporting live *Tripneustes gratilla* sea urchins - **Danilla Adonis** (46)
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Special Session Abstracts – SWIOFISH3

Blue Carbon Assessment for Mangrove Systems in Seychelles

Author: Consultancy Firm: Deakin University's Blue Carbon Lab, presented by Ameer Ebrahim

Marine ecosystems capture carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and store it in the form of elemental carbon, acting as a “carbon sink”. Carbon stored in marine waters, be it in deep oceans or in the shallow coastal areas, is called “blue carbon”. Another example of the blue carbon sinks are the mangroves that inhabit coastal areas. Mangroves trap 10 times more carbon than their terrestrial counterparts and at up to 40 times the speed. Hence, with Seychelles’ 2195 hectares of mangrove forests, the country possesses abundant coastal blue carbon storage opportunities.

However, the same coastal features make Seychelles extremely vulnerable to climate change impacts such as sea-level rise and tropical cyclones. Hence, removing heat-trapping carbon dioxide from the atmosphere to mitigate climate change is a priority for the country. In part, this can be realised through the protection and restoration of mangrove ecosystems.

While qualitative data on the structure and composition of Seychelles’ mangrove networks are already available, there remains a big gap in quantitative information related to carbon storage capacity. This study aims to address this by collecting baseline information on local mangrove attributes such as height, diameter at breast height, and organic carbon content in soil. The resulting values give insights into Seychelles’ blue carbon storage capacity and solidify the case for mangrove protection, conservation, and restoration.

Field sampling estimates revealed that Aldabra holds the highest total carbon stocks, marked at 67% of the country’s total. This is expected as it is also home to 80% of Seychelles’ mangrove forests. Overall, the mangroves store almost 700,000 tonnes of organic carbon, 70% of which are trapped in soils. This is equivalent to 2.5 million tonnes of atmospheric CO₂ removed from the atmosphere or 14,017 tonnes annually. In the national context, these coastal forests offset 3% of Seychelles’ annual CO₂ emissions.

Analysis of field samples further uncovered that Seychelles’ mangroves captured carbon at a rate of 313.48 tonnes C/hectare, while the global average is between 702 to 856 tonnes of carbon per hectare of mangrove forest. This significant difference between global and local values further emphasises the need for local assessments to more accurately gauge country-specific blue carbon potential to avoid overestimating its offsetting capacity.

Overall, the outcome of this study quantifies the climate mitigation potential of Seychelles’ mangrove forests using local field sampling results and clarifies the role they play in supporting Seychelles to achieve its Nationally Determined Contributions commitments.

Processes and lessons learned from the development of Management Plans for sustainable use areas (MSP Zone 2)

Jude Bijoux*, Johanna Johnson‡, Andrew Chint†, David J. Welch‡, Alison Green‡ and Dr Mari-Carmen Pineda‡.

Management plans for protected areas play a crucial role in ensuring the effective conservation and sustainable management of these ecologically valuable sites. Over a period of one year, the Seychelles went through the process of developing site management plans for the three largest Sustainable Use Areas designated under the Seychelles Marine Spatial Planning initiative. This included the Amirantes to Fortune Bank, Farquhar Archipelago and the Cosmoledo and Astove Archipelago Sustainable Use (Zone 2) Areas covering a total of 237,392 km² or approximately 17.56% of the Seychelles Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ). The first step in the management planning process was to define a process framework, which aligned with that of the Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) initiative, that set the principles and detailed the steps to be followed for the development of the plans and how stakeholders will be able to participate. The development of the Management Plans built on the extensive consultative processes and networks developed during the SMSP processes since 2014. A consultative process involving multiple and diverse stakeholders was conducted from September 2022 to August 2023. The second step was to define the key principles in collaboration with to guide the management plans development and implementation. This set the stage for stakeholders to define the priority issues, pressures and threats that were affecting the management of these areas and to define the goal and four overarching objectives for each area. The overarching objectives focussed on the ecology and biodiversity, governance, social and cultural, and economics. Allowable activities were defined by those that had been agreed as part of the SMSP initiative. Strategies and priority actions for implementation were identified by stakeholders to address key issues. Compliance and enforcement approach was then defined along with monitoring and surveillance requirements. A performance Measurement Framework with core performance indicators was then developed to guide the evaluation of the plans. A generic process framework was also developed to guide the preparation of management plans for other Sustainable Use Areas.

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Gender Assessment in the Blue Economy Sector

Author: GEM Consultancy – presented by Terence Crea

Despite gender equality being embedded in Seychelles' constitution, striving to provide equal opportunities for both men and women throughout its different sectors remains a challenge. To provide and extract more value from the country's workforce, it is important to understand the impacts of gender on Seychellois when accessing work opportunities, upskilling, and delivering optimal performance.

Through surveys participated by 22 organizations and establishments, this study focused on capturing the gender landscape across 4 main sectors of the blue economy, namely, Marine Security, Maritime/Coastal Tourism, Development/Shipping, and Education/Training. In doing so, the study aims to inform policy and engage stakeholders and the broader community to create a gender-equal environment for the Seychellois.

The results revealed that Seychelles' workforce consists of roughly 64% men and 36% women. Furthermore, more women (31%) landed managerial positions than men (21%). The majority of the respondents also completed at least their secondary education, with women being 1.3 times more likely to finish their university degrees than their male counterparts. Slightly more women (56%) also completed post-secondary studies than men (52%).

However, there's more to these numbers, as when diving into salary brackets, men still got paid higher than women overall. These layered findings require more thorough research to understand how wage disparity makes its way into the workforce. Among the main hypotheses were that women eventually leave the workforce to care for their families or that their careers are put to a halt during pregnancy.

Even without explicit institutional barriers, cultural norms also remain to weigh heavily on men and women, as they bear the stigma associated with their respective genders. For instance, women pursuing careers in Maritime/Coast Tourism report facing discrimination, while men suffer from negative stereotypes such as laziness and lacking motivation in schools, reportedly leading to poorer academic performance. Men also reported feeling marginalized and are allegedly facing substance and drug abuse problems as a result of difficulty in adjusting to changing gender norms. On the other hand, 4 in 10 women suffer from domestic abuse by their intimate partners, leading to the portrayal of men Seychellois as irresponsible fathers, further reinforcing media stereotypes.

More than decisively dismantling institutional barriers, these study's findings reveal that embedding gender equality also requires cultural work. Deeply seated gender norms continue to affect both men and women and it is necessary to develop strategies to address issues such as pay gaps, domestic violence, and substance abuse. Otherwise, no legal provisions would suffice in putting out the self-feeding fires that gender norms pass onto the Seychellois, from one generation to another.

Employment Study and Capacity Needs Assessment for the Fisheries Sector in Seychelles

Author: MRAG Consultancy Firm, presented by Sharif Antoine

Seychelles' fisheries and fisheries-supporting industries comprise a significant portion of the national economy and provide livelihoods to thousands of local households. Fisheries workers are engaged in activities such as artisanal line, trap, and net fishing; diving for sea cucumber; and industrial-scale purse seine and longline fishing. Supporting sectors and downstream activities include fisheries management, refrigeration, and machine operation and maintenance.

This study describes the current state of play in the fisheries sector and provides recommendations for its development. It also gathered data on COVID-19 pandemic-related benefits for fisheries workers to determine their level of dependency on government support.

The study conducted surveys using paper forms, web questionnaires, and mobile applications to collect information from 5,282 individuals employed in the fisheries and related sectors. 1,788 respondents represented the fisheries sector, most of which came from the artisanal sub-sector at 1,278; the remaining 3,494 respondents represented the non-fishing, supporting sub-sectors. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the sport fishery sub-sector experienced low tourist numbers and a significant gap in operations, resulting in most respondents classifying themselves as either inactive, in the process of selling their boat, or reporting privacy concerns. The study analyzed the responses across sectors, gender, age, nationality, employment status, occupation, education level, and wage.

The survey revealed a significant reliance on foreign labour to augment the local workforce. This is especially true for highly technical and skilled occupations in purse seine, longline, semi-industrial, and sea cucumber fishing sub-sectors and non-fishing sub-sectors that involve machine operation, refrigeration, and mechanical and electrical maintenance. The study noted that while the Seychelles Maritime College trains new artisanal fishers yearly, the completion of the course remains low resulting in few recruits into the sector. The survey also found that technical workers such as seamen, skippers, divemasters, mechanics, electricians, machinists, and fibreglass plant workers are in high demand across all fishing and related sectors.

Although not entirely a skills issue, the shift work required in the fisheries sector is also a significant concern for many Seychellois, with employers viewing foreign labor as more reliable and willing to undertake this work arrangement. The research also notes that higher wages and dedicated training could improve Seychellois' attitude towards working in the sector.

Another finding of the survey suggests that the three sub-sectors of artisanal fishing, processing, and transportation are facing an ageing workforce where the majority of workers belong to the 35-44, 45-54, and 55-64 age bands. In particular, the artisanal fishery sub-sector has a higher number of workers between 45-64 years. Younger workers aged between 18 and 24 seem to enter the workforce at a lower rate that cannot compensate for retiring workers. Respondents also noted substance abuse and better financial and lower-risk opportunities in other industries as factors that drive away youth participation in the fisheries and related sectors.

When asked to provide recommendations to encourage younger workers to join the fisheries industry, the respondents named better working conditions, higher wages, and more benefits protections compared to other sectors as the most influential factors. Education and training in fishing and environment-related subjects would also encourage younger workers to pursue a career in these sectors thanks to ample demand for skilled workers and opportunities for professional advancement.

When evaluating the gender component, the survey found that male workers in the fishing sector, and the transport and storage sub-sectors dominated both in the highest (> 83,000 SCR/month) and the lowest (< 5,805 SCR/month) wage bands, likely a result of these sectors being predominantly male and not necessarily due to gender-based disparities. Conversely, in the few instances of female employment in fishing, and transport and storage sub-sectors, women tend to command higher

wages compared to men. Meanwhile, in sub-sectors having more or less equal male and female participation, no gender pay gap was recorded.

The study also looked into the dependency of artisanal fishers on the government for their health insurance, sickness benefits, and pension contributions, and the impact of being registered with SFA on access to these benefits. 86 percent of respondents said they were registered with the SFA, 92 percent of which have a pension. In contrast, only 76 percent of the unregistered fishers contributed towards retirement. A larger gap is seen between the two cohorts in terms of participation in an insurance scheme with 91 percent of registered fishers having contributed compared to only 68 percent for unregistered fishers. Lastly, the survey found registered fishers were more likely to claim sickness benefits, with 97 percent of them having received such benefits compared to only 67% for unregistered fishers, suggesting that the SFA registered fishers are more aware of their right to sick benefits.

Given the fisheries sector's current status and capacity needs, the study recommends a multi-faceted approach to bolster the local workforce in line with the existing 2019 Fisheries Policy. The government must first identify critical skill gaps and, with the help of industry stakeholders, craft a comprehensive human development plan that prioritizes training and education to equip Seychellois with the necessary skills to participate fully and thrive in the sector. Furthermore, the government must put policies in place to encourage participation in fisheries and fisheries-related work via apprenticeship programs, targeted skills development, and certifications. Finally, the study recommends that the government continue to monitor and improve employment accessibility, implement labor standards, and promote advanced fisheries training to build a skilled fisheries workforce continuously.

Economic and social importance of the Seychelles recreational fishery

Author: Advance Africa Management Services (consultancy firm), presented by Prof. Thomas Hecht

Seychelles offers world-class recreational fishing that attracts both foreign and resident anglers. It is estimated that between 20 000 and 30 000 tourists and 8 500 residents participate in recreational angling in Seychelles each year.

The recreational fishery is a significant contributor to Seychelles' Blue Economy. A recently completed economic evaluation showed that total annual expenditures associated with the fishery were between USD 167 million and USD 196 million, and that it contributed USD 80 million to USD 94 million to annual income with a total annual economic impact of between USD 36 million and USD 48 million. In addition, the recreational fishery sector provides in the region of 1 100 and 1 200 jobs.

The fishery has a large spatial footprint, operating over the entire Mahé Plateau to beyond the drop-off and including some of the Outer Islands. Both boat-based and shore-based fishing is conducted.

Non-resident anglers made the largest contributions to Seychelles' economy. Non-resident anglers were typically very satisfied with their fishing trip experience, and primarily enjoyed the catchability of fish, as well as the exclusivity of fishing destinations, notably the Outer Islands.

The existence of the recreational fishery provides a recreational outlet for Seychelles residents. Residents' motivation for angling were primarily related to being close to nature, and the tranquillity and escape associated with angling. The sale of fish was of little importance in motivating fishing participation amongst resident anglers.

On average (and likely an underestimate as catches are often underreported), recreational fishers keep approximately 144 kg of fish per angler per year, comprised predominantly of demersal species. This equates to a theoretical total catch by resident recreational anglers of over 1 200 tonnes per annum (or about one third of the total artisanal catch).

The total potential loss associated with the introduction of bag limits was between USD 5.4 million and USD 21.0 million. The total potential loss associated with the introduction of size limits was between USD 1.04 million and USD 15.22 million. These impacts represent short-term losses and are likely to decrease as species recover.

Stakeholders generally agreed that a permitting/licensing scheme would contribute towards the sustainable management of the recreational fishery. The average price that non-resident anglers were willing to pay for continued access to the fishery was USD 231 amongst Outer Islands anglers, and USD 36 amongst Inner Islands anglers. The average price that resident anglers were willing to pay for continued access to the fishery was USD 61.

Perception survey of ocean governance, fisheries management and blue economy

Authors: Laing, S.C.S. (Stuart)¹, Etongo, D. (Daniel)¹, Antha, S. (Sylvanna)^{1,2}, Bristol, U. (Uvicka)¹ and Hoareau, K. (Kelly)^{1,3}

A nationally representative survey was conducted in Seychelles in 2022 to gauge the public perception of ocean governance, fisheries management, and the Blue Economy. The survey, commissioned by the Department of Blue Economy through the Third South West Indian Ocean Fisheries Governance and Shared Growth (SWIOFish3) Project, employed random sampling across the main islands of Mahé, Praslin, and La Digue, yielding 674 usable responses from 730 collected. The survey was developed initially by literature review, then built upon with focus group discussions, and finalised through a piloting exercise conducted by 10 trained enumerators. The enumerators then conducted supervised data collection, primarily on weekends, from June to September, 2022. Key findings indicated low or uncertain levels of self-reported knowledge of the key topics. Familiarity with the Blue Economy concept was high (93%), but with limited understanding of its specifics (12%). Awareness of Seychelles Marine Spatial Plan (SMSMP) and marine protected areas (MPAs) was low, with 45% and 18% respectively. However, satisfaction with MPAs (77%) and fisheries management (78%) was high among respondents. The overwhelming majority of respondents indicated the need for improved education and awareness of aquaculture (98%) and for minimum catch size limits for certain species (90%). TV was the primary news source for respondents (89%). The study offers nine recommendations, emphasizing enhanced education on fisheries, aquaculture, and the Blue Economy. It suggests public dissemination of results through focused media campaigns, particularly on TV, for wider reach and online/social media for younger demographics. These recommendations aim to improve public understanding and participation in marine resource management initiatives.

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Assessing Key Fish Stocks of Seychelles' Artisanal Trap and Line Fishery

Author: James Robinson

This assessment analyzed catch and effort data collected over 1990-2019 to determine the stock status of key artisanal fisheries in Seychelles. Fisheries included traps deployed by outboard vessels, which targeted reef-associated species in nearshore habitats, and handlines deployed by outboard and whaler-type vessels (lavenir, lekonomi, schooner, whaler), which targeted demersal and semi-pelagic species across the Mahé Plateau. These fisheries provide between 4,500 and 8,000 tonnes of catch per year, most of which is consumed in Seychelles, as well as high-economic value species (e.g. *Lutjanus sebae*) that are exported to international markets. Previous assessments have indicated that most of Seychelles' artisanal fisheries are overexploited, with catch rates and total landed catch decreasing as fishing effort has increased.

Catch rates in trap fisheries increased steadily from 1990-2019, coinciding with a moderate increase in total fishing effort. Catch rates of species groups, however, declined over time, suggesting individual species have declined in biomass, or are more spatially variable. Traps primarily targeted either cordonier (*Siganidae* sp., the 4th most landed species group across all artisanal fisheries) or a mixed group of reef-associated herbivores and invertivores. Total catch and effort data indicate that cordonier are currently being fished below sustainable limits, and have not experienced overfishing in Seychelles, likely due to their fast population growth rate and thus high resilience to fishing pressure. In contrast, the mixed reef fish group was above sustainable limits, though it is difficult to estimate fishing reference points for this group, which contains over 30 species with varying life history traits. The available biomass of these species has also changed as a result of mass coral mortality throughout the inner Seychelles, likely contributing to both increases and decreases in catch rates.

Handline fisheries comprised the majority of landed catch from artisanal vessels in Seychelles, mostly carangues (*Carangidae* species), jobfish, and bourgeois (*L. sebae*) landed by whaler-type vessels on the Mahé Plateau. Across all vessel types, the average handline catch rate declined between 2005-2019. Outboard vessels had the most widespread catch declines, with catch rates decreasing for 8 of the 12 targeted species groups, suggesting that populations at inshore fishing grounds have become depleted. In contrast, whaler-type vessels showed evidence of recovering catch rates for in carangues, jobfish and bourgeois, but consistent declines for other vieille and maconde (groupers species), capitaine (*Lethrinidae* species) and becune (*Sphyraenidae* species). Despite negative catch trends, analyses of total catch suggested that most whaler-type handline fisheries were operating at or above sustainable limits. These predictions were likely due to recent increases in total landed catch that suggest demersal and semi-pelagic populations have recovered from high fishing pressure over 2000-2010. Nevertheless, catch-based reference points should also be accompanied by fishery-independent observations, information on population structure, and fishing ground maps, which were not available. Ultimately, drivers of catch trends (recovery or decline) were not clear, while there was considerable uncertainty in catch based reference points. Fishing by whaler-type vessels accounted for the majority of handline catches, and thus regulation of these fleets will likely help to protect long-term artisanal catches in Seychelles.

Over 2000-2016, fishing effort remained constant for trap fisheries (number of traps deployed), whereas outboard handline effort has increased from 2012-2016 and whaler-type vessel effort has decreased since 2000. Increased biomass of trap target species has likely sustained increases in total trap catch, though changes to catch composition should be further investigated. For handlines, reduction of fishing pressure may have enabled key stocks to recover, resulting in recent increases in total catch. However, these species vary considerably in life history and in fishing selectivity, and it is unlikely that all offshore stocks have recovered to similar levels.

Seychelles' artisanal fisheries do not presently have harvest controls. Given the history of overexploitation and key economic and food security importance of these fisheries, the report recommends investigation of harvest controls and/or key habitat protection for four key stocks: carangues (handlines), bourgeois (handline), jobfish (handline), and cordonier (trap). These four groups are represented by one or more species with similar life history, are major contributors to total

catch, and represent the most frequently caught species in three fisheries types (handline-pelagic, handline-demersal, trap-coastal). Harvest controls must be designed with consideration of the species' life history and fishery dynamics, for example using size limits to minimize risk of growth overfishing of semi-pelagics, and protecting key habitats for aggregating species such as *L. sebae* and *Siganus sutor*. Routine biological monitoring of these species will be necessary to inform appropriate management measures (e.g. fishery-independent surveys; size and age estimates; spatial analysis of fishing grounds, aggregations and spawning habitat).

Finally, the Seychelles Fishing Authority's catch assessment survey has provided a rich source of information on catch and effort across diverse and productive fishing fleets. These data will become increasingly important for gauging the effectiveness of harvest control rules, and minimizing risk of overfishing. It is recommended to fund additional fisheries science expertise within SFA, specifically to analyse catch data and help to transition the catch database into a format for rapid, real-time stock assessments.

Seychelles sea cucumber survey 2021/22 – sample design, analysis of survey data and management recommendations

Author: TIM SKEWES CONSULTING

The commercialization of sea cucumber fishery in Seychelles began in the early 1990s and has since provided livelihood and income to fishers and communities involved in their processing and trade. However, the industry experienced declines in catch in the latter years of the succeeding decade, prompting the Seychelles Fishing Authority (SFA), in 1999, to introduce management measures for the industry, including limiting the number of non-transferrable fishing licenses to 25, limiting the number of divers per license to four, and requiring licensees to submit catch data.

The first full-scale stock study, conducted in 2004 at 246 sites across the Amirantes and Mahe Plateau, concluded that the two sea cucumber species, sandfish (*Holothuria scabra*) and surf redfish (*Actinopyga mauritiana*), were overexploited, while the white teatfish (*Holothuria fuscogilva*) and flower teatfish (*Holothuria sp. type pentard*) were fully exploited. The succeeding stock surveys, which were limited in scope and relied on mandated logbook data, revealed an overall decline in several species of sea cucumber with the number of pentard appearing stable.

This study conducted in 2021-2022 aims to update stock data and inform the development of new management measures for the sea cucumber fishery industry.

The survey estimated the white teatfish population to be only 8.3% of the 2004 stock estimate, continuing the declining trend observed in 2011. The 2021 catch-per-unit-effort (CPUE) also decreased significantly to 14.4% of its value in 2004 and is at its lowest level in all surveys conducted from 2004. The decline in white teatfish densities in the survey sites, low population, and all-time low CPUE indicate that the species may be below the level of recruitment impairment.

Focusing on the flower teatfish species, the survey found that its population has declined to 59% of its original estimate in 2004. Meanwhile, the CPUE exhibits greater variability compared with the survey estimates but shows an overall downward trend and currently is at 47.4% of its 2004 value. Despite the decrease in these values, however, they still represent a remarkably stable population given the fishery focus on this particular species of sea cucumber, especially compared to the white teatfish. Still, with the downward trajectory of its population numbers, the current fishing levels are likely to be unsustainable.

Displaying an increase of 52% over its 2004 estimate, the prickly redfish (*Thelenota ananas*) was the only major sea cucumber species surveyed to have gotten a boost in its population. However, the CPUE was more variable and showed a very weak temporal trend with the 2021 value landing on the lower end of the scale. Overall, the high population increase indicates that current fishing levels would not have a significant detrimental effect on the prickly redfish population.

The survey also found that the black teatfish (*Holothuria nobilis*) population has decreased to 84% of its 2004 value and continued a downward trend first observed during the 2011 survey. The CPUE data, only available up until 2016, showed a 91% decrease from its 2004 value. These figures indicate that the black teatfish is still in a depleted state, despite ceasing fishing of this species in 2018. However, higher densities were monitored compared to the all-time low observed in 2017, suggesting that the population is recovering.

Overall, the sea cucumber population estimate in 2021-2022 is 77.7 million, a 30% decrease from the value recorded in 2004. While it is fortunate that some species, such as the prickly redfish, appear to become resilient to heavy fishing pressure, most sea cucumbers experienced a decline in their populations and show signs of overexploitation.

Therefore, the study recommends putting in place species management measures to ensure a sustained catch over the long term. For the white teatfish, an immediate cessation of fishing activities is recommended to allow for the population to recover to sustainable levels and monitor its recovery after 3 years for another assessment. Meanwhile, to prevent the flower teatfish from sliding down to a

level where recruitment impairment could occur, a 10% reduction in the fishing quota is recommended. This assessment should be used as the basis to develop specific management actions for the pentard population. Despite the increase in prickly redfish population, additional stock modeling must be carried out using current surveys and fishery logbook data to see the impacts of possible increases in fishing pressure for this particular species. With the black teatfish population still continuing to slide down, the study recommends continuous monitoring with eventual fishing reopening once the population reaches sustainable levels. For underexploited and recovered species, experimental quotas can be reintroduced, contingent on additional catch reporting requirements.

Concerning crafting strategies and plans, the study recommends introducing and promoting standard species names and crafting a comprehensive fisheries species identification guide to help future research and management endeavors. Additionally, the study urges authorities to develop multispecies harvest strategies that outline the objectives, performance indicators, reference levels, and control measures to guide sustainable fishing practices. Implementing a system of closed areas in deeper non-reef regions, targeting 30% of each fishery area, is recommended to protect fish stocks. Finally, the study recommends that the authorities look into the potential of rotational harvest schemes and stock enhancement approaches, such as reseedling and broodstock aggregation, to ensure the long-term viability of the sea cucumber fishery in Seychelles.

Development of a Fishing Fleet Management and Licensing System

Presenter: Jan Robinson

The frame survey of the Seychelles domestic fleet, which took place between August and November 2017 was part of the larger project to develop a fishery-specific fishing fleet management and licensing system.

It aimed to capture information on all vessels, not limited to the boats already licensed through the SFA. This group of licensed vessels is made up of around 550 boats. A second group are the hire craft vessels engaged in sports fishing and other sea related activities. The estimated number of the vessels is 600, although not all are engaged in fishing. According to the databases provided by the Tourism Department, there are currently 250 boats with a licence to engage in sports fishing. The final recreational group has no licence and registration requirements. They are privately owned, and ownership is largely unknown. Another group of vessels are the visiting yachts and live-aboard, including those operating in the outer lying islands. Data on the visiting yachts could be ascertained from the Seychelles Maritime Safety Administration (SMSA).

The survey counted and recorded a total of 1,115 boats of which 742 were commercial fishing boats, 168 hire craft (sports fishing) and 116 recreational boats. There were 95 boats with no data and considered as “unknown”. In addition, there were missing information for each of the boats recorded. The survey covered 114% of the commercial fishing boats, 78% of the hire craft boats (charter boats) and 46.4 % of the recreational boats. The overall coverage of the fleet was estimated at 110%. The Eden Marina was eventually surveyed but data on the operations of the vessels were largely limited.

The number and types of boats was dominated by Mini Mahé for both the commercial fishing boats and the recreational fleet. The so-called “pleasure craft” type of vessel dominated the sport fishing fleet. From a capacity management perspective, it is recommended for the pleasure craft/hire craft category to be disaggregated further. The boats from the different fleet sub-sectors exhibited different patterns in their activities. The commercial fishing boats had a higher proportion of full-time vessels (<60%) while sports vessels recorded 16% undertaking part time fishing and 27% on a full-time basis. Victoria was the principal landing site for the commercial fishing boats followed by Providence, Bel Ombre and Praslin. In the case of hire craft, Providence had the highest number of vessels (42) followed by Bel Ombre (26) and Providence (16).

The average size of the boats was estimated at 10.1 m length over all (LOA). The greatest number of boats was in the range 4-7 m which reflects the Mini-Mahé type boats, the most popular boats in Seychelles. The second most popular size of boats were around 16 m which relate to schooner/semi-industrial type vessels. In the case of Hire Craft, the majority of vessel were between 4 and 10 m in length with mean length of 5.6 metres. A significant number of hire craft vessels did not provide their length overall. The average engine capacity of the commercial fishing boat for the outboard and inboard were estimated at 80 HP and 168 HP respectively. The proportion of outboard and inboards engine was estimated 45% and 24% respectively. The average hire craft engine capacity at 316 HP was almost twice that of the commercial fishing boats. The hire craft were on average undertaking fishing for 6 days per month and the recreational fleet 3 days per month. The average minimum and maximum catch for the hire craft was 24 kg and 80 kg per fishing trip.

Developing the Seychelles fisheries value chain

Authors: Advance Africa Management Services, presented by Prof. Thomas Hecht

The development of Seychelles' blue economy is the focus of the government's long-term strategy of promoting diversification, resilience, and sustainability of the economy. Central to this initiative is enhancing the country's fisheries sector through the promotion and development of aquaculture and other value-adding activities such as locally based seafood processing. To support the development of Seychelles' seafood value chains, this review critically assessed the current state of play of these value chains, identified the challenges and capacity needs they face, and proposed the Seafood Value Chain Development and Upgrading Strategy to position Seychelles into a regional processing hub.

The seafood value chains in Seychelles are diverse in their scale, species, and the products processed. They are an essential component of domestic food security and supply cost-effective, culturally appropriate seafood to the domestic market. Additionally, high-value, niche seafood products are sold to the hotel and restaurant and exported to premium international markets.

The government has prioritized the development of these value chains to derive more value from finite fisheries resources. Excluding the IOT tuna canning facility, government infrastructure investments in seafood processing facilities have resulted in 21,867 Mt per annum of operational, 6,550 Mt per annum of complete but not yet operational, and 31,631 Mt per annum of pipeline (to be completed by the end of 2020) processing capacities. If successfully operationalized in the coming years, the capacity offered by these facilities could help establish Seychelles as a regional processing hub.

However, the development of processing capacity is contrasted by a tightening of raw material supplies from the fisheries. Notably, the Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC) yellowfin quota for the West Indian Ocean is set to proportionately reduce the entire region's tuna catch from the industrial purse seine fleet by an estimated 80,000 Mt annually. Landings in Seychelles by the industrial longline fleet remain immaterial. The artisanal fishery is considered over-exploited, and catches are declining. The only fishery with expansion potential is the semi-industrial fishery, which is unaffected by the IOTC yellowfin tuna quota and includes species that are considered to be currently under-exploited – particularly spanner crab.

Securing the future supply of raw materials to the value chains is a critical driver of success. The Policy for the Management of Bycatch in Seychelles, which required the landing of bycatch from all fishing fleets, has added a new source of raw material for local seafood processors. The processors have responded swiftly by developing capacity, products, and markets in line with increasing supplies.

The bycatch policy will be strengthened by the Landing Regulations proposing that bycatch, and a portion of the target catch, should be landed and retained in the Seychelles by flagged and licensed vessels. Meanwhile, the imminent development of the aquaculture sector will add to supply volumes and diversify the seafood products available to the value chains. In particular, the pearl oyster farming and sea cucumber ranching segments have been strategically prioritized.

The development strategy proposed by the current review identified 26 seafood processing value chains in Seychelles and prioritized 13 for further analyses based on their potential for growth. By zooming into the traded volumes, activities of clustered value chain actors, costs and profit margins, and risk elements, the review has identified vital interventions specific to each value chain and the corresponding costs.

Finally, the review recommends the following overarching strategies aimed at developing in parallel critical aspects of each value chain:

- **Resource Strategy:** 'Secure the resource base and improve local access to raw material'. Three plans bolster the Resource Strategy. The "R&D Plan" aims to establish R&D as a solid platform to base all MCS activities. The "Landings Plan" seeks to ensure the landing of

bycatch and target catch from all Seychelles fisheries and vessels under its flag and fishing in its EEZ. The “Access Plan” recognizes the need for access to raw materials landed in Seychelles to be transparent and for prices to be determined in a market-led manner.

- Infrastructure Strategy: ‘Operationalise infrastructure to support medium-term capacity requirements’. The Infrastructure Strategy contains three plans. The “Bel Ombre/Providence Plan” provides for refitting processing facilities at these locations according to emerging processing opportunities. The “Industrial Facilities Plan” proposes the development of ULT freezing capacity at the industrial ports. The “Airport Plan” allows for upgrading perishable handling facilities at the international airport.
- Market Strategy: ‘Improve market intelligence as a basis for product-market activities’. The Market Strategy incorporates the “Market Intelligence Plan,” which aims to improve access to critical market data and trends in a quickly circulated format. The “Branding Plan” seeks to develop the Seychelles brand in fisheries products beyond wholesale.
- Products Strategy: ‘Optimize the Seychelles basket of products for target markets’. The Products Strategy looks at developing the necessary skills and technologies to support the processing and manufacturing of uniquely formulated products in line with target market requirements.
- Certification Strategy: ‘Underpin the Seychelles brand with globally value certifications’. The need for certification as a critical requirement underpinning the Seychelles brand has been recognized, and plans have been formulated to address requirements at the sustainability, retailer, labelling, and food safety levels.
- Species Strategy: ‘Expand and diversify the species offering of the Seychelles’. The species strategies align with identified interventions of the prioritized value chains.

The complete implementation of these strategies and their underlying plans total an investment value of US\$1,705m for short-term capacity limitations and a further US\$14,425m to expand and enhance the prioritized value chains to the targeted outcomes.

Determination of Post Harvest Fish Losses (PHFL) in Seychelles Fisheries Value Chains

Presenter: Margaret Ally

In 2020 a survey carried out by SFA showed that around 24,025 kg of fish waste are disposed at the landing filled every month. The data Collected only captured 6 of the 10 local fish processors. A consultancy work was carried out in 2023 to assess PHFL in the Seychelles fisheries value chain focusing mainly on the artisanal and semi-industrial sector. The three main objectives of this study were to; i) Characterization and quantification of PHFL throughout the fisheries supply chain, focusing on the nearshore artisanal and semi-industrial sectors; (ii) examine new technologies and practices to reduce PHFL within the Seychelles and (iii) Provision of recommendations for mitigation measures to reduce PHFL, inclusive of potential business opportunities and economic gain from investing in the processing of fisheries by-product.

Upon mapping, it was identified that PHFL exists around the entire supply chain which includes On-Board Vessels, at Disembarkation upon processing, at local fish markets and fish mongers. To reduce PHFL along the different segments of the value chain, the study identified a range of technologies and potential measures that can be taken. These includes;

- I. setting-up handling standards for both artisanal and semi-industrial and providing capacity training to fisherman on how to ensure that their fish remains of high quality upon landing.
- II. Changing of legislations to reduce waste disposal in landfills.
- III. Greater monitoring and enforcement at different stages along the value chain
- IV. Certification in the sustainable use of fish waste and waste streams
- V. Maintenance of cold chain: (i) insufficient ice availability; (ii) uneven distribution of available ice; and (iii) lack of space on-board constraining amount of ice.
- VI. National investment in larger ice machines able to produce higher volumes of ice and in additional areas of the Seychelles.
- VII. Providing avenues for use of waste resources (foster new business ventures). This will provide greater value to fish waste.
- VIII. Development of suitable processing facilities
- IX. Proper storage system for waste on vessel to allow for by-products

Evaluation of Ecosystem Services

Author: The Nature Conservancy (online)

The Republic of Seychelles ranks among the most ocean-dependent economies on earth, with its population of some 100,000 people relying heavily on ocean and coastal ecosystems for income, employment, health, and well-being. Maintaining healthy ocean ecosystems and using their resources sustainably is a crucial pillar of the Seychelles' Blue Economy strategy.

Through an inclusive and equitable consultation process with stakeholders, the country developed a comprehensive system of marine protected areas (MPAs), which covers over 444,000 km² or 33% of the country's total maritime jurisdiction. Combined with pre-existing protected areas, this MPA system developed under the Seychelles' Marine Spatial Plan (SMSP) is critical for harnessing ecosystem services provided by marine and coastal areas.

This study quantifies and maps natural capital nationwide before assessing its coverage using the current protected areas system. Such data can enable subsequent assessment of where that capital is likely being "spent down" the fastest or where it is relatively safe from threats. Key findings from the modeling and stakeholder review highlight the contributions of Seychelles' protected areas to ecosystem services and reveal the following:

1. **Ecosystems:** The Seychelles' MPA system includes a vast expanse of deep ocean space with rich pelagic ecosystems. In addition, it includes 89% of shelf waters (<200m depth), 80% of all beaches, 92% of mangroves, 90% of coral reefs, 78% of granitic reefs, and 85% of seagrasses.
2. **Blue Carbon:** Every protected area in Seychelles contains blue carbon from either seagrass, mangroves, or both, with the total blue carbon amount in protected areas estimated at 156.7 million metric tons (mt). The numbers are dominated by the contribution of seagrasses, most notably from the Mahé Plateau.
3. **Coastal Protection:** In Seychelles, approximately 90% (1,149 km) of shorelines benefit from protection by fringing coral reefs, with 77% (889 km) of these shorelines located in or adjacent to protected areas, far from human habitation. Of the 44,280 people living in low-lying (<30m) coastal areas, only about 18% receive risk reduction from reefs within protected areas.
4. **Artisanal Fisheries:** Artisanal fisheries substantially contribute to food security and the local economy, with a total catch of 4500 to 8000 Mt between 1990 and 2019 (Robinson, 2021). This is equivalent to SCR 169 million (US\$12.3 million). From 2007 to 2016, around 37% of the catch was through small outboard boats, while the remaining 63% was extracted through larger, vessel management system (VMS)-tracked vessels. To add a more locally relevant dimension to these numbers, the study estimated the degree of fishing effort required per location and based the relative values of fishing locations on this data. According to the results, Seychelles Protected Areas currently cover 89% of fishing areas traversed by VMS-tracked vessels but only 27% of areas where smaller outboard vessels are used.
5. **Recreation and Tourism:** Within Seychelles, we estimate that coral reefs generate US \$51.5 million annually from on-reef activities such as snorkelling and diving, which attract the equivalent of 30,156 visitors to the country. Beaches in Seychelles are estimated to generate a combined total of US \$160 million in tourism expenditure annually, with 94,000 visitors attracted specifically to the natural aspects of Seychelles' beaches. These represent spending and visits that would be at risk if the natural values of these beaches were to be degraded. Of these, we estimate that 34% of all on-reef tourism and 15% of all tourism associated with nature-dependent beaches are supported specifically by Seychelles' Protected Areas. The poor representation of nature-dependent beaches within the Seychelles' Protected Area System partly reflects the focus on protected areas away from the granitic Seychelles and the fact that beaches may fall between terrestrial and marine spaces and not be effectively covered by either.

Overall, this work supports the adaptive management of Seychelles' waters. The process of quantifying ecosystem services provides us with a reference base against which changes can be evaluated going forward, and management actions can be adapted as necessary. Our maps cover some of the most critical ecosystem services in the Seychelles, and they show a generally comprehensive coverage of these services by the new and extensive protected areas network. The network is particularly comprehensive over the atolls and shallow banks where most of all values are incorporated into MPAs. By contrast, some of the highest individual values, notably for small-scale fishing, coastal protection, recreation, and tourism, have lower levels of coverage in protected areas.

The ecosystem service data generated through this project can strengthen existing knowledge and create new understanding, filling knowledge and data gaps on human uses that had been less widely considered or mapped. The results of this analysis suggest that, in general, Seychelles' protected areas make a very strong contribution toward preserving the values that underpin the nation's Blue Economy. We highlight outstanding ecosystem service values within marine protected areas that can help guide the development of future management plans and potential gaps where the protected area system may not adequately cover important services for the long-term sustainability of these values.

Study on the Conservation Status of Threatened (IUCN criteria) and Protected Sharks and Rays to inform the Management of Seychelles Protected Area Network

Author: John Nevill, presented by Ashley Dias

Seychelles harbors various elasmobranch species, such as sharks and rays, fulfilling crucial roles in boosting tourism and maintaining ecological balance. Seeing the need to protect these fish stocks and following several international obligations, Seychelles has enacted several national legislative measures and action plans. These measures aimed to evaluate the status of elasmobranch populations, plan and implement conservation interventions, and promote their sustainable use.

In its first National Plan of Action for the Conservation and Management of Sharks 2007-2010, the country has tagged its national elasmobranch fishery as overexploited and depleted. Meanwhile, the second iteration of this planning initiative resulted in the listing of 82 species of elasmobranch occurring in Seychelles, with the number later refined to 73 species after undergoing review and taxonomic revisions. Of the 73 species, the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) has classified 46 (63%) as threatened worldwide, i.e., species listed as Vulnerable, Endangered, or Critically Endangered on the IUCN Red List. Meanwhile, five other species are classified as Data Deficient. Despite these factors, the country only lists the whale shark (*Rhincodon typus*) as protected under Seychelles law.

While published data on the species-specific elasmobranch species in Seychelles are scarce, according to the Seychelles Fishing Authority, the general information indicates that some species populations have declined from historical levels, and others may have been locally extinct. As such, in aid of the accounting of elasmobranch species in Seychelles, the current project aims to assess the catch of threatened species in the local artisanal fishery industry and formulate recommendations grounded on existing national legislation and international commitments. The project conducted catch surveys in Victoria Market, fisher partner landing sites, and several key landing sites from August 2021 to September 2022. The assessment also used separate standardized measurement protocols for sharks and rays to identify the species. The assessment results led to the development of morphological and length-weight models to enable a rapid monitoring protocol for similar activities in the future.

During the survey period, the study recorded 20 elasmobranch species, consisting of 12 shark, 7 ray, and 1 guitarfish species. Eighty-four percent of the shark catch belonged to 3 species, namely, blacktip (*C. limbatus*), grey reef (*C. amblyrhynchos*), and scalloped hammerheads (*S. lewini*). This figure translates to 83% by weight. Meanwhile, ray catch consisted mainly of 2 species, with ocellated eagle ray (*A. ocellatus*) and shortfin devil ray (*M. kuhlii*) constituting 95% of the catch numerically and 92% by weight.

For the species that exhibited a good population spread, from juvenile to adult, in the catch surveys, namely *C. amblyrhynchos*, *C. limbatus*, *S. Lewin*, *R. australiae*, *A. ocellatus*, and *M. kuhlii*, the mean size of the specimens caught for each species was substantially lower below the size of maturity. This crucial finding suggests that growth overfishing or the excessive fishing of juveniles occurs in Seychelles' waters. Except for *C. amblyrhynchos*, the study also found that the catch of juveniles predominantly resulted from illegal fishing for sharks with nets. Furthermore, the study also found a separate unpublished survey conducted from 2013 to 2018, which showed a decrease in mean sizes for *C. amblyrhynchos* and a significant decline of mature females, indicating potential excessive catch of breeders or recruitment overfishing.

The survey and literature review findings support the current understanding of a depleted shark fishery and ongoing catch decline and highlight the need for a more precautionary approach toward elasmobranch fishery management. Given these considerations, the current study provides the following recommendations:

Fishery management and monitoring recommendations:

- full enforcement of the ban on fishing for sharks with nets
- development and institution of minimum fishery retention sizes for sharks and rays
- assessment of critical elasmobranch habitats and their incorporation into the next iteration of the Seychelles Marine Spatial Plan
- relaunch of the Seychelles National Plan of Action for the Conservation and Management of Sharks
- institution of systematic, continued, species-based elasmobranch catch monitoring

Species-based recommendations:

- full legal protection of 6 species of elasmobranch in line with Seychelles' existing commitments under the Convention on Migratory Species
- full legal protection of all 3 species of thresher shark (*Alopiidae*) in line with Seychelles' existing commitments under the Indian Ocean Tuna Commission
- full legal protection of the bowmouth ray (*R. ancylostoma*) due to its scarcity and Critically Endangered status
- licensing and strict control of the Hammerhead (*Sphyrnidae*) fishery
- development of species recovery plans for blacktip reef shark (*C. melanopterus*), sandbar shark (*C. plumbeus*), and sicklefin lemon shark (*N. acutidens*)

Some facts for potential highlighting:

- mean size of the specimens caught for the following elasmobranch species, *C. amblyrhynchos*, *C. limbatus*, *S. Lewin*, *R. australiae*, *A. ocellatus*, and *M. kuhlii*, was substantially lower below the size of maturity
- growth overfishing (excessive fishing of juveniles) and recruitment overfishing (excessive fishing of breeders) threaten elasmobranch fishery in the Seychelles

Socio-economic impact assessment of the Mahé Plateau trap and line fishery co-management plan

Jude P. Bijoux* and Karine Rassool‡

In fisheries management, it is important to regularly assess the impact of management action on fish stocks, ecosystems and habitats as well as on the fishers and other stakeholders along the fishery value chain. On the 1st January, 2022, the Seychelles started the implementation of the Fisheries (Mahé Plateau Trap and Line Fishery) Regulations, 2021 as part of the implementation of the Seychelles Mahé Plateau Trap and Line Fishery Co-management Plan. The regulations introduced several measures which included output controls (minimum retained length, bag limits) and technical measures (trap limit, gear/time restrictions, gear registration requirements for fish traps). The better known of these measures included a minimum retained size limit of 32 cm fork length for emperor red snapper (*Lutjanus sebae*; bourzwa) and green jobfish (*Aprion virescens*; zob gri). As implementation of the management plan obtained financial support from the World Bank, the World Bank's Process Framework was immediately triggered. This framework provides the criteria and procedures to be followed when a sub-project activity is identified as having a potentially adverse socioeconomic impact on existing rights, assets or livelihoods. To assess whether the new regulations was having any impacts on Project Affected Persons (PAPs), a study was conducted between February and April 2024 to assess the degree of support and determine the socioeconomic impacts of these measures on the public, small-scale fishers and semi-industrial longline vessel owners. As part of the study three surveys were undertaken with members of the public (n=210), small-scale fishers (n= 51) and semi-industrial longline vessel owners. Results indicate that measures concerning minimum retained size limits were well known among the public and fishers, but that the other measures were less known. The majority of the members of the public and fishers surveyed were supportive of the measures for reason of ensuring sustainability and did not report any major economic, social, cultural or mental impacts resulting from the implementation. Semi-industrial longline vessel owners were not affected by the demersal species bag limit as they are not dependent on demersal species for their livelihoods. The majority of fishers claimed that the measures are acceptable and that it should be enforced by the SFA and requested for more presence of SFA staff on the field. Fishers claimed that there are other measures in the fisheries that is affecting their trade much more than these measures that the SFA should focus on including issues with the availability of inputs such as bait and ice and the price of fishing gears, as well as issues regarding an exploding population of sharks which is taking a substantial proportion of the catch of line fishers. The survey indicates that a Livelihood Restoration Plan (LRP) is not required at this stage and that policy should address ensuring that fishers have available inputs to go fishing.

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Special Session Agenda - The Ocean Project Seychelles

Marine plastic pollution in Seychelles: research results, education perspectives, and ways forward to continuously address this increasing threatening issue.

Marine plastic pollution is a well-known global threat to the ocean and the marine ecosystems. In Small Island Developing States (SIDS), such as the Seychelles, this issue has become an increasing threat for the marine and coastal environment and the communities that depend on the ocean for sustenance, tourism, and other social and economic activities (Newman et al., 2015; Werner et al., 2016). Actions towards mitigating this pollution, as well as research on the abundance of plastic debris and their impacts have gained momentum in the last eight years in the country, leading to many awareness activities, clean-ups, and research. The Ocean Project Seychelles has been one of the leading organisations working in that field, creating and implementation advocacy and awareness campaigns, educational activities, and several research projects since 2016. This special session on Marine plastic pollution in Seychelles wishes to showcase the research and work done in the country on this matter by The Ocean Project Seychelles and many other stakeholders and organisations, as well as highlight the importance of continuously addressing the issue through more research, education, policy implementation, and waste management. It aims to bring together local speakers to share their research and experience on this topic with each other and with the Symposium participants.

Agenda:

9h30-9h50: WIOMSA Marine Litter Monitoring Programme – Investigating the Abundance, Composition, and Seasonality of Marine litter in Seychelles.

- Presentation of the Project, Methodology, Results, and Recommendations [10min]
- Questions & Answers [10min]

Speakers:

Victoria Alis – The Ocean Project Seychelles

Zara Pardiwalla – The Ocean Project Seychelles

9h50-10h40: Marine plastic pollution in the Inner Islands of Seychelles

- Presentation of TOP Seychelles & MACCE pilot project for micro and macro plastic monitoring in rivers [10min]
- Presentation National Inventory on Chemicals and Hazardous Waste in Seychelles: Plastic pollution focus [10min]
- Presentation “Beached plastic and other anthropogenic debris in the inner Seychelles islands” [10min]
- Presentation Plastic Pollution Policies & Waste Management in Seychelles: state of the art and challenges [10min]
- Questions & Answers. [10min]

Speakers:

Bianca Marzocchi – The Ocean Project Seychelles

Cliff Gonzalves – National Chemicals and Hazardous Waste Expert

Alvania Lawen – Environmentalist and Parley for the oceans coordinator

Estelle Lau Tee – LWMA

----- 10h40-11h00: Tea break (20min) -----

11h00-11h40: Marine plastic pollution in the Outer Islands of Seychelles

- The Outer Islands Clean up – TOP Seychelles. [10min]
- Marine plastic debris & FADS in the Outer islands – Island Conservation Society. [10min]
- Marine plastic pollution on Aldabra and its surrounding area – Seychelles Islands Foundation. [10min]
- Questions & Answers. [10min]

Speakers:

Karine Young & Natasha Burian – The Ocean Project Seychelles
Island Conservation Society
Seychelles Islands Foundation

11h40-11h50: Free time for room displays and outreach activities

11h50-12h10: Case study - Marine plastic pollution education and awareness in Seychelles: the Captain Fanplastic Programme.

- A regional educational programme: Captain Fanplastic - Seychelles implementation [10min]
- Questions & Answers. [10min]

Speakers:

Alice Mascarenhas – The Ocean Project Seychelles
Magali Rocamora – The Ocean Project Seychelles
Ruben Hazelet – Soapbox SA

12h10-12h30: Free time for room displays and outreach activities

Scientific Abstracts

Development of a protocol for transporting live *Tripneustes gratilla* sea urchins

Type: poster

Danilla Adonis¹, Shamira Payet¹, Bas de Vos^{1,2}

Tripneustes gratilla, a species of sea urchin, are highly valued in the marine economy due to their prized gonads, known as “roe”. Roe is nutritionally rich and highly demand as a culinary delicacy primarily in the East. Due to their high value and fast growth rates, *T. gratilla* has been recognised as highly suitable for aquaculture in the Seychelles. Transporting sea urchins alive is necessary for both logistical purposes during the aquaculture processing chain and for achieving the maximum value at markets. However, the live transport of *T. gratilla* presents a critical challenge due to literature gaps regarding the possible duration and methods. This project's goal is to find out a suitable transport protocol for delivering of high-quality live *T. gratilla*. To achieve this goal, a factorial experiment will be conducted where urchins will be placed in insulated boxes with specific packing configurations (piled or separated), with and without ice and exposed to varying transportation durations (12, 24 and 48 hours). Temperature will be logged over the duration of the trial. To assess the influence each transport treatment has on the sea urchins, frequency of spawning, disease and mortality will be measured at the end of the trial. The study's findings will not only contribute to optimizing the transportation process for live sea urchins but also hold potential economic benefits for Seychelles. Ensuring the timely delivery of high-quality sea urchins to consumers can significantly boost the region's economic growth by meeting market demands and sustaining the export of this valued marine delicacy.

1 Seychelles fishing Authority, Mahe

2 GOPA, Hamburg, Germany

Seabirds and mangroves on Aldabra Atoll, Seychelles

Type: talk

Jennifer Appoo,^{1,2,*} Nancy Bunbury,^{2,3} Sébastien Jaquemet,¹ and Nicholas A.J. Graham⁴

Mangrove forests are highly sensitive to variations in nutrient availability, which influences their productivity, function and resilience. Seabirds nesting in mangroves represent a source of marine-derived nutrients, but information on their influence on mangrove ecology and function, including the export of nutrients to adjacent habitats remains poorly investigated. We assessed the contribution, uptake, cycling and export of seabird-derived nutrients on Aldabra Atoll (Seychelles), a large mangrove-nesting seabird colony in the Western Indian Ocean. By comparing mangrove sites with and without nesting seabirds, we found that nutrients from seabird guano enriched mangroves and associated macrofauna. Mangroves with seabirds had higher foliar %N and %P indicating seabird-derived nutrient uptake, while reduced foliar nutrient ratios showed seabirds alleviated mangrove nutrient limitations. We detected no differences in N and P foliar resorption efficiencies. In the lagoon, nutrient concentrations in macroalgae adjacent to mangroves and in surface seawater were higher at seabird sites, indicating seabird nutrient export from mangroves through tidal flow. We highlight the important role of seabirds in maintaining functional connectivity between oceanic systems and coastal seascape and improving the nutrient status of highly productive coastal habitats. Conserving seabird populations is therefore vital to preserve and enhance their role in mangrove productivity, resilience and provision of diverse functions and services.

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Seabird-derived nutrient contributions to Seychelles' atoll ecosystems

Type: poster

Jennifer Appoo ^{1,2*}, Nancy Bunbury ^{2,3}, Jake Letori ⁴, Aurélie Hector ⁴, Nicholas A.J. Graham ⁵, Gerard Rocamora ⁶, Matthieu Le Corre ¹, Sébastien Jaquemet ¹

Seabirds play a vital role in transferring and depositing marine nutrients from their oceanic feeding areas to their breeding sites. Despite the abundance of tropical seabird populations on atolls, their nutrient contributions to atoll ecosystems remain poorly understood. Our study addresses this knowledge gap by investigating how seabird contributions vary spatially and seasonally. We compared seabird colonies of different taxa, including red-footed boobies, brown noddy and sooty terns nesting on separate islands of Farquhar Atoll (Seychelles). We assessed nutrient concentrations in guano, soil, coastal plants, and adjacent seagrass in seabird colonies and a control island without nesting seabirds, during wet and dry seasons. We found that sooty terns delivered the highest quantities of nutrients due to their higher biomass. Nutrient transfer from seabird colonies to soil, coastal plants, and seagrass occurred during both seasons. Soil macro- and inorganic nutrient levels were highest in the high-density, ground-nesting tern colony and during the dry season, coinciding with breeding of sooty terns and brown noddies. Seabird colonies maintained high nitrogen levels in coastal plants year-round, while phosphorus levels did not differ between islands or seasons. Our findings shed light on seabird-driven nutrient dynamics in Seychelles' atoll ecosystems, emphasizing the need for seabird conservation to bolster ecosystem resilience. Our research on a relatively pristine atoll, provides a baseline to compare more impacted atolls and future changes.

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Sea cucumber fishery in Seychelles

Type: poster

Clara Belmont & Dainise Quatre

Sea cucumber, also known as a beche-de-mer in some countries, is an invertebrate which plays a crucial role in recycling nutrients and bioturbation processes in marine benthic ecosystems. In Japan, China, Korea, and Southeast Asia, sea cucumbers have long been considered a delicacy. Since they are easy to catch, they have been commercially fished in the Pacific for centuries. In recent years, increasing demand coupled with easy harvesting has led to many local stocks being overfished and some becoming extinct. Due to their sedentary lifestyles, density-dependent reproduction, and lack of knowledge on their biological parameters, sea cucumbers are especially vulnerable to overexploitation. Over the past 100 years, sea cucumbers in Seychelles have been harvested in very small quantities, until heavy exploitation began in the late 1990s. Consequently, the fishery rapidly expanded due to increasing international market demands and better price offers. Local depletion in commercially targeted sea cucumber species was observed in 1999, owing to a lack of baseline information on the stock's state. As a response, several proactive management measures were implemented by the Seychelles Fishing Authority (SFA). Along the years, the SFA has also undertaken numerous stock studies on the Amirantes and Mahé Plateau with the aim to evaluate economically the stock status targeted sea cucumber species and establish baseline information on the resource. Data acquired during these surveys enabled SFA to develop and implement sustainable management measures for the Sea cucumber fishery.

Seychelles Fishing Authority

Seabirds boost primary and secondary productivity on coral reefs

Type: talk

Casey Benkwitt¹, Lucie Bennett², Emma Cotton³, Ameer Ebrahim³, Sean Evans⁴, Rodney Govinden⁵, Melissa Schulze⁴, Anna Zora⁶, Nick Graham¹

Tropical coral reefs thrive in part by relying on natural nutrient inputs from other ecosystems, with seabirds providing one such link. Seabirds can transport large amounts of oceanic nutrients to islands and nearshore coral reefs during their daily feeding migrations. However, many seabird populations are in decline due to a number of human-caused threats (e.g., invasive rats), with the implications for coral reefs not fully understood. Here, we investigated how seabird-derived nutrients influence primary and secondary productivity on coral reefs by comparing five sites across four islands in the inner Seychelles with a range of seabird densities. We measured primary productivity as growth rates of turf algae within herbivore exclusion cages, and secondary productivity of herbivorous fish assemblages by combining models of individual growth trajectories with underwater survey data. Turf algae grew faster with increasing amounts of seabird-derived nutrients. These higher rates of primary productivity, in turn, fuelled higher secondary productivity of herbivorous fishes, with the strongest effects on herbivore grazers that feed mainly on turf algae. Thus, seabirds can enhance coral-reef ecosystem function as measured by productivity. Removing invasive rats from islands, which has already been successful on many islands in the Seychelles, may be one way to restore seabird populations and their associated benefits for coral reefs.

1 Lancaster University, UK

2 Felicite Island, Seychelles

3 Island Conservation Society, Seychelles

4 Cousine Island, Seychelles

5 Seychelles Fishing Authority, Seychelles

6 Fregate Island, Seychelles

The importance of monitoring the subsistence fishing on outer islands for management purposes: the Farquhar example.

Type: poster

Elena Levorato¹, William McNeely¹, Gregory Berke¹

In most of the outer islands of the Seychelles managed by Island Development Company (IDC), the fish caught in the artisanal fishery are for subsistence, meaning that they are used to feed both the staff working and the tourist visiting the islands. Since one of the main goals of IDC is the environmental management and sustainable exploitation of the resources, there is a partnership with Island Conservation Society (ICS) to monitor the subsistence catch in the outer islands where ICS has operational centres, like the atoll of Farquhar.

For each fishing trip, crucial data are collected, such as the fishing locations, the fishing efforts, the species diversity, the total catch, the total biomass and the species length-weight relationship. All these data are important to understand the fishing pressure on the targeted species by the subsistence fishery and thus, ensure sustainable fishing practices. For example, assessing the Catch Per Unit Effort can provide insight of the stability of the fish stock. Moreover, the information collected also gives an idea of the spatial distribution and size trends of a species through time, which are essential for any management plan. Commercially valuable species inhabit the lagoon of Farquhar and some gather each year in spawning aggregations, such as the Camouflage grouper – *Epinephelus polyphekadion*. Therefore, it is important to look into variations or trends through time that may reveal potential threats for certain species, for which ICS will propose solutions accordingly. For instance, reduction in the fork length of the individuals caught might be an indicator of high pressure on the species.

¹ Island Conservation Society, P.O Box 775, Pointe Larue, Mahé, Seychelles.

Sea Turtle Nesting Patterns in the Seychelles MPAs

Type: talk

Sophie Berlouis

The Seychelles Parks and Gardens Authority manages and protects five of the Seychelles' marine protected areas (MPAs). Renowned for their diverse marine habitats, these areas safeguard the nesting beaches, foraging grounds and migratory pathways of several marine turtle species, including the Endangered Green turtle (*Chelonia mydas*) and the Critically Endangered Hawksbill turtle (*Eretmochelys imbricate*). Our research aims to establish a comprehensive and long-term sea turtle monitoring program, allowing us to assess the population status and habitat use of these iconic species. We will examine total nesting attempts, laying success and beach preference, and explore how these variables have changed in recent years. We will also discuss the primary stressors currently influencing turtle nesting patterns within Seychelles' MPAs, the most evident being coastal erosion. We hope that our findings will help inform future evidence-based conservation and management strategies, allowing these key species to thrive for generations to come.

Seychelles Parks and Gardens Authority (SPGA)

Standing stock assessment of the Mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) in the lagoon of Astove atoll and evaluation of the potential for commercial crab fattening

Type: poster

Jude Bijoux¹, Justin Prosper², Daig Romain³ and Karine Rassool⁴

The Mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) is one of the candidate species for aquaculture identified in the Seychelles Mariculture Masterplan. High market demand and value coupled with the fast growth of this species makes it an ideal aquaculture species. To investigate the feasibility of commercial crab fattening from wild-sourced juveniles inside the lagoon of Astove island, Southern Seychelles a spatially structured survey was undertaken between 19th and 24th March 2022. A total of 307 circular plots each with an area of 314 m² were surveyed. Mud crabs found within the survey plots were captured, sexed and their carapace length measured. Carapace length was used to estimate crab biomass using the length-weight relationship. Crab biomass per m² was calculated for each survey plot and was used as input data for geostatistical interpolations which predicted distribution surfaces and allowed for the calculation of the standing stock biomass. Out of the 11 types of interpolation techniques tested, Inverse Distance Weighted (IDW) interpolation provided the most realistic distribution and biomass estimates. The area surveyed was estimated to have a standing stock of 582 Kg of crabs and the carrying capacity of 705 Kg. Biomass harvesting at 40% of the carrying capacity per year was estimated to equate to about 282 Kg or an average of about 550 average size individuals. It was not possible to sample the centre of the lagoon due to difficult access. Targeted surveys are required to confirm if they are found in the centre of the lagoon and in what densities.

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3 GoS-UNDP-GEF Project Coordination Unit, Victoria, Mahe, Seychelles

4 Island Development Company, Victoria, Seychelles

Acoustic Telemetry: conservation, questions, and collaboration in the outer islands

Type: talk

Eleanor Brighton, Andy Danylchuk, Lucas Griffin, Steve Cooke, Jack Coupland, Greg Berke & Lauren Peel

Acoustic telemetry is a powerful and effective tool used increasingly around the world to gain insights about the spatial ecology of aquatic animals. When an array of fixed receivers is deployed, there are opportunities to passively detect the movement patterns of tagged marine life 24/7, 365 days of the year, and across a range of habitats and environmental conditions. Depending on the hypotheses to be addressed, the same configuration of acoustic receivers can be used to track the movement patterns of different tagged species, amplifying the benefits of such technology. In 2018, a fixed receiver array was established in the Alphonse Group to track the movement patterns of Giant Trevally. Setting up an array of over 70 receivers presented numerous challenges, yet its establishment opened up the potential for additional partnerships and collaborations to study the movement patterns of other species. With its broader purpose, the Alphonse Underwater Tracking Observatory – AUTO – is now being used to track the spatial ecology and residency times of reef mantas and milkfish, and soon will be tracking the movement patterns and core habitats of several species of sharks. Such partnerships and collaborations require a mutual understanding of the limitations of acoustic telemetry, a consistent source of funding, expertise, and labor to maintain the receiver array, and ample communications and planning related to future opportunities. For our talk, we will review the lessons learned through the establishment of AUTO, as well as reveal the suite of questions acoustic telemetry can answer. Ultimately, we highlight how this initiative and its associated partnerships can inform conservation of marine resources and unite global research and academia with active management on the ground in remote locations.

The last dugongs of Seychelles – population assessment at Aldabra Atoll

Type: talk

Caulvyn Bristol

Dugong (*Dugong dugon*) populations worldwide are declining and the species is listed as Vulnerable to extinction on the IUCN Red List due to habitat loss, entanglement in fishing gear, illegal hunting, boat strikes and ingestion/entanglement in marine debris. Historically, dugongs are thought to have occurred around many islands of Seychelles, but records of dugong sightings over the past 50 years are restricted to the Aldabra Group, particularly Aldabra Atoll. Therefore, there is a critical need to understand the status of Aldabra's dugong population and its importance in the regional context. However, most of the data available of Aldabra's dugong population is qualitative, and there are extensive gaps in quantitative knowledge of the dugong population status, distribution and behavioural characteristics. In 2023, and catalysed by the advancement in imaging and drone technology, the Seychelles Islands Foundation launched the first drone surveys of dugongs to assess their population number and distribution across Aldabra's lagoon and outer reefs. This presentation outlines the survey methodology, insights from the field as well as the results of the first assessment of dugongs in Seychelles via drones.

Seychelles Islands Foundation

An investigation in sea cucumber (*Holothuria scabra*) broodstock conditioning in Seychelles

Type: poster

PJ Bristol¹, Bas de Vos ^{1,2}

In Seychelles, sea cucumber fishing has been a very successful business however, overfishing has resulted in overexploitation of wild stocks. Subsequently, the demand is higher than supply. Aquaculture of sea cucumbers could fulfil this demand and relieving natural stocks. The initial step to produce the sea cucumber *Holothuria scabra* is inducing broodstock to spawn. This has not previously been attempted in the Seychelles and has proven challenging in other regions. Therefore, the main goal of this study is to identify a suitable method of conditioning broodstock of *H. scabra* to enhance spawning. To achieve this, a factorial experiment will be conducted which compares of land-based and sea-based broodstock condition systems with sediment that is or is not fertilized with dried *Sargassum sp.* (macroalgae). *Sargassum* is believed to increase nutrient content in the sediment and therefore enhance feedstock for *H. scabra*. After a period of conditioning the spawning induction will be attempted. The frequency of successful spawning, egg counts and larval survival will be compared between treatment. This research could contribute to Seychelle's economy, environment, climate and society. This sea cucumber species is of high value, thus if production is increased, it will boost and diversify the blue economy of Seychelles. As *H. scabra* is overexploited, potential restocking programs could assist ecological integrity. Additionally, sea cucumbers are known to contribute towards marine sediment carbon capture via bioturbation, therefore they could be a potential climate change mitigation strategy. Lastly, through these environmental and economic benefits, sea cucumber aquaculture and restocking has the ability to improve the social well-being of the Seychellois people.

1 Seychelles fishing Authority, Mahe

2 GOPA, Bad Homburg, Germany

Integration of population genetics with oceanographic models reveals strong connectivity among coral reefs across Seychelles (Marine ecology)

Type: talk

April Burt, Noam Vogt-Vincent, Helen Johnson, Ashley Sendell-Price, Steve Kelly, Sonya M. Clegg, Catherine Head, Nancy Bunbury, Frauke Fleischer-Dogley, Marie-May Jeremie, Nasreen Khan, Richard Baxter, Gilberte Gendron, Christophe Mason-Parker, Lindsay A Turnbull

Countries with tropical reef systems are implementing urgent measures to preserve the functions of coral reefs in the face of climate change. One option is to focus management efforts and target resources at reefs from which larval export to other reefs is likely to be highest, thus maximising regional reef resilience. This requires knowledge about connectivity patterns among reefs. To investigate coral reef connectivity in the Seychelles reef system, we carried out a population genomic study of the *Porites lutea* species complex. We also used a 2-km-resolution regional ocean simulation coupled with a larval dispersal model to predict the flow of larvae between reef sites. Comparison of empirical results for genetic connectivity with that from model predictions of larval dispersal agree on connectivity patterns although the observed level of connectivity revealed by population genomics is greater than that predicted from model simulations. Both methods detected a biogeographic dispersal barrier between the Inner and Outer Islands of Seychelles. However, this barrier is permeable and substantial larval transport is possible across Seychelles. The agreement between our predicted connectivity with observed genetic connectivity in patterns, if not degree, allow us with more confidence to use larvae dispersal simulation to directly support reef system management in Seychelles and the wider region

An international assessment of the barriers influencing the effectiveness of island ecosystem management

Type: poster

April Burt, Ana Nuno, Lindsay Turnbull, Frauke Fleischer-Dogley, Nancy Bunbury

Island ecosystems are disproportionately impacted by biodiversity loss and as such their effective management is critical to global conservation efforts. Practitioners world-wide work to manage island sites and species to conserve them, but various day-to-day barriers compromise these efforts, reducing management effectiveness and preventing local and potentially even national biodiversity targets from being met. Identifying the most important barriers that currently impede effective island conservation could streamline investment to focus on cost-efficient interventions that better reflect realities on the ground and the need to address barriers under substantial time and budget constraints. A survey of 360 practitioners working in island ecosystem management across 77 countries was conducted. The three most common barriers perceived by practitioners to prevent them from achieving more effective management are: low staff capacity; difficulties turning data into useful information for management (including lack of capacity and time to analyse data); and lack of a research and management strategy. Practitioners' perceptions of national-level management effectiveness were mostly associated with their perception of governance issues, the presence/absence of research and management strategies and their experience of collaboration outcomes. Practitioners' experience of staffing and monitoring programme issues was important in shaping their perception of management effectiveness within the organisation(s) they worked with. Despite the indisputable need for transformative change to address the underlying causes of many of these barriers, more immediate and direct investment in strengthening the people and systems that are at the frontline of preventing biodiversity loss on islands is needed to bridge these barriers and achieve more effective management of island ecosystems.

Influence of oceanographic features on habitat suitability of a tropical baleen whale species in a newly identified 'hotspot' off Seychelles

Type: talk

Michelle Caputo^{1,2}, Ella Nancy³, Kate Stafford⁴, Ladd Irvine⁴, and Jeremy J. Kiszka^{1,2}

Bryde's whales (*Balaenoptera edeni*) are one of the three known species of baleen whales that do not migrate and that only occur in tropical marine habitats. However, limited research has been conducted to assess the effects of environmental variables on the distribution and abundance of these large predators, and how global climate change could affect their future distribution, potentially affecting their ecological roles and impacts. Here, we investigated the environmental drivers of the occurrence of Bryde's whales off the northern islands of Seychelles, in the western tropical Indian Ocean. In November 2020 and 2021, we performed large vessel sighting surveys to determine the occurrence and habitat preferences of large whales in relation to several key environmental predictors, particularly sea surface temperature, primary productivity, and physiography (depth and slope). In total, we recorded 100 Bryde's whale sightings over 30 days of effort and 6490 kilometers surveyed. Bryde's whales were found in slope and deep oceanic waters (840- 3600m). Species distribution modelling (SDM) using ensemble models were used to predict habitat suitability in Seychelles and adjacent waters in relation to environmental predictors from remotely sensed data. Using SDMs, we also assessed the potential impact of climate change by predicting how the distribution of these animals may shift with future scenarios based on global climate model projections.

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Marine Spatial Planning in South Africa: Algoa Bay, a pilot study

Type: talk

Tegan Carpenter-Kling¹, Hannah Truter¹, Anne Lemahieu^{1,2}, Mia Strand¹, Nina Rivers^{1,3}, James Blignaut^{1,4,5,6}, Rozanne Bester¹, Bernadette Snow^{1,3}, Amanda T. Lombard¹

The Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) Act (Act No. 16 of 2018) of South Africa aims to unlock the ocean's economy whilst ensuring sustainable use and protection of marine resources and heritage. The MSP framework intends to divide South Africa's ocean space (ca 473 380 km²) into four planning areas making the large area manageable and sufficient for detailed planning. Here, we pilot MSP in South Africa using a much smaller area, Algoa Bay, Eastern Cape (ca 3 950 km²) and spatially zone six regular uses of the bay: conservation, commercial fisheries, community-use (extractive and non-extractive), mariculture and transport. The large bay is well-studied and has a significant body of existing data of its biophysical features and human-uses. We increase the size and dimension of this data set by including data from various stakeholders, including areas important to various cultural groups for either spiritual/religious, heritage, livelihood or learning reasons. Three scenario zonations, under different management regimes (biodiversity biased, human-use biased and fair-use), are produced using the R package *PrioritizR*, a decision support tool which uses mixed integer linear programming to solve complex planning scenarios. The resulting scenario zonations are presented and loosely coupled to a systems dynamic model to produce estimated gains and losses of ecosystems services in the bay under the different management regimes. We discuss the importance of scale in MSP and the inclusion of stakeholders that represent all uses of the ocean instead of limiting zonation to conventional uses such as biodiversity and commercial enterprises

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2 Department of Geography, Rhodes University, Makhanda, South Africa

3 Law School, University of Strathclyde, Glasgow, United Kingdom

4 ASSET Research, Sedgefield, South Africa

5 School for Public Leadership, Stellenbosch University, Stellenbosch, South Africa

6 South African Environmental Observation network (SAEON), Pretoria, South Africa

Stor(y)ing the Ocean – A Seychelles Saga

Type: poster

Carlo Ceglia

In the past decade or so, the Republic of Seychelles has been at the forefront of global discourses around conservation, sustainable development, and social inclusion focussed on renewed attention to its ocean space. Under the banner of either the Blue Economy, debt restructuring, Marine Spatial Plan, Marine Protection Areas, Big Ocean State, or fisheries management plans – the ocean in Seychelles has recently been discovered, experienced, visualised, circulated, allocated, limited, abstracted, foreclosed, and expanded in a multitude of, often simultaneous, ways. This poster will sketch several of these key elements surrounding such a production of the ocean in the archipelago based on geographical literature interested in space, and ocean space, as a site of social (re)production, contestation, and negotiation. It will do so with data gathered during a twelve-month period in the country, as well as additional secondary material. Ultimately, it will gesture towards what the current ocean politics could mean for, among others, Seychelles' political agency, territorial sovereignty, and social development in the present turbulent times.

Geography Department, Durham University (UK)

Investigating the feasibility of *Gracilaria* seaweed aquaculture in Seychelles

Type: poster

Ian Confiance¹, Bas de Vos²

The Seychelles has great potential for aquaculture development in seaweed production as it could be a major source of sustainable economic growth and food security/stability. *Gracilaria* is a genus of red algae (Rhodophyta) notable for its economic importance. A recent seaweed species survey of Seychelles has identified two species of *Gracilaria*; *salicornia* and *corticata*, which are believed to have high potential in nutraceutical, home aquarium, culinary and agar markets. The domestic agar market has been identified as particularly promising due to its high cost and demand. However, a lack of knowledge and technical skills are major challenges to *Gracilaria* production. The main goal of this study is to determine the optimum methods to produce *Gracilaria salicornia* or *corticata* in the Seychelles. This study will focus on open-water cultivation, as this is more suited to the Seychelles opposed to land-based aquaculture due to a lack of land area and high electricity costs. Various methods of cultivation attachment substrates (rope, tube net and HDPE mesh) will be tested at various depths (surface, 1m and 3m) at various sites for both *Gracilaria salicornia* and *corticata*. Biomass growth rates, epiphyte coverage and subsequent agar yields will be measured and compared between treatments of the two species. These findings will indicate the technical feasibility of *Gracilaria* production in the Seychelles and possibly provide the necessary information required for its production. This study could result in the formation of a new and sustainable aquaculture industry in the Seychelles, thus further increasing and diversifying its blue economy.

1 Seychelles Fishing Authority, Republic of Seychelles

2 GOPA Hamburg, Germany

Low average shoreline change rate in 51 years on the low-lying Aldabra Atoll

Type: talk

Annabelle Constance^{*.a,b}, Nancy Bunbury^{b,c}, Natalie Lack^d, Stephan Nebiker^d, David Obura^e, Frauke-Fleischer-Dogley^b, Gabriela Schaepman-Strub^a

Atolls, due to their low elevation, are at risk of rising sea levels. This research examines Aldabra Atoll, a UNESCO World Heritage Site in the Indian Ocean with a diverse coastal ecosystem, to track shoreline changes against a regional sea level rise of 2–3 mm yr⁻¹. Aerial and satellite images in 1960 and 2011 were used to study 85% of the atoll's shoreline through a Digital Shoreline Analysis System. Over 51 years, 61% of the shoreline remained unchanged, while 24% changed at an average rate of 0.25 ± 0.36 m yr⁻¹, a low rate compared to global atoll changes. Among the areas that did change, accretion and erosion rates were nearly balanced although localized shoreline changes were pronounced. Part of the lagoon shore transformed from a sandy beach to a mangrove habitat, accreting by 214 meters over the period. Erosion occurred at crucial turtle nesting sites and the research station. The lagoon shoreline underwent more rapid changes than the ocean shoreline, particularly in areas exposed to wind and waves. These results highlight Aldabra's shoreline stability over the analysed period, consistent with other Indo-Pacific atolls. With the projected acceleration in sea level rise in the coming decades, ongoing shoreline monitoring is crucial for informing timely adaptation strategies for the conservation of Aldabra's unique ecosystem.

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Spatial ecology and response to catch-and-release of recreationally targeted fish species on St. François and Alphonse Atolls, Alphonse Group, Seychelles Outer Islands: Implications for conservation and management

Type: poster

Jack Coupland¹, Kaeleah Andrew¹, Greg Burke¹, Gail Fordham¹, George Curd¹, Pierre André Adam¹, Christopher Narty¹, Josep Nogues¹, Keith Rose-Innes^{2,3}, Devan Vd Merwe³, Eleanor Brighton³, Lucas P. Griffin⁴, Caitlin McGarigal⁴, Marin Allen⁴, Andy J. Danylchuk⁴, Steven J. Cooke⁵, Sascha Clark Danylchuk⁶, Jacob W. Brownscombe⁷

Recreational fishing is a growing sector of tourism and a major contributor to the Blue Economy in the Seychelles. In particular, Giant trevally (*Caranx ignobilis*, GT) are increasing in popularity as a target for tourism-based recreational fisheries throughout their range in the Indo-Pacific. In theory, this pressure can be conducted in a sustainable manner such as through catch-and-release (C&R) where fish are released rather than harvested. To date however, there is very little species-specific scientific evidence to support fishery guidelines. By combining acoustic telemetry, mark-and-recapture, cooperative monitoring and GT C&R response analysis, we assessed whether angler-fish interactions altered the behavior and spatial ecology of GT in the Alphonse Island Group. In 2018, 70 GT were acoustically tagged to assess their habitat preferences, residency, and response to environmental drivers, including habituation and angler activity. GT primarily selected either reef or lagoon habitats, with their movement patterns broadening over time. Analyzed in tandem with ongoing location-specific catch logs and mark-recapture, GT core use area overlapped with angler catch maps by 30%. Despite this, recaptures were relatively infrequent, suggesting that GT became hook shy and increasingly modified their movement patterns to avoid areas where angler activities occurred. Physiological impacts and post-release impairment was assessed using a variation of common handling and exposure treatments on 42 GT. Overall, the analysis suggests that GTs in the Alphonse Island Group are resilient to being caught via fly fishing, handled, and air exposed for up to 30 s. Collectively, these findings highlight how C&R fisheries have the potential to modify the behavior and spatial ecology of GT, and may influence the viability of the fishery by exceeding carrying capacity. The results from the multi-faceted study can aid resource managers on their decisions on the management of the fly-fishery.

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Effectiveness of coral reef restoration on shark and predatory fish communities in the Cousin Island Special Reserve, Republic of Seychelles

Type: talk

Dale Charlotte¹, Fassbender Nico^{2,3}, Saponari Luca¹, Shah Nirmal¹

Under the threat of climate change the health of coral reefs is in rapid decline. Bridging the gap in our understanding of these ecosystems, Baited Remote Underwater Video Stations (BRUVS) have emerged as valuable tools for ecological observation. BRUVS are underwater camera stations equipped with bait suspended in a mesh bag, strategically positioned in front of the camera's lens using a bait arm. This allows for the capture of footage depicting interactions between predatory and other species with the bait, or as they swim within the camera's view. The recorded footage provides crucial insights into relative species abundance, community structure, and can yield precise estimates of an organism's length and biomass. Additionally, BRUVS can document habitat types, enriching subsequent analyses. In an effort to combat habitat loss, coral restoration projects are striving to revive ailing reefs. While the link between coral restoration and the increased presence of reef fish has been established, there exists a notable data gap concerning the effects on higher trophic levels, specifically predators such as sharks. Past projects have used BRUVS to observe and track various populations and behaviors, yet a monitoring protocol explicitly connecting augmented coral cover through coral restoration to the heightened presence of predators like rays, sharks, groupers, and others remains undeveloped. Nature Seychelles thus aims to employ BRUVS to study the relationship between coral restoration and predatory and other fish species. The project also aims to establish a baseline for these marine predators surrounding the Cousin Island Special Reserve. To the best of our knowledge, this represents an innovative approach to the assessment of coral restoration success, marking uncharted territory in the application of BRUVS within such projects.

Keywords: BRUVS, coral, coral restoration, Seychelles

1 Nature Seychelles, The Centre for Environment & Education Roche Caiman, Mahe, Republic of Seychelles

2 University of Western Australia

3 Save Our Seas Foundation

A comparative analysis of stocking methods in a coral restoration project, Cousin Island Special Reserve, Republic of Seychelles

Type: poster

Dale Charlotte^{1,2}, Antoine Athina¹, Strona Giovanni³, Yathiraj Roshni¹, Bell Michael², Shah Nirmal¹, Saponari Luca¹.

Coral restoration plays a pivotal role in mitigating the decline of coral reefs, increasing the need of implementing techniques and methodologies. This study investigates the efficacy of stocking *Acropora muricata* and *Pocillopora grandis* using fishing line with copper crimping versus traditional rope in mid-water floating nurseries, offering valuable insights for coral restoration practitioners. Over a year, survival, health, growth, cleaning time, cost, preparation, and stocking timing for both methods were evaluated. Survival differed significantly among species with higher rates for *P. grandis* (95.7%) compared to *A. muricata* (54.4%). Stocking methods did not affect survival among and within species. Challenges like nursery collapses and amphipod outbreaks may have impacted survival, emphasizing the importance of consistent maintenance and accessibility of project sites. Fishing line reduced contact with fouling organisms, contributing to significantly enhanced coral health and growth for both species compared to rope. The fishing line method reduced cleaning efforts, optimising operational efficiency. However, cost considerations and preparation complexities for fishing line warrant careful evaluation, particularly with regards to project budgets. The study underscores vital guidance and best practices for coral restoration practitioners, aiding informed decisions on stocking methods for *A. muricata* and *P. grandis* while considering the balance between coral health benefits, operational and cost feasibility.

Keywords: *Acropora muricata*, coral, coral restoration, *Pocillopora grandis*, Seychelles, stocking methods

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Coral Resilience Under Cover: Insights from the Coral Shading Initiative

Type: poster

Brett Hugo¹, Boudault Mehdi¹, Dale Charlotte¹, Vicktoria Sturm¹, Kiran Bhageerutty¹, Shah Nirmal¹ and Saponari Luca¹

The health of coral reefs is declining worldwide from the effect of the 4th global coral bleaching. The consequent mass mortality of corals is triggered by unusually elevated water temperature and excessive solar irradiance. Shading-based interventions have been proposed as conservation tools to limit light exposure and reduce coral mortality during bleaching events. Despite reported success, species- and location- specific variation is still unclear. Thus, this study aims at testing sustainable solutions under the Coral Shading Initiative on the reef in the Cousin Island Special Reserve during the 2024 coral bleaching event. A total of four shading units, made of braided palm leaves, were deployed on the 8th - 11th of March 2024, covering an area of around 2m² each. A group of 34 randomly selected colonies of 1-year old outplanted *Pocillopora grandis* were selected under the shading structures. Whereas, a group of 25 unshaded colonies of 1-year old outplanted *P. grandis* were randomly selected as control. Monitoring of coral colonies was planned for a minimum of 4 sessions during the pre-bleaching, bleaching peak and post-bleaching/recovery phase. Data were collected on shading rate and lifespan of the structures, water temperature, size of the colonies, and colonies response to shading and bleaching through change in R channel values of macro-pictures analyzed using Matlab and R-studio. Preliminary results of changes in R values showed a decrease in chlorophyll/zoanthellae density with an increase in R values for both control and shaded corals. However, the results show a stronger increase in shaded colonies, which seems to contradict the majority of outcomes available in literature. Further monitoring sessions will be carried out, although these preliminary results are key to start to understand the behavior of one of the most common corals in Seychelles and the effect of the sustainable shading system. Additionally, challenges, implementation and best practices are presented to facilitate practitioners in operating shading strategies as effective tools to reduce coral mortality during bleaching events.

Key words: coral shading, sustainability, photographic analysis, coral restoration, coral bleaching

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USING FARM-SCALE MODELLING TO ASSESS THE FEASIBILITY OF A COMMERCIAL SCALE RECIRCULATING AQUACULTURE SYSTEM INTEGRATING SEA URCHINS (*TRIPNEUSTES GRATILLA*) AND SEAWEED (*ULVA*)

Type: talk

Bas C de Vos^{1,3,4} Mark D. Cyrus^{1,2}, John J. Bolton¹ and Brett M. Macey^{1,4}

The concept of a land-based recirculating Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) system combining the highly valued sea urchin, *Tripneustes gratilla*, and the green macroalga, *Ulva*, has gained substantial interest globally. This is due to *Ulva*'s potential to simultaneously provide bioremediation of urchin wastewater and a primary feed source for the urchins, thus mitigating the principal economic and environmental concerns of aquaculture. This study aimed to establish the biotechnical feasibility of this system through a farm-scale model. To construct this model, certain literature gaps need to be filled regarding the optimal *T. gratilla* basket depth, stocking density, quantification methodology and nitrogen emission in wastewater. An experiment revealed that deeper baskets result in reduced feed consumption by *T. gratilla* ($W > 38$, $p < 0.026$), attributed to lower feed accessibility. Shallow baskets (± 15 cm deep) therefore enhance *T. gratilla* production and were subsequently applied in stocking density trials. This study determined an optimal stocking density to be approximately 20% of the basket's surface area being occupied by urchins, for both grow-out and gonad enhancement phases. Recognizing the need for precise and efficient live urchin measurement in a commercial setting, this study developed a computer vision-based protocol for efficient and accurate measurement of large quantities of live sea urchins. This protocol offers potential automation for farm processes and enhances measurement accuracy in research contexts. The *T. gratilla-Ulva* IMTA farm-scale model uses total ammonia nitrogen (TAN) the underlying limiting factor. Utilizing a 'black box' approach, regression models predict TAN concentrations in *T. gratilla* effluent. The farm-scale model then estimates *T. gratilla* and *Ulva* production, indicating some potential for an efficient system with proper design and management adjustments. This model offers valuable insights for industry establishment, serving as a tool for environmental impact assessments, aiding stakeholders in farm design and comprehensive analyses.

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Diversity and distribution of benthic marine species with depth around D'Arros island and St Joseph Atoll

Type: poster

Clara Diaz, Nicola Foster, Callum Turner, Edward Robinson, Phil Hosegood.

Tropical coral reefs represent one of the most important and diverse marine ecosystems. However, they are in crisis from a combination of direct human impacts, and the effects of climate change. Due to these alarming trends and the evolution of technology in these past decades, scientific research started to focus slightly deeper, where mesophotic corals ecosystems (MCEs) reside. MCEs are defined as light-dependent corals and associated communities at depths of 30m to >150m in tropical waters. MCEs may occur over extensive geographic distributions and the potential importance of MCEs as refugia from the effects of climate change has only recently emerged. Little is known about the diversity, distribution, abundance and health of mesophotic reefs worldwide as they occur in deeper waters, but MCEs host a high biodiversity, both benthic and pelagic. Documenting species abundance and the overall diversity is a first requirement to develop conservation management plans. Here, we surveyed MCEs from 15m to 90m deep in D'Arros Island and St Joseph Atoll using a drop-cam to firstly document shallow- and upper-mesophotic reef communities found there and to survey any differences in these communities. The second objective was to establish how the structure and diversity of coral communities change with depth at both sites. Overall, we observed a high benthic biodiversity with differences in communities between sites and depths. This research demonstrates the richness and uniqueness of benthic communities along the mesophotic depth gradient in the Seychelles, highlighting the need for conservation measures throughout depth to protect the overall diversity.

University of Plymouth, UK

Differences in foraging range between white-tailed tropicbirds breeding on inner and outer Seychelles islands

Type: talk

Orphéo Ensanyar-Volle^{1,2}, Jennifer Appoo^{3,4}, Nancy Bunbury^{3,5}, Gemma Clucas⁶, Nasreen Khan⁷, Gérard Rocamora^{8,7}, Cheryl Sanchez^{3,9}, Annette L. Fayet^{2,10}

The foraging ecology and distribution of Phaethontiformes, an order of tropical seabirds, remains generally poorly understood, despite being essential to inform their conservation. Here, we track for the first time the foraging movements of breeding white-tailed tropicbirds *Phaethon lepturus*— a common but poorly studied seabird—in the Indian Ocean. We compare the foraging movements and habitat preferences of two populations, one from Aride Island in the inner Seychelles and the other from Aldabra Atoll in the outer Seychelles, ca. 1200 km to the southwest. We find considerable differences in foraging trip metrics between populations, with birds from Aride having an average foraging range two times greater (231 km on Aride vs 105 km on Aldabra), and both populations feeding far beyond the protected areas around their respective colony. We also find differences in foraging range between incubation and chick-rearing stages and sexes. Using habitat models, we highlight the birds' preference for deep waters, which may explain the greater foraging range of Aride birds, although human activities may also play a role. Our study provides unprecedented insight into the foraging ecology of white-tailed tropicbirds in the Western Indian Ocean.

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The predator, the prey, and the polyp

Type: talk

Nico Fassbender^{1,2}, Robert Bullock², Henriette Grimmel², Rory McAuley^{3,4}, Jessica Meeuwig¹, Ellie Moulinie², Dillys Pouponeau², Dirk Zeller⁵

Sharks are present on 4 out of 5 reefs globally. But what about the 20% of reefs where they have disappeared? As top predators these animals rely on suitable habitat to forage and prey availability. What we don't know is how the continued homogenization of coral reefs due to climate change will impact the way they utilize these environments. Here we investigate the behaviour of three reef-associated shark species: the blacktip reef shark (*Carcharhinus melanopterus*), grey reef shark (*Carcharhinus amblyrhynchos*) and sicklefin lemon shark (*Negaprion acutidens*) in the Amirantes Islands and across Seychelles Inner Islands. We use a multi-faceted approach to understand shark and prey assemblage structure, movement behaviour, and habitat structure. We combine the acoustic tagging of sharks, benthic baited remote underwater video systems (BRUVS), faecal DNA swabbing and 3D reef photogrammetry to investigate fine-scale shark behaviour and how that is influenced by prey availability and habitat complexity. Since September 2022 we acoustically tagged and faecal swabbed 72 sharks, collected 411 hours of BRUVS footage and photogrammetized over 6000 m² of coral reef. Our preliminary results indicate that sharks are present across all habitat types and are more than twice as abundant in the Amirantes compared to the Inner Islands. Whilst we saw more sharks in the Amirantes, we observed a greater predator diversity around Mahé, especially of subadult, critically endangered species. Our final model will help define shark priority habitats and aid in the conservation and management of these threatened predators.

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Marked differences in foraging area use and susceptibility to predation between two closely-related tropical seabirds

Type: talk

Annette L Fayet^{1,2}, Cheryl Sanchez^{3,4}, Jennifer Appoo^{3,5}, Jessica Constance³, Gemma Clucas⁶, Lindsay A. Turnbull² & Nancy Bunbury^{3,7}

Ecological theory predicts that closely-related species must occupy different niches to coexist. How marine top predators achieve this during breeding, when they often gather in large multi-species colonies and are constrained to central-place foraging, has been mostly studied in productive temperate and polar oceans with abundant resources, but less so in poorer, tropical waters. Here, we track the foraging movements of two closely-related sympatric seabirds—the white-tailed and red-tailed tropicbirds *Phaethon lepturus* and *P. rubricauda*—breeding on Aldabra Atoll, Seychelles, to investigate potential mechanisms of niche segregation and shed light on their contrasting population trends. Combining data from GPS, immersion, depth and accelerometry loggers, we show that the two species have similar behaviour at sea, but are completely segregated spatially, with red-tailed tropicbirds flying further to feed and using different feeding areas than white-tailed tropicbirds. Using nest-based camera traps, we show that low breeding success of both species—which likely drives observed population declines—is caused by high nest predation. However, the two species are targeted by different predators, with native avian predators mainly targeting red-tailed tropicbird nests, and invasive rats raiding white-tailed tropicbird nests when they leave their eggs unattended. Our findings provide new insight into the foraging ecology of tropicbirds and have important conservation implications. The extensive range and spatial segregation highlight the importance of considering large-scale protection of waters around tropical seabird colonies, while the high level of nest predation provides evidence in support of rat eradication and investigating potential nest protection from native avian predators.

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Sea-level rise could cause severe damages in the Seychelles

Type: talk

Dorothee Fehling¹ Athanasios Vafeidis¹

As a Small Island Developing State, the Seychelles are particularly vulnerable to sea-level rise (SLR). Although their three main islands are mountainous, most of the population and infrastructure are exposed to SLR because they are located in the narrow and low-lying coastal plain. Local stakeholders have identified coastal erosion, wave overtopping and extreme coastal water levels as the main current and future concerns regarding SLR. Nevertheless, analyses of the potential impacts of SLR in the Seychelles are still lacking. In our study we address this gap by conducting an assessment of potential impacts of coastal flooding. We use the hydrodynamic model LISFLOOD-FP and the DIVA (Dynamic Interactive Vulnerability Assessment) modelling framework to analyse the implications of various SLR, socio-economic and adaptation scenarios for the coastal population and infrastructure of the Seychelles' three main islands. Our findings show that flood damages and affected population will increase in every scenario. Adaptation in the form of hard coastal protection can be effective, but long-term adaptation planning would be essential to reduce the future impacts of SLR.

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Nitrogen isotope constraints on southwestern Indian Ocean variability in the 20th century

Type: talk

Alan D. Foreman^{1*}, Nicolas Duprey¹, Tanja Wald¹, Holger Anlauf², Robert Bullock³, Henriette Grimmel³, Alfredo Martínez-García¹

Tropical variability in the Indian Ocean impacts both regional and global climate via atmospheric teleconnections. The ocean–atmosphere dynamics in the tropics are extremely sensitive to perturbations associated with natural and anthropogenic climate change, and respond to these changes on multiple (seasonal, interannual, and multi-decadal) time scales. Despite their importance in informing our understanding of past and future climate, however, observational data of Indian Ocean variability is sparse over the 20th century, and little consensus exists as to the response of the Indian Ocean to long term anthropogenically-forced climate change. One particularly under-sampled region is the Southwestern Indian Ocean, which plays a significant role in the regional climate of the Indian Ocean on seasonal and interannual timescales. Here we present monthly-resolved coral skeleton-bound nitrogen isotope ($CS-\delta^{15}N$) data from a pair of *Porites* coral cores collected at St. Joseph Atoll, in the Seychelles Archipelago. This data, which spans the 20th and early 21st centuries, shows distinct seasonal variations in $CS-\delta^{15}N$ that correlate with monsoonal-driven upwelling. In addition, the $CS-\delta^{15}N$ record varies on decadal timescales. We compare these variations with changes in $\delta^{18}O$ (itself sensitive to changes in temperature and salinity) in order to distinguish the drivers of the observed decadal-scale variability in $CS-\delta^{15}N$ (for example, fluctuations in the influence of the Indonesian Throughflow). Taken together, these records allow us to better characterize the variability of the southwestern Indian Ocean during a period in which observational data for the region is scarce, and to better understand the impacts of anthropogenic climate change.

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Moving Towards Regenerative Aquaculture for coral conservation

Type: talk

Fourie Lize¹, Ramkalawan Samuel¹, Shah Nirmal¹

Nature Seychelles has successfully, over the last 13 years, conserved coral reefs using the method known as coral gardening, a form of ocean-based aquaculture where fragments are selected from a donor reef, grown out and planted onto degraded reefs. However, ocean-based coral restoration presents several limitations, including the susceptibility of environmental stresses, genetic diversity concerns and structural maintenance of ocean-based nurseries. To overcome these limitations, Nature Seychelles has embarked on a path to integrate regenerative aquaculture for coral conservation through the use of land-based aquaculture. The addition of this land-based aquaculture facility complementing Nature Seychelles' current coral conservation efforts aligns with the broader (SDG 14) objective of promoting healthy reefs, preserving marine diversity and sustaining the marine ecosystems that benefit both marine and human life. This study details the intricacies of establishing a land-based regenerative coral facility for coral conservation in Seychelles. From site selection and systems designs, to operational considerations, with a key focus on navigating legislative frameworks and securing requisite licensing.

Keywords: Seychelles, Aquaculture, Regenerative aquaculture

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The Ecological Status of the Baie Ternay and Port Launay Marine National Parks

Type: talk

Gameiro, R.¹, Coupland, J.¹, Julie, C.¹, Stimpson, Z.¹, Shah, N¹, Henri, K. ¹

A comprehensive ecological assessment of the Baie Ternay and Port Launay Marine National Parks' (MNP) coral, mangroves, and seagrass was undertaken to establish a baseline and to facilitate future governance and management of the parks. Surveys conducted in both MNPs during the South East and North West monsoon revealed distinct patterns in hard coral genera diversity and distribution across reef types in both marine parks. Bleaching prevalence varied between monsoons, parks, and reef types, showcasing the vulnerability of coral colonies and the low abundance of the fish and invertebrate communities. The study also provided a baseline assessment of the seagrass ecosystem of both MNPs. Eight species of seagrass were recorded in the intertidal and subtidal zones of the MNPs, and species diversity and abundance within the seagrass meadows of Baie Ternay were higher compared to Port Launay. A thorough understanding of the mangals at both sites was achieved through aerial and ground-based methods. This includes species diversity and abundance, recruitment rates, biomass estimates, and the impact of urban development at both sites. Six of the seven Seychelles mangrove species were found at Baie Ternay, and *Rhizophora mucronata* was prevalent at both sites. The paper underscores the imperative need for sustained ecosystem monitoring and restoration efforts, invasive species management and pollution control, and increased education and awareness for all park users.

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Can extreme temperature induced coral bleaching be mitigated by feeding plankton?

Type: poster

Steven Gappy, Bas de Vos ^{1,2}, Lawrence Grant¹

In the context of escalating climate change impacts, coral reefs are threatened by rising sea temperatures which trigger coral bleaching events. Feeding plankton, specifically microalgae and rotifers, has shown promise as a potential strategy to mitigate the impact of extreme temperatures and prevent coral bleaching. This study investigates this potential of targeted plankton feeding to prevent coral bleaching. Recognizing the delicate symbiotic relationship between corals and zooxanthellae microalgae, the primary objective is to assess whether supplementing coral diets during thermal stress can mitigate extreme temperature-induced bleaching. *Acropora* fragments in laboratory conditions will be subjected to high temperatures (31°C) and intense light conditions will be exposed to treatments of various quantities of microalgae and rotifers. The selected plankton aim to provide a diversified and nutritious food source, enhancing coral resilience. The study's methodology involves monitoring coral health, symbiotic relationships, and bleaching occurrences, evaluating the effectiveness of plankton feeding. The extent of bleaching will be quantified via an eye rated color assessment. While acknowledging the broader context of climate change mitigation and comprehensive conservation measures, this research delves into a potential intervention for coral reefs facing extreme temperature challenges. The findings hold promise for contributing to coral reef resilience, with the supplementation of coral diets serving as a practical tool within a broader toolkit for conservation. Successful outcomes could guide future efforts in aquaculture and coral conservation in the Seychelles, providing focused insights into interventions crucial for the preservation of these invaluable ecosystems.

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2 GOPA, Hamburg, Germany

A glimpse of the macro and megafauna diversity and distribution in the Joint Management Area (JMA), Saya de Malha Bank.

Type: talk

Gilberte Gendron^{1,2}

The Saya de Malha Bank (SMB) is one of the largest and least studied marine banks on the Mascarene Plateau. A first characterization of the distribution and composition of benthic and demersal macro- and megafauna was carried out in May 2018 during the EAF-Nansen Indian Ocean Research Expedition. Data was derived based on Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV) video records sampled along pre-determined transects up the slope on the western, northern, and eastern sides of the SMB on the Mascarene Plateau, starting at a maximum depth of 1000 m. For transects in the deeper areas, the abundance was highest in the upper parts of eastern slope locations, primarily reflecting a relatively higher abundance of black corals (*Antipatharia*) than in other locations. A consistent feature of several transects, but most prominent in eastern and northern slopes, was the occurrence of patchy coral and sponge aggregations along the margin where the substrate was mostly hard. For transects in the shallower areas, four main benthic habitats were investigated and their relative abundance determined during the survey. For the study on fish diversity in addition to ROV videos, pelagic trawls, bottom trawls, and basket traps were also used. Analysis of data showed that the main fish family recorded in the pelagic waters of SMB, using pelagic trawl, was Myctophidae. To thoroughly assess the biodiversity and abundance of fauna of the Saya de Malha Bank, further studies conducting more detailed video transects and sampling of specimens are warranted to better formulate conservation and management measures and strategies.

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Evaluating the feasibility of sustainable seafood labelling programmes in Small Island Developing States: a pilot study in Seychelles

Type: talk

Glass, Jessica R^{1,2}, Belle, Kalsey³, Berke, Gregory⁴, Bodin, Nathalie^{5,6}, Burt, April J.^{7,8}, Duncan, Murray I.^{9,10,11}, Morgan, Sian K.^{12,13}, Pillay, Pavitray¹⁴, and Talma, Sheena^{15,16}

The Republic of Seychelles is one of six African Small Island Developing States (SIDS) and has a marine-based economy reliant on fisheries and international tourism. Seychelles has been flagged by the United Nations as highly vulnerable to climate change. Climatic threats are compounded with population declines of key fishery species. A progressive national stance towards ocean sustainability and an emerging economy partially driven by tourists are two of several factors that make Seychelles a good candidate for a sustainable seafood labelling and consumption programme, which would provide market-based incentives for fishery harvesters, regulators, buyers and consumers to improve sustainable practices. To address the feasibility of such a programme, we conducted a pilot study and mapped supply chain structure to examine incentives and challenges. We gathered data in the form of surveys (N = 268) from artisanal fishers, local consumers, tourists, regulators, restaurants and hotels, and fishery industry representatives. 64% of fishers would like to see a programme implemented but only 34% thought it would be successful. Stakeholders identified several barriers and benefits that primarily spanned socioeconomic and regulatory themes. Our pilot results indicate the sociocultural and economic impacts of sustainability programmes in Seychelles are as important as environmental considerations, a finding pertinent to anyone undertaking similar research efforts in other SIDS. We advocate for the necessity of thorough, location-based research and in-depth stakeholder consultation to elucidate economic, societal, behavioural and cultural factors that will affect the success of designing and implementing seafood labelling programmes in SIDS.

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Spatial trophic variability and genetic connectivity of giant and bluefin trevallies across Seychelles

Type: poster

Jessica R. Glass^{1,2}, Ryan Daly³, Scott R. Santos⁴, John S. K. Kauwe⁵, Brandon Pickett⁶, David M. Post⁷, Paul D. Cowley¹

Trevallies (Carangidae) are economically valuable for small-scale fisheries in Seychelles, yet remain understudied. In particular, giant trevallies (*Caranx ignobilis*) and bluefin trevallies (*Caranx melampygus*) are highly-targeted recreational fishery species. Identifying spatial patterns of diet variability and gene flow are critical components of fisheries management. During 2015–2019, we studied the genetic connectivity of giant and bluefin trevallies across the Seychelles and throughout their Indo-Pacific ranges. From several sites in the western Indian Ocean (WIO), we also collected muscle tissue of giant trevally to examine trophic position across multiple habitat types: coral atolls, coastal reefs, and granitic islands. Analyses of population structure indicate the two species display different phylogeographic patterns across the Indo-Pacific, with giant trevally exhibiting population substructure in the Central Pacific and bluefin trevally comprising a panmictic population. Both species maintain gene flow throughout the WIO, displaying patterns that resemble large pelagic predators such as sharks and tunas rather than most reef-associated teleost fishes. In spite of genetic connectivity in the WIO, giant trevallies display trophic variability that is reflective of habitat. We observed patterns suggestive of ontogenetic changes in diet and habitat utilization, and an offshore to coastal gradient in carbon that drove niche distinctiveness between localities. Trophic position estimates of giant trevally ranged from 3.5 – 5, placing it at the equivalent trophic level as many predatory sharks. This work demonstrates how evaluating spatial components of trophic ecology and genetic connectivity can characterize organisms' functional roles and ecosystem influence, allowing for spatially explicit conservation and management efforts.

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Distribution and drivers of phytoplankton along the Saya de Malha Bank in the Western Indian Ocean.

Type: talk

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The Saya de Malha bank within the Western Indian Ocean is known as a key biodiversity area with high productivity. In situ data however, is characterised by paucity, therefore the 2022 Monaco Exploration of the Indian Ocean provided an opportunity to assess the primary productivity of this bank and investigate the major drivers of the phytoplankton community across this bank. In situ phytoplankton results indicate a rather well-mixed water column across the Bank, with some spatial differences observed in total chlorophyll-a, and the relative abundance of the pico, nano and microplankton. Especially for the total chl-a, there appears to be higher pelagic productivity on the shelf in the northern section of the bank, decreasing towards the southern section, and is comparable with a similar pattern of biomass distribution as the 2008 ASCLME cruise. Size distribution of phytoplankton biomass indicated that the communities of the Saya de Malha were dominated by the very small pico-phytoplankton (~46%), and that highest relative abundance of this group was encountered in the surface waters. On the other hand, the larger micro-phytoplankton had low relative abundance in the surface water (~13%), but increased towards the deeper waters (~36%). Comparing the phytoplankton biomass with ACDP data obtained during this expedition, shows a strong correlation between maximum biomass and dominant current velocities at 30 m depth across the bank, and therefore can be used to inform the likely export patterns of biomass towards the rest of the Western Indian Ocean and the contribution of the Saya de Malha to the rest of the pelagic trophic web in the region.

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Increased resilience and a regime-shift reversal through repeat mass coral bleaching

Type: talk

Nicholas A J Graham¹, Shaun K Wilson^{2,3}, Rodney Govinden⁴, Rodney Bonne⁵, Cassandra E Benkwitt¹, James PW Robinson¹

Coral reef ecosystems are expected to decline in coral dominance, and more reefs undergo regime-shifts to non-coral states, due to coral mortality caused by increasingly frequent and severe marine heatwaves. However, long-term detailed ecological datasets are rare, making ecosystem predictions over multiple heat stress events uncertain. Assessing coral reefs across the inner Seychelles islands, using a 28-year dataset, we document faster coral recovery from the 2016 than the 1998 marine heatwave event. Coral cover recovery was about 4 years ahead following the 2016 bleaching event as compared to coral recovery rates following 1998. Further, compositions of benthic and fish communities were more resistant to change following the more recent heat stress, having stabilized in a persistent altered state following the 1998 climate disturbance. Counter to predictions, one reef that had regime-shifted to macroalgal dominance following the 1998 disturbance, is transitioning to a coral-dominated state following the 2016 heat stress. Collectively, these patterns indicate that the reef system of the inner Seychelles may be more resilient to repeat heatwave events than anticipated.

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Evaluation of an experimental grow-out protocol aimed at optimizing food conversion ratio to minimize the impact of Aquaculture utilizing mangrove snapper (*Lutjanus argentimaculatus*) as a model organism

Type: talk

Walter Lawrence Grant¹, Nulette Gordon²

An experimental grow-out protocol aimed at optimizing the Food Conversion Rate (FCR) was tested utilizing juvenile Mangrove Snapper (*Lutjanus argentimaculatus*) collected from the wild in an Aquaculture facility in Mahe, Seychelles. Fish were fed with a formulated feed suitable for culturing warm-water marine finfish (Biomar). Survival was 100 % during the trial and consistent results were achieved between replicates. Fish were successfully cultured from approximately 100 g to 1 kg during an 11-month period with an average FCR of 1.31 (SD 0.07) achieved for four replicates using a theoretically optimum feeding table that had been constructed beforehand. This compares favorably with previous studies and this study is unique in its duration. A growth model was constructed with this data using the machine learning module Scikit-learn.

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2. James Michel Blue Economy Research Institute, University of Seychelles, Seychelles; nuette.gordon@unisey.ac.sc

Implications of degraded coral reef habitats for artisanal fisheries in Seychelles

Type: talk

Mark Hamilton¹, James PW Robinson¹, Sarah M Martin¹, Cassandra E Benkwitt¹, Shaun K Wilson^{2,3}, Ameer Ebrahim⁴, Rodney Govinden⁴, M Aaron MacNeil⁵, Christina C Hicks¹, Nicholas AJ Graham¹

Changing coral reef habitats alter fish assemblages, with implications for associated fisheries. Understanding how reef fish communities are affected by disturbances, such as coral bleaching, and how small-scale fisheries respond to these changes can provide insights into environmental impacts on fisheries catches and livelihoods. We examined fisheries productivity after mass coral bleaching events and assessed perceptions and responses of artisanal trap fishers using data from coral reef surveys and interviews around Mahe and Praslin. Fish productivity increased on reefs recovering to a coral-dominated state, with herbivores such as parrotfish driving biomass production. Productivity on reefs that regime-shifted to a macroalgae-dominated state remained stable at pre-bleaching levels in fished areas but increased inside protected marine reserves, driven mainly by browsing rabbitfish. Parrotfish and rabbitfish dominated fish trap catches in post-bleaching years and many fishers reported steady catches of these fishes throughout the year, with some seasonal differences and variation between fishing grounds, however most fishers noted their catches had decreased in the long term. Although most fishers had noticed environmental changes on fishing grounds, only ~30% of fishers thought this had led to changes in catches. Several fishers stated increased fishing effort and theft of fish traps were reasons they had changed their fishing activity, such as travelling further to fishing grounds. Our findings suggest fish productivity can be sustained on climate-disturbed reefs in Seychelles, benefitting fisheries, however trap fishers must overcome logistical issues and increasing costs in addition to environmental changes to maintain catches and provide reef fish to markets.

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2 Department of Biodiversity, Conservation & Attractions, Perth, Australia

3 Oceans Institute, University of Western Australia, Crawley, Australia

4 Seychelles Fishing Authority, Victoria, Mahe, Seychelles

5 Department of Biology, Dalhousie University, Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada

Blue Carbon in Seychelles' Blue Economy

Type: talk

J. Harlay¹, G. Rowlands², S. Baez³, T. Hickey, S. Antat¹, A. Faure⁴, J. Mortimer^{5,6}, B. Lee⁷, D. Traganos⁷, M. Wartman⁸, M. Costa⁸, P. Macready⁸, M. Morgan⁵, A. Cupidon⁵

Two national Blue Carbon projects were conducted between 2020-2023 on Mangroves and Seagrass to guide the government of Seychelles on its track towards the 100% protection objective for these habitats by 2030. In these projects, the distribution and areas of Blue Carbon habitats were assessed as well as their carbon stocks and sequestration rates, as baseline data to include Blue Carbon in the National Greenhouse gases inventory (NGHGI). Beside the monitoring, the Seagrass project also highlighted the need to align governance in the light of the distribution to provide protection. This talk will also present some of the pilot projects that have been or will be conducted and shows how Blue Carbon meets all of three of the essential elements of sustainability – economic, environmental and social – that are intrinsic to the Blue Economy model of Seychelles

1 BERI-UniSey

2 University of Oxford

3 The PEW Charitable Trusts, USA

4 SEYCCAT

5 ICS

6 Department of Biology, University of Florida, USA

7 DLR, Germany

8 Blue Carbon Lab, Deakin University, Australia

Genetic Adaptability and Conservation of Coral Reefs in the Seychelles

Type: poster

Chloe-Marie Hawley, April Burt, Raphael Gollnisch, Lindsay Turnbull, Rosalind Rickaby, Ash Sendell-Price, SIF

The long-term viability of coral reefs hinges on their capacity to adapt to increasing thermal stress driven by climate change. This research employs a genome-wide analysis with environmental assessment to understand the adaptive potential of a common reef-building coral, *Porites lutea*. We characterise the genetic adaptation of *P. lutea* populations across the Seychelles Archipelago, which inhabit different thermal environments and exhibit varying levels of thermotolerance. Utilising RAiSD, a selective sweep detection program, we identified genomic regions with strong positive selection signatures. Annotation of these regions revealed the types of genetic and molecular pathways under selective pressure. Importantly, this analysis across different thermal regimes could link genetic variation to varying degrees of environmental selective pressures. Our research revealed two key findings: pronounced selection signatures on stress-related genes, including heat shock proteins, apoptotic regulators, and calcium ion channels, and variation in selection intensity among populations living in different thermal environments. Notably, the Aldabra lagoon population, inhabiting a highly fluctuating and extreme environment, shows the strongest adaptive signatures. This study provides key insights into the genetic adaptability of corals, providing not only candidate genes for coral thermotolerance but also highlighting the adaptive potential of *P. lutea* to cope with diverse thermal conditions. These insights are vital for understanding the survival and sustainability of coral reefs, thereby guiding effective and appropriate conservation strategies. Protecting key coral reef refugia like Aldabra Atoll, with its stress-adapted genotypes, is imperative for preserving these genetic reservoirs and subsequently bolstering the overall resilience of reefs across the Seychelles.

Developing the methods for *Caulerpa lentillifera*, sea grape, aquaculture in the Seychelles

Type: talk

Calvin Horner¹, Shamira Payet¹, Devis Monty¹, Bas de Vos^{1,2}

Seaweed farming is a practice well-established in East Asian aquaculture and is gaining global attention, including the Seychelles, due to its potential environmental benefits. A majority of global production is low-value red and brown macroalgae, however, to achieve profitability these species require high-volume production which is unlikely to be viable in the Seychelles due to its economic and environmental climate. *Caulerpa lentillifera*, also known as sea grapes, is an edible green macroalgae. It is highly demanded and valued in various regions globally but especially in Asia. Due to its high value and being indigenous to Seychelles, it has been identified as a potential aquaculture candidate species. The main challenge is the growth of *C. lentillifera* as there are literature gaps regarding the methodology required for its production. Therefore, before entrepreneurs can begin production, research is required to develop and validate standard operating procedures for the production of *C. lentillifera* in the Seychelles. The objective of this project is to explore the possibilities of growing *C. lentillifera* in captivity and to make a feasibility study for a business in the Seychelles. To achieve this, stocks collected from the wild will be grown under land-based and controlled environments. This will allow us to manage and determine optimal lighting, nutrient and temperatures by monitoring growth rates and production levels of *C. lentillifera*. By validating and providing standard operating procedures to produce the *C. lentillifera* on a large scale, Seychelles can diversify its exportation and benefit extra revenue and increase the economy. Seychelles subsequently could emerge as the primary aquaculture center for such seaweed farming.

¹ Seychelles fishing Authority, Mahe

² GOPA, Hamburg, Germany

Seabird nutrient enrichment effects on cryptobenthic fishes

Type: poster

L.-L. Jeannot¹, J.P. Lozano-Peña², A. Zora³, S.J. Brandl², N.A.J. Graham¹

The world's shortest-lived vertebrates, cryptobenthic reef fishes, play a critical role in coral-reef ecosystem functioning. Their high abundance, rapid growth, and extreme mortality underpins reef productivity, by converting hard-to-access food sources to readily accessible nutrients for larger reef consumers. However, their limited dispersal and rapid turnover expose them to risks of rapid genetic isolation and local extinction. Here, we study how variation in nearshore nutrient subsidies affect these fish communities. We compared two sites in Fregate Island that differ in seabird-related nutrient inputs, and used stable isotope analyses to explore how nutrient loads affect these fish communities. We show that while fish communities remain similar across both sites, they exhibit higher reliance on benthic nutrient sources as opposed to pelagic sources when located close to seabird colonies. Overall, higher $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ close to shore near seabird colonies suggests that cryptobenthic fish rely directly on seabird-derived nutrients close to shore, and mixing models highlight that benthic nutrients can reach farther into reefs when coupled with seabird inputs. This study underlines the important role of seabirds for oligotrophic reef ecosystems, and evidences how cryptobenthic fish can transfer these nutrient subsidies to larger predators. With increasing anthropogenic pressure on reefs, including the threat of invasive species to seabirds, evaluating the response of cryptobenthic fish to localized environmental variations is a critical step in elucidating how these chronically understudied fish may influence coral reefs' future.

1 Lancaster Environment Centre, Lancaster University, Lancaster, UK

2 Department of Marine Science, Marine Science Institute, The University of Texas at Austin, Port Aransas, TX, USA

3 Fregate Island Foundation, Angelfish Marina, Roche Caiman, Seychelles

Co-Management of marine areas in Seychelles: How to get from here to there?

Type: talk

Julie, C.¹, Shah, N¹, Henri, K.¹

The management of marine areas by local communities is ongoing, in one way or another, in all countries in the *region* except Seychelles. An understanding of the enabling conditions for this is important, especially given Seychelles' unique socio-economic context in the region, before locally managed marine areas can be established. The Locally Empowered Area Protection (LEAP) has been piloting a Co-Management process in the Port Glaud district for the Port Launay and Baie Ternay marine national parks. It is aimed at 'unpacking' Co-Management, guided by government policy and legislation, for a better understanding of the modalities around a collaborative governance framework for protected areas and OECMs. To do so, a research-for-management approach was adopted and the project engaged in a number of studies to produce relevant scientific and survey evidence that can be used to inform decisions in policy and practice. This paper will explore Seychelles' existing context for Co-management and the building blocks identified through the Port Glaud case study.

¹ Nature Seychelles, The Centre for Environment & Education Roche Caiman, Mahe, Republic of Seychelles

Seychelles blue bond: Indebting ecological restructuring of fisheries

Type: talk

Arınç Onat Kılıç

Seychelles' issuance of the world's first blue bond in 2018 represents a novel approach to financing sustainable blue economy activities. Consisting of socio-legal methodologies, this paper examines the implications of this financial innovation, particularly for the local fisheries sector, and explores how it shapes the implementation of international environmental law in small island states. The paper reveals that the ecological modernization trajectory based on the discourse that sees sustainable transition as a profitable opportunity prioritizes commercial interests over the needs of local communities and alternative fisheries proposals. Contrary to the arguments in the literature indicating that innovative financing models are externally imposed on the island states, blue bond appears to be a deliberate decision by the government to enhance Seychelles' competitive advantages within the global markets. However, the paper claims that such a strategy should be read in the context of low climate financing for adaptation to small island states that are pushed to come up with their climate financing solutions.

University of Antwerp (Belgium)

Unraveling the importance of the Republic of Seychelles for whales and dolphins: implications for capacity building and conservation efforts

Type: talk

Jeremy J. Kiszka¹, Michelle Caputo^{2,3}, Rachel Pool³, Ella Nancy⁴, Nulette Gordon⁵, Kathleen Stafford^{6,7}

Cetaceans are highly charismatic species protected in most countries around the globe, including Seychelles. Increasingly, these species offer opportunities for economic development through tourism and whale watching, particularly in nations of the Global South. However, they face major conservation challenges due to a range of threats, including interactions with fisheries, direct exploitation, habitat degradation, disturbance from shipping traffic, noise and chemical pollution, as well as climate change. Since 2020, multiple research institutions have partnered to initiate a research program on cetaceans in Seychelles aiming to describe their diversity, occurrence, relative abundance, and habitat preferences. This program also aims to investigate the threats affecting cetaceans in Seychelles, as well as their ecological and socioeconomic importance. To ensure the long-term sustainability of this program, capacity building initiatives involving local students and researchers have been initiated. Here, we will overview the goals and objectives of this ongoing research on cetaceans in Seychelles. Since 2020, over 10,000km of boat- and aerial-based survey effort was carried out in Seychelles, and over 400 sightings of 24 species of whales and dolphins were recorded. We will provide preliminary results from data collected between 2020 and 2023, including the discovery of the seasonal presence of blue whales (*Balaenoptera musculus*) in the waters of Seychelles. Future perspectives will also be discussed, particularly on the importance of this program for cetacean conservation, and on the critical importance of local capacity building.

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3 Island Biodiversity and Conservation Centre, University of Seychelles

4 Seychelles Island Foundation

5 BERI-Unisey

6 Applied Physics Lab, University of Washington, USA

7 Marine Mammal Institute, Oregon State University, USA

Marine ecosystem conservation and management at Aldabra Atoll – past, present and future

Type: talk

Anna Koester^{1,*}, April Jasmine Burt¹, Nancy Bunbury¹, Annabelle Constance¹, Frauke Fleischer-Dogley¹

Aldabra Atoll, one of the world's most secluded ecoregions and among the largest globally, has remained largely untouched by humans due to its remote location, limited freshwater resources, and challenging access. This makes it a unique and invaluable site for studying evolutionary and ecological processes on islands. However, despite its isolation from direct human impacts, climate change poses a threat to its ecosystems, necessitating robust conservation efforts.

Over the past twelve years, significant progress has been made in marine conservation at Aldabra. This includes mapping its coral reefs, laying the groundwork for extending the no-take Marine Protected Area (MPA) under the Seychelles Marine Spatial Plan Initiative—a key component of the Seychelles Blue Economy. Additionally, the Seychelles Islands Foundation (SIF) has implemented an annual marine monitoring program, providing invaluable insights into the dynamics of Aldabra's coral reefs, specifically in light of coral bleaching events and subsequent recovery. Furthermore, scientific research at Aldabra continues to yield findings of profound significance at both national and international levels.

Looking ahead, there is a pressing need to enhance ecosystem resilience in response to escalating climate pressures. Previous research has demonstrated the interconnectedness between terrestrial and marine ecosystems, highlighting the role of seabird-derived nutrients in supporting native vegetation and boosting coral growth and fish biomass on coral reefs near seabird colonies. Eradicating invasive rats and cats, thereby restoring natural nutrient cycles, thus holds significant potential for fostering adaptation to climate change across both terrestrial and marine ecosystems. This presentation will outline past and ongoing marine conservation and research initiatives at Aldabra, emphasizing their importance in advancing our understanding of the atoll's ecosystems. Moreover, it will underscore the potential of invasive mammal eradication as a catalyst for enhancing marine ecosystem-based adaptation to climate change, contributing to the conservation and resilience of Aldabra's unique natural heritage.

¹ Seychelles Islands Foundation, Victoria, Mahé, Seychelles

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Co-created mitigation solutions on the tropical tuna purse seiner FAD fishery

Type: talk

Krug I., Murua J¹, Grande M. ¹, Salgado, A. ¹, Ruiz J. ¹, Ferarios J.M. ¹, Zudaire I. ¹, Santiago J. ¹

During the last decade, the OPAGAC and ANABAC purse seine tuna companies have been working in close collaboration with fisheries scientifics to co-create effective mitigation solutions to reduce FAD-derived impacts (i.e. minimize ETP species mortality, reduce marine litter and impacts to marine and coastal sensitive habitats). Also, to provide improved data for management bodies on FAD activities, FAD designs and interaction with sensitive species 100% observer coverage was implemented in their purse seiners and tender vessels. These actions include the implementation of a Code of Good Practices (CGP), which integrates the use of non-entangling FADs and the progressive introduction of biodegradable materials in their construction. The CGP also supports the development and implementation of bycatch release devices for best releasing practices of sensitive fauna to reduce manual manipulation, ensure crew safety and enable a quick release for increased post release survival rates of turtles, sharks and manta rays. The release devices are based on fisheries technologist and skipper feedback gathered during workshops, and includes selective grids to release manta rays, and ramps and hoppers for vulnerable species. In order to evaluate the efficiency of these new devices released animals are monitored with satellite tags to assess post-releasing survival. This work summarizes the main sustainability actions conducted in the Indian Ocean and at global scale by the Spanish and Seychelles tropical tuna purse fleets.

AZTI, Marine Research, Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA), Pasaia, Gipuzkoa, Spain

Do seabird derived nutrient subsidies influence parrotfish feeding behaviour and reef functions?

Type: poster

Lange, Ines¹; Rodriguez-Fillol, Julia¹; Benkwitt, Casey²; Graham, Nick²; Perry, Chris¹

Parrotfishes provide important geo-ecological functions on coral reefs, including grazing, bioerosion and sediment generation. Natural nutrient subsidies from seabird colonies on islands have been shown to increase growth rates and body size of some parrotfish species on adjacent reefs, but the pathways of energy transfer from seabird guano to fish is not yet known. In this study we quantified bite rates and sampled feeding substrates of two parrotfish species (*Scarus rubroviolaceus* and *Chlorurus sordidus*) to investigate differences in a) feeding behaviour and b) nutritional quality of food sources across a natural nutrient gradient. The nutrient gradient across the five studied reefs in the Seychelles (Fregate, Aride, Cousine, Felicite) correlates with seabird populations on islands and was confirmed by elevated $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ signals in reef macroalgae. Bite rates of parrotfishes scale allometrically with fish size and show different patterns across species and sites, but the correlation with site-specific $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ signals is weak. Using microhistology analysis we are currently investigating if seabird nutrient subsidies alter densities and composition of cyanobacteria and other photoautotrophs in feeding substrates, potentially affecting nutritional quality of food resources, and explaining patterns in feeding rates. On a reef scale, total parrotfish biomass (UVC-surveys) is higher around islands with large seabird colonies, which together with site-specific feeding rates leads to 2-3-fold increases in grazing, bioerosion and sediment production. This demonstrates that island and reef ecosystems are tightly connected, and that the restoration of natural nutrient pathways may benefit reef functioning.

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² Lancaster Environment Centre, Lancaster, UK

Understanding early reproductive failure in turtles and tortoises

Type: talk

Lavigne, Alessia M¹; Bullock, Robert⁴; Shah, Nirmal Jivan³; Tagg, Chris³; Zora, Anna²; Hemmings, Nicola¹

Abstract: Turtles and tortoises are facing an extinction crisis, and ecosystems in the Seychelles and globally are at risk of collapsing with the loss of key roles they play. Hatching failure is a crucial barrier to population growth and persistence, but its causes are poorly understood, and it is unknown whether fertilisation rates are declining as populations become smaller and more female-biased. Here, we first show via a review of current scientific literature that fertilisation rates are considered in only a small proportion of studies of turtle and tortoise hatching success, and those studies that do attempt to measure fertilisation rates use unreliable methods. We also show that studies of hatching success are biased towards marine turtles, as opposed to freshwater and terrestrial species, and wild rather than captive populations. We address the lack of reliable methods for assessing fertilisation rates by developing and testing a microscopy-based method for detecting perivitelline membrane (PVM) bound sperm and embryonic nuclei in the germinal disc of unhatched eggs. We demonstrate that this method can provide unequivocal evidence of egg fertilisation in five different turtle and tortoise species from both captive and wild populations in the Seychelles, even after eggs have been left in the nest for the full incubation period. This approach represents a valuable new tool for monitoring egg fertility and embryo survival rates in turtles and tortoises, with the potential to provide important insights into the underlying drivers of reproductive failure and aid the conservation of Seychelles turtle and tortoise populations.

1: The University of Sheffield

2: Fregate Island Foundation

Island Conservation Society

Marine Conservation Society Seychelles

3: Nature Seychelles

North Island Company Limited

Olive Ridley Project Seychelles

4: Save Our Seas Foundation (SOSF)

Seychelles Conservation and Climate Adaptation Trust (SeyCCAT)

Seychelles Island Foundation

Principles for transformative ocean governance

Type: talk

Amanda T. Lombard¹, Jai Clifford-Holmes^{1,2}, Victoria Goodall^{1,3}, Bernadette Snow^{1,4}, Hannah Truter¹, Patrick Vrancken^{1,5}, Peter J. S. Jones⁶, Kevern Cochrane⁷, Wesley Flannery⁸, Christina Hicks⁹, Lena Gipperth¹⁰, Edward H. Allison¹¹, Daniela Diz¹², Kimberley Peters^{13,14,15}, Bolanle Erinosh¹⁶, Phillip Levin¹⁷, Paul Holthus¹⁸, María Nube Szephegyi¹⁹, Adnan Awad²⁰, Harrison Golo²¹ & Elisa Morgera²²

With a focus on oceans, we collaborated across ecological, social and legal disciplines to respond to the United Nations call for transformation in the '2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development'. We developed a set of 13 principles that strategically and critically connect transformative ocean research to transformative ocean governance (complementing the UN Decade for Ocean Science). We used a rigorous, iterative and transparent consensus-building approach to define the principles, which can interact in supporting, neutral or sometimes conflicting ways. We recommend that the principles could be applied as a comprehensive set and discuss how to learn from their interactions, particularly those that reveal hidden tensions. The principles can bring and keep together partnerships for innovative ocean action. This action must respond to the many calls to reform current ocean-use practices which are based on economic growth models that have perpetuated inequities and fuelled conflict and environmental decline. We will focus in this presentation on the application of the principles to the Western Indian Ocean (WIO) region and how the principles may inform the regional marine spatial planning strategy developed for UNEP-Nairobi Convention in 2021 (Lombard et al.).

Publication: Lombard et al. 2023. Principles for transformative ocean governance. *Nature Sustainability*. 2023 Sep 7:1-3.

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- 3 Department of Statistics, Nelson Mandela University, Gqeberha, South Africa.
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- 5 Faculty of Law, Nelson Mandela University, Gqeberha, South Africa.
- 6 Department of Geography, University College London, London, UK.
- 7 Department of Ichthyology and Fisheries Science, Rhodes University, Makhanda, South Africa.
- 8 Environmental Planning, Queen's University Belfast, Belfast, UK.
- 9 Lancaster Environment Centre, Lancaster University, Lancashire, UK.
- 10 School of Business, Economics and Law, University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, Sweden.
- 11 WorldFish, Batu Maung, Penang, Malaysia.
- 12 The Lyell Centre, Heriot-Watt University, Edinburgh, UK.
- 13 Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung, Bremerhaven, Germany.
- 14 Helmholtz-Institute for Functional Marine Biodiversity, University of Oldenburg, Oldenburg, Germany.
- 15 Institute for Chemistry and Biology of Marine Environments, University of Oldenburg, Oldenburg, Germany.
- 16 Faculty of Law, University of Cape Coast, Cape Coast, Ghana.
- 17 The Nature Conservancy, University of Washington, Seattle, WA, USA.
- 18 World Ocean Council, Honolulu, HI, USA.
- 19 Marine Program, Vida Silvestre Uruguay, Montevideo, Uruguay.
- 20 The Nature Conservancy, Cape Town, South Africa.
- 21 Centre for Conflict, Human Rights and Peace Studies, University of Education, Winneba, Ghana.
- 22 UKRI GCRF One Ocean Hub, Strathclyde Centre for Environmental Law and Governance, Strathclyde University Law School, Glasgow, UK.

Baseline study to investigate demersal fish assemblage using baited Remote Underwater video (BRUV) on Mahe Plateau

Type: Poster

Rosabella Mangroo

The Seychelles small-scale demersal fishery is concentrated mainly on the Mahé plateau. Over the years the demand for the fish has increased resulting in increased vessel sizes and the number and improvement in fishing techniques. These changes have direct impact on fisheries resources. In addition, such changes, if not properly understood, it can potentially complicate the interpretation of fisheries dependent indices of stock status. It is imperative that the fisheries resources are monitored and assessed to determine changes in stocks. Fisheries independent surveys can potentially be used to provide reliable measures of relative abundance and size composition of various fish species which can be used to inform stock status.

A pilot study was carried out, the aim is to test the effectiveness of Stere0 Baited Remote Underwater Videos (BRUVS) a fisheries independent tool to identify, estimate abundance and distribution of the fish assemblages over various areas on the Mahé plateau. This study was carried out across the Mahé plateau exploring more of the fishing grounds where most of the artisanal fishers community would harvest fish. The sampling design involved the systematic stratification of the study areas with deployments carried out in shallow (10-30 m), Mid (31 – 50 m) and deep (51 -70m) depths and in various random benthic habitats. The videos recorded from the field work was analyzed using the EventMeasure software to obtain species composition, diversity and relative abundance.

During the pilot survey which took place in November and December 2020 a total of 76 BRUV deployments were carried out. A total of 506 fish species and 37 families were recorded, the most common species recorded was *Lethrinus variegatus*, *Carangoides fulvoguttatus*, *Aprion Virescens*, *Parupeneus barberinus* and different species of *Acanthuridae*. The species richness and abundance was greater in coral reef habitats and at depth of 10m – 30m. The data suggest that the benthic habitat type plays more of a factor than depth. Results were successfully obtained from the trip which highlighted the success of BRUVS as a fisheries independent tool to collect data on the plateau fish community. Considering the many factors affecting fisheries (such as visibility, water temperature, moon phase....) the data can be made more rigorous by having models that consider influence of such factors.

Seychelles Fishing Authority

Fish Diversity Associations Across Habitat Types Within the Denis Island Zone 2 Sustainable Use Marine Protected Area

Type: talk

Annia Marengo¹, Stuart Laing^{1,2,3}, Kaylee Smit^{3,4}, Murray Duncan^{1,2}

Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) are vital for conserving and managing fish stocks. However, understanding baseline fish diversity patterns is crucial for practical and effective designs and monitoring. The Seychelles Marine Spatial Planning (SMSP) is denoting and establishing critical management zones at the Denis Island Zone 2 MPA. However, little information about the island's fish diversity patterns and habitat association are known. We quantified fish diversity around the Denis Island MPA using the Baited Remoted Underwater Stereo Video System (stereo-BRUVS). We also determined and quantified the most critical habitats for diversity. Using the Shannon-Weiner Diversity Index, we find significantly more fish diversity in rocky rubble than in sand habitats. Fish diversity increased with depth for both habitat types, but the relationship was revealed to be insignificant. While the habitat types are associated with different diversities and will require targeted and specific monitoring, our results propose that continued monitoring across depth may not be necessary to quantify changes. This study can serve as a baseline for locally assessing changes in fish diversity in pre- and post-MPA establishments.

1: University of Seychelles

2: Blue Economy Research Institute

3: Ocean Life Sciences

4: South African Institute for Aquatic Biodiversity

Effects of climate variability and change on tuna fisheries in the Indian Ocean

Type: talk

Francis Marsac

The economies of many countries and small island developing states (SIDS) in the Western Indian Ocean (WIO) are strongly dependent on large-scale commercial industrial tuna fisheries and small-scale coastal fisheries. Climate change has already produced observable impacts on fisheries throughout the WIO, including shifts in spatial distribution and range of tropical tuna species. This talk will briefly describe the Indian Ocean Dipole, (IOD) the main tracer of interannual ocean variability in the Indian Ocean. Then we shall review the various impacts of the coupled IOD/ENSO system on catchability and abundance of tuna species, and its economic implications in the Seychelles-based tuna industry. Finally, we shall present the projections of key ocean variables for the 21st century, and how this would affect tunas and their fisheries. Warmer habitats with declining productivity would cause potential tuna fishing grounds shift well outside the core of the current WIO fishery for the industrial surface fishery. The longline fishery would be less affected than the purse seine fishery and the WIO and Seychelles EEZ could remain potential longline fishing grounds under conditions in which deep longlining is performed. Ocean-climate trends must be monitored cautiously to develop adaptive harvest models ensuring the sustainability of tuna fisheries.

Institute of Research for sustainable Development (IRD), France

Climate change affects multiple coral reef fisheries ecosystem services

Type: talk

Sarah Martin

Coral reef fisheries support livelihoods and provide an affordable, local source of essential dietary nutrients to coastal people. But reef ecosystems are undergoing fundamental changes following climate-driven coral bleaching, leading to dramatically altered reef habitats, and changes in reef fish assemblages, functional composition, diversity and productivity. Yet the consequences for fisheries, and the associated nutritional and cost implications are not well understood. Here, we use data from climate-impacted artisanal trap fisheries in the Seychelles to explore how fisheries outcomes vary across divergent reef states. Coral reefs that had recovered from bleaching events provided the highest catch rates and economic returns for fishers, supporting diverse catches that were affordable for a range of consumers. Yet overall yields were greater from reefs that had undergone regime-shifts to macroalgal-dominated states, indicating higher fisheries dependence on these habitats. The total nutrient content of reef fish landings was high across all habitats, but varied by nutrient, suggesting that fishing across a range of reef habitats provides the greatest variety of nutrients to coastal communities. While coral reefs are unlikely to return to pre-bleached states, recovered reefs may still support diverse and productive fisheries, maintaining fisher livelihoods and accessibility of fish. Degraded macroalgal-reefs can also support productive fisheries, yielding a less diverse but still highly nutritious food supply.

1. Lancaster Environment Centre, Lancaster University, UK.
2. Seychelles Fishing Authority, Victoria, Seychelles.
3. University of Western Australia, Indian Ocean Marine Research Centre, Crawley, Western Australia.

Rapid Assessment of fish biodiversity in shallow water habitats of the Alphonse Group

Type: talk

Eleanor Brighton¹, [Christophe Mason-Parker](#)²

In order to implement conservation measures that are appropriate, specific and effective to a certain marine ecosystem, it is crucial to have an understanding of the species present. Fish diversity and the relative abundance of different species within tropical marine ecosystems, particularly coral reefs, has often shown to correlate closely with overall ecosystem health and resilience. The isolation of the Alphonse Group (+400km from Mahe) combined with the relative lack of anthropogenic pressure means it is likely a hotspot of marine biodiversity yet very little information exists as to the species present. In March 2022 a rapid assessment of fish species found around the Alphonse Group was conducted. The study was based on a similar previous assessment at D'Arros Island in 2017. In total 41 in-water hours were spent collecting photographic data from 36 sites covering 10 habitat types. 479 species were recorded from 68 families which is consistent with comparable sites recognized as having high levels of marine biodiversity in the region, and higher than the global average for shallow-water tropical ecosystems. Highlights from the study include the documentation of 7 species of fish in the Seychelles for the first time, including a range extension of ~1500km in the case of *Pseudanthias parvirostris*. Two species were not recognised and are possibly unidentified: *Opistognathus* sp. and *Trimma* sp, the latter is currently undergoing morphological and genetic analysis in Canada. The study also recorded species of high conservation importance: 3 species listed as Endangered or Critically Endangered and 9 as Vulnerable on the IUCN Red List, including 10 species of elasmobranchs.

1: Blue Safari Seychelles

2: Marine Conservation Society Seychelles

Breeding success monitoring of the Red-footed booby on Farquhar atoll, Seychelles.

Type: talk

William McNeely¹, Elena Levorato¹, Gregory Berke¹, Gerard Rocamora^{2,1}

The Red-footed booby (RFB) – *Sula sula* is an iconic seabird nesting on the Atoll of Farquhar, Seychelles. In 2016, Fantala, the strongest cyclone ever recorded in the SW Indian Ocean hit the atoll three times, destroying most of the RFB preferred nesting areas. Indeed, before Fantala, most of the colony was nesting in tall Casuarina trees – *Casuarina equisetifolia*, but, after the passage of the cyclone, which brought down many of these large trees, the birds adapted by building nests in lower trees, mainly Pemphis – *Pemphis acidula*, and less frequently coconut trees – *Cocos nucifera* and tree heliotrope - *Heliotropium foertherianum*. Today, the colony is mostly gathered on Ile du Sud, in two coastal lagoons formed by a sand bar, where salty water enters during high tide, called Barachois. They are also found in lower numbers on the leeward coasts of Ile du Sud and Ile du Nord with an estimate of more than 9000 pairs breeding annually. As a consequence of their adaptation to nesting in lower vegetation, most of the nests were easily accessible for the Island Conservation Society (ICS) to monitor their breeding success. In 2023, 120 nests at egg stage were selected and monitored until either failure or fledging of the chick, resulting in a 37% reproductive success. However, this might be an overestimate of the actual breeding success, due to a bias in the nest selection. Therefore, ICS is currently working on developing a more accurate yet not more time-consuming method to reduce biases to a minimum and get success values that are more accurate. Long-term monitoring of the breeding success of the RFB on Farquhar provides valuable insights on the demographic trend in one of the biggest breeding colonies in Seychelles. Such data may also indicate potential conservation issues. For example, a decrease of breeding success can reveal a degradation of their nesting habitat or of their foraging grounds, leading to prompt targeted investigations and responses.

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Coastal Erosion: Coastal development and Climate change in the Seychelles

Type: talk

Jean Luc Mondon

Climate variability has an undoubtable effect on the Earth's surface ever since it came to existence. Recently the effect of climate change on coastal areas of the main islands of Seychelles has received increased attention and this is because islands are particularly susceptible to such effects that include increase in sea-level as well as more frequent and intense storm events. Climate change coupled with insufficient or poor urban planning and development contribute to the growing threat to the islands' coastlines. This study describes these threats to the coastlines, with emphasis on increased storm surges and coastal retreat. The main factors driving physical change in the coastal areas of the Seychelles are wind, waves, ocean currents, the Seychelles plateau and coastal development. The combined effects of these factors, together have become increasingly evident with beach erosion and coastal retreat on the shores of Mahe, the main island of the Seychelles. In response to this the government belatedly implemented mitigation measures to protect its flat coastal zones from coastal erosion and coastal flooding without properly using a coastal management plan, no proper EIA and mitigation measures are often implemented on a post disaster basis. Such mitigation measures systematically involves hard structures such as seawalls, rock armoured coastal extensions and artificial islands, have ultimately altered the natural coastal ocean currents and consequently impacted the balance of erosion and deposition of sediments along the coastlines. Channels to facilitate fisheries and the tourism facilities have also changed the natural coastal currents also contributing to these sedimentary changes. This study also highlights the critical intersection of climate change and coastal development in Seychelles, resulting in heightened threats. This study emphasizes the need for more sustainable and adaptable coastal management plans to address the actual cause effectively. Smarter approaches are essential for the long-term resilience of Seychelles' coastlines. This study seeks to undertake an overall review of the impacts of various coastal developments and hard engineering associated with coastal erosion and coastal protection on Mahe Island.

Petro Seychelles

BLUE CARBON STOCKS OF SEYCHELLES' LARGEST MANGROVES

Type: talk

Wartman M*, Costa MDP*, Palacios MM, Nourice B, Macreadie PI, Constance A, Oehri J, Bunbury N, Wiesenberg G, Pennekamp F, A'Bear L, Fleischer-Dogley F, Schaepman-Strub G, [Montano L.](#)

Mangrove forests are highly effective carbon sinks, playing an important role in climate change mitigation. With 78% of Seychelles' mangrove forest located on Aldabra, it is crucial that the management of the carbon sink capacity of Aldabra's mangroves is data-driven. Recent studies have focused on establishing baseline data on the carbon content of Aldabra's mangroves and understanding which factors influence this. As part of a broader blue carbon assessment in Seychelles, mangrove biomass and soil cores across various sites were analysed to estimate the above- and below-ground carbon content of Aldabra's mangrove forests. In parallel, we used structural equation modelling to assess the direct and indirect environmental factors on above-ground biomass, an established indicator of organic carbon stock. It was found that Aldabra holds approximately 67% of Seychelles' total carbon stocks, at 462,451 tonnes. This carbon reservoir is differentially distributed, with 64% stored as inorganic carbon in the soil, 19% as organic carbon in below-ground biomass and 18% as organic carbon in above-ground biomass. Modelling identified soil nutrient content as having the greatest impact on organic carbon stocks (standard estimate = 0.80, $p < 0.05$), with water level variation positively impacting soil nutrient content (0.73, $p < 0.05$), while soil salinity demonstrated no significant impact. These studies emphasise the importance of adopting a holistic ecosystem-level management approach to protect Aldabra's mangroves. This is crucial to maintain the integrity of Seychelles' carbon sink capacity, especially in the context of optimising Seychelles' potential for blue carbon credits, which could in turn be used to finance the management of a globally significant site.

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Finfish species comparison: Evaluating the potential for aquaculture success in the Seychelles.

Type: talk

Walter Lawrence Grant¹, [Devis Dean Paul Monthy](#)¹

Given Seychelles' unique environment and absence of previous finfish aquaculture, it is important to evaluate which species have the most promise to ensure the resources spent on aquaculture development are wisely applied. A multiphase and multitiered approach was taken in assessing potential species for aquaculture. In the first phase a variety of factors have been considered such as market price, growth rate, hardiness, abundance, scientific knowledge, and their suitability for cage culture in Seychelles. Only indigenous species were considered as specified by legislation. More than 1000 species of fish have been identified in Seychelles and in the first phase 8 of the most likely candidates were selected for further analysis. The following species were on the short list: Camouflage Grouper (*Epinephellus polyphkadion*), Brown Marbled Grouper (*Epinephelus fuscoguttatus*), Mangrove Snapper (*Lutjanus argentimaculatus*), Emperor Snapper (*Lutjanus sebae*), Green jobfish (*Aprion virescens*), Longfin Amberjack (*Seriola rivoliana*), Greater Amberjack (*Seriola dumerilii*) and Golden Pompano (*Trachinotus blochii*). These species were assessed based on broodstock husbandry, first feeding, weaning, hardiness, growth rate and market price. Each category had a ranking system that was utilized to score the potential of each species with the highest total score indicating the most favored species. The three species that ranked the highest were Mangrove Snapper (*Lutjanus argentimaculatus*), Longfin Amberjack (*Seriola rivoliana*) and Golden Pompano (*Trachinotus blochii*). A SWOT analysis was performed on these three species to further understand the risks and advantages of each species for aquaculture in Seychelles.

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From data to recommendations: long-term analysis of *Tripneustes gratilla* (collector sea urchin) disease and mortality in aquaculture

Type: poster

Zachary Morin¹, Shamira Payet¹, Bas de Vos^{1,2}

Sea urchins are a culinary delicacy with high demand in Asian countries and expanding markets in Europe and North American. Due to the rise in demand, high value wild sea urchin stocks have been overexploited. Several countries are making attempts to culture sea urchins in aquaculture including the Seychelles where an indigenous species (*Tripneustes gratilla*) has been identified as the primary candidate for aquaculture due to its high value and fast growth rates. Unfortunately, this species of urchin is susceptible to the Bald Sea Urchin Disease (BSUD), that frequently leads to mortalities, which may be trigger by environmental factors such as temperature, oxygen and ammonia. The goal of this project is to see if BSUD can be avoided and potentially treated. To achieve this, we investigate what factors cause BSUD and mortalities among *T. gratilla* to see if said factors can be mitigated/controlled. At a sea urchin research facility in Providence, Mahe, there are records of temperature, dissolved oxygen (DO), ammonia and the quantity urchin mortalities and disease rates from 2019 until present. This long-term data set offers a unique opportunity, to conduct a meta-analysis to determine the influence and correlations of these environmental factors on urchin disease and mortality. This analysis may reveal insight into environmental conditions and thresholds that promote health and production of *T. gratilla*. This study will provide recommendation to future *T. gratilla* farmers on what conditions are optimal to reduce or avoid diseases and mortalities within their stock.

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² GOPA, Hamburg, Germany

Decades of declining trends in body size of nesting hawksbill and green turtles in Seychelles

Type: talk

Jeanne A Mortimer^{1,2,3}, Sean Evans⁴, Melissa J Schulze⁴, Nicole Esteban⁵, Mark Brown⁶, Graeme Hays⁷

Adult body size has implications for how animals allocate limited resources towards growth, survival, and reproduction. Mean body size of sea turtles varies across populations and over time. Long term monitoring of green turtles (*Chelonia mydas*) at Aldabra Atoll and hawksbills (*Eretmochelys imbricata*) at Cousin/Cousine Islands in Seychelles was conducted by flipper tagging and measuring carapace lengths of nesting females each season to determine both mean annual carapace length and adult female growth rates at each site. Curved carapace lengths of nesting females declined by about 0.64 cm^{-yr} for green turtles, and 0.05 cm^{-yr} for hawksbills during 1996-2016 and 1974-2022, respectively. Meanwhile, mean annual female growth rates were 0.14 cm^{-yr} for green turtles, and 0.18 cm^{-yr} for hawksbills. Possible mechanisms responsible for declining body size over time include mortality of larger turtles due to human impact, declines in size at maturity caused by ecosystem change at developmental (juvenile) feeding grounds, and an increase in the relative proportion of neophyte (new) nesting females in response to conservation. By saturation tagging the nesting hawksbills at Cousine Island, it was possible to distinguish between neophyte and remigrant females and demonstrate both significant decline in size at maturity and increases in relative proportion of neophytes.

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In the end it all comes down to poop: Diet assessment of two reef associated shark species at a remote tropical nursery site in the Indian Ocean.

Type: talk

Ellie Moulinie*¹, Maurits van Zinnicq Bergmann², Nico Fassbender³, Dillys Pouponeau¹, Henriette Grimmel¹ and Robert Bullock¹

Accuracy in techniques for determining dietary ranges is critical in understanding community ecology and species requirements in different ecosystems. This study explores the application of novel DNA metabarcoding techniques to resolve the precise diet composition and ontogenetic diet shifts of two sympatric, reef associated shark species. Juvenile blacktip reef sharks (*Carcharhinus melanopterus*) and sicklefin lemon sharks (*Negaprion acutidens*) were caught at thirteen different microhabitats across varying tidal phases in the St Joseph Atoll over one year. Feecal DNA (fDNA) samples were collected using a non-invasive cloacal swabbing method on 134 *Carcharhinus melanopterus* and 35 *Negaprion acutidens*. Information on physical and environmental conditions were also collected and used to investigate differences in feeding ecology and body condition of juvenile sharks occupying different microhabitats within the study site. fDNA swabs were analyzed using DNA metabarcoding to elucidate shark diet up to 14 days before sample collection. Here we present the preliminary results from a sub-set of samples collected between October 2022- 2023. This novel research will aid in unravelling the intricacies of the feeding ecology and diet of juvenile sharks and inform the management and conservation of critical nursery areas. Keywords: metabarcoding; elasmobranch; cloacal swabbing; sympatric species; blacktip reef shark, sicklefin lemon shark

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Aldabra Reef Monitoring: Results and lessons from 10 years of annual data collection

Type: poster

Anna Koester*, Ella Nancy** , Luke A'Bear, April Jasmine Burt, Karen Chong-Seng, Philip Haupt, Cheryl Sanchez, Nancy Bunbury, Frauke Fleischer-Dogley

Coral reefs are exceptionally biodiverse ecosystems and their integrity is paramount for coastal societies. Nevertheless, coral reefs experience significant local and global anthropogenic pressures, and provide a sensitive indicator of coastal ocean health and climate change. Reef monitoring programmes have therefore become a standard tool to track changes within these ecosystems and are essential to better inform science, management and policy. Aldabra Atoll offers the opportunity to study coral reef ecosystem changes in the absence of substantial local human pressure. The Seychelles Islands Foundation (SIF) has monitored Aldabra's coral reef benthic and fish assemblages annually since 2013 through the Aldabra Reef Monitoring (ARM) programme. The implementation of the ARM programme started 2 years before the third global coral bleaching event, which hit Aldabra in 2015/2016. ARM data revealed an overall decline of 52% in live hard coral cover across Aldabra's reefs, which varied across locations and depths, with lagoonal reefs experiencing the lowest (34%), and the shallow eastern seaward reefs the highest (62%) coral mortality. Declines were also observed in the density of coral juveniles, with a 48% drop across all reefs following the bleaching, whilst the abundance of fish, particularly herbivores and omnivores, increased by 77% on shallow reefs. Our results showcase Aldabra's reef ecosystem trajectories over the past 10 years in the context of historically available data. Challenges and lessons learned are highlighted and SIF's current and future endeavours within the ARM programme are outlined.

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Comparison of migrations of post-nesting hawksbill and green turtles satellite tracked from Alphonse and Saint François Atolls, Seychelles.

Type: talk

Josep Nogués^{1,2, #}, David March^{3,4}, Ariadna Fernández¹, Christopher Narty¹, Jeanne A. Mortimer^{1,5,6}

Important populations of green turtles (*Chelonia mydas*) and hawksbills (*Eretmochelys imbricata*) nest on the beaches of the islands nations of the south-west Indian Ocean region. The identification of migratory corridors connecting nesting sites to foraging areas is essential to ensure the regional genetic diversity of long-lived, marine turtle populations and define effective conservation efforts. From August 2017 to August 2019 we satellite tracked the migrations of post-nesting green turtles (7) and hawksbills (3) from the Alphonse Group (AG) in the Outer Islands of Seychelles. Nine of 10 tracked individuals migrated to distant foraging grounds for periods of between 3 and 42 days. We describe 2 general movement patterns of migration: (1) direct movement to one or two regional foraging grounds and (2) long-distance oceanic crossing followed by coastal migration along the coastlines of east Africa. We found a clear dichotomy in speed behaviour during migration period (mean = 54,57 km/day) than to the prior-migration or foraging periods (mean= 4,2 km/day). All foraging sites for 9 turtles were located in shallow areas, whether in offshore Seychelles islands and Mahé plateau, or in coastal areas along the coastlines of east Africa in the western Indian Ocean (WIO). Four green and three hawksbill turtles (7) crossed the deep waters of the Indian Ocean during their journeys. 5 of the 10 turtles (2 greens and 3 hawksbills) remained in the Seychelles Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) of 1.37 M km², while the other 4 green turtles did long-distance oceanic migrations to Tanzania, Kenya (2) and Somalia. This range encompasses a >1.7 M km² section between Seychelles' marine waters and the coastline of east Africa, highlighting the need for supporting effective conservation strategies to protect regionally important foraging areas, such as those in the Seychelles Bank, and strengthening international cooperation in identifying and mitigating foraging grounds threats and further establishing Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) from networks of small coastal MPAs up to vast MPAs that can protect such key areas, migratory corridors and benefit future conservation efforts for both critically endangered and endangered populations within the Seychelles and the broader WIO.

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Uncovering the relationship between light intensity and *Tripneustes gratilla*: implications for aquaculture

Type: talk

Shamira Payet

Tripneustes gratilla, a promising sea urchin species for aquaculture, utilizes debris to cover itself. It is believed it does so to avoid light, which implies potential negative effects of high light levels on production, impacting both profitability and ethical considerations. This study aimed to empirically validate these concerns. Higher solar radiation intensity correlated with an increased collection of covering materials per urchin ($H(3) = 7.844$, $p = 0.049$). Unlike prior studies on *T. gratilla* from different regions, this research found no evidence that covering materials were chosen for their shading ability (transparency; $F(2, 33) = 0.27$, $p = 0.765$), indicating regional behavioural variations. While high light intensity reduced fitness ($H(2) = 5.615$, $p = 0.020$), this effect occurred only when urchins were acclimated to low light. A long-term experiment demonstrated that *T. gratilla* can acclimatize to higher light intensities, showing no significant differences in fitness, mortality, disease susceptibility, growth, and gonadosomatic index ($p > 0.128$). Although shading may not be a strict requirement for *T. gratilla* aquaculture, it is recommended for consideration. The findings underscore the importance of gradual acclimatization when altering light conditions and emphasize the need to account for regional variations in *T. gratilla* behaviour.

SFA Aquaculture

Underwater cultural heritage for a blue economy in Seychelles

Type: poster

Dr Elena Perez-Alvaro

Oceans should be understood as a complex set of sites, landscapes and narratives that involve multiple players and perspectives centred not only on trade, leisure and energy, but also on subsistence, regional development and belief systems. Consequently, the remains of the activities in the oceans, what we understand as underwater cultural heritage, include cultural and natural tangible as well as intangible cultural heritage, human remains, practices and oral histories. This presentation will study how and why the consideration of underwater cultural heritage is a key piece to reach a sustainable blue economy model in Seychelles. The presentation will explore the importance of this submerged knowledge for the countries' identity and the necessity of protecting it as an integral heritage, a heritage where natural, cultural and intangible heritage can be understood as just one.

Nelson Mandela University, South Africa

UNIR, Spain

ICOMOS International Committee on the Underwater Cultural Heritage

Into the shallows: atypical behavior of the Risso's dolphin around the atoll of St. Joseph, Amirantes

Type: talk

Rachel Pool¹, Michelle Caputo^{1,2}, Jeremy J. Kiszka^{1,2}

The Risso's dolphin (*Grampus griseus*) is a deep diving delphinid that occurs in tropical and temperate waters around the globe. While present in both coastal and oceanic habitats, this species exhibits a preference for steep-sloped bottoms and the outer edges of continental shelves (>200 m). In the Indian Ocean, Risso's dolphins have predominantly been recorded around oceanic islands including Seychelles, where they have been recorded at high densities. In November 2022 and November 2023, small vessel-based surveys were undertaken to assess the distribution, abundance and behavior of small cetaceans around D'Arros–St. Joseph. Risso's dolphins were the most common species (37% of all sightings, n=41), followed by spinner dolphins (*Stenella longirostris*, 31.8%) and Indo-Pacific bottlenose dolphins (*Tursiops aduncus*, 30.9%). Risso's dolphins were recorded at an average depth of 151.6m (minimum=7 m, maximum=899 m), with 57% of sightings near or on coral reefs and seagrass meadows. Group size ranged from 1 to 50 individuals (mean=12.7, SD=10.5), and group composition varied, with 48.8% of groups composed of only adults (likely males), 26.8% of mother-calf pairs (nursery groups), and 24.4% were mixed groups of adults, juveniles and calves. Photo-identification was used to estimate population size, examine site fidelity and social structure. A total of 204 individuals were identified and 34 (16.7%) were resighted at least two times. The importance of reef-associated habitats for Risso's dolphins observed here is unique and raises the need for future investigation into the role of this species in nutrient transport and cycling in these habitats.

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Plankton soup: Investigating reef manta ray feeding ecology at an important aggregation site in Seychelles

Type: talk

Dillys Pouponeau^{1,2,3}, Ellie Moulinie¹, Henriette Grimmel¹ and Robert Bullock¹

The availability of food is a key component critical for the survival of any species. Reef manta rays (*Manta alfredi*) are listed as vulnerable on the IUCN Red List with a decreasing population, globally. Understanding their feeding ecology at key aggregation sites will therefore be essential to informing future protection measures. This study investigates how much, when and where reef manta rays feed around D'Arros Island in the Amirantes, which represents the largest population of reef manta rays in Seychelles and serves as an important feeding ground. Boat and snorkel surveys quantified the presence/absence of manta rays at specific sites around D'Arros Island year-round, observing their feeding and non-feeding behaviors respectively. Plankton samples were regularly collected and environmental data recorded. These data were combined to assess feeding thresholds and investigate spatiotemporal patterns in feeding behavior. Thus far, findings indicate a strong, tidally influenced correlation between plankton densities and manta feeding behavior, with particular micro-locations highlighted as key feeding areas. These results will further be used to develop a predictive model for manta ray visitation and feeding at D'Arros and will contribute to setting appropriate regulations within this newly designated MPA.

Keywords: *Mobula alfredi*, feeding ecology, zooplankton, prey density patterns, Seychelles;

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Development of *Scylla serrata* (mud crab) juvenile production in the Seychelles

Type: poster

Danroy Prudence, Shamira Payet¹, Lawrence Grant¹, Devis Monty¹, Bas de Vos^{1,2}

The mud crab species, *Scylla serrata*, is the focus of both commercial fisheries and aquaculture production throughout their distribution and is one of the most traded and valuable seafoods in several Indo-pacific countries. It is highly suited to aquaculture in Seychelles, due to its high value, low space requirements and being indigenous. Efforts have been made to establish an industry relying on the grow-out of wild caught juveniles. However, initial attempts of capturing wild juveniles have not been highly successful, indicating the wild population in Seychelles may not be large enough to support this industry. This project addresses the issue of the lack of juvenile mud crabs for aquaculture by taking the initial steps to develop larval production of *S. serrata* in the Seychelles. Specifically, the objective is to determine the lighting and temperature parameters which best induce spawning of robust *S. serrata*. This will be achieved by holding *S. serrata* broodstock in culture systems in various settings, namely indoors, partially shaded outdoors and fully shade outdoors. Over a two-month period, the frequency of spawning, quantity and quality of eggs and the survival of the larvae will be compared between treatments. This research will be an important first step to commence the production of juvenile *S. serrata* in the Seychelles. This will allow for aquacultural production to serve both the local and export markets. Additionally, there is scope to use juveniles to restock overfished mangroves across Seychelles, thus benefiting both the environment and the surrounding communities.

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² GOPA, Hamburg, Germany

Dispersive migration and interbreeding distribution of White-tailed tropicbirds nesting on Aride Island, Seychelles.

Type: talk

Gérard Rocamora^{1,2}, Ricky Payet^{2,3}, Annette L. Fayet^{4,5}

The foraging ecology and distribution of the White-tailed tropicbird *Phaethon lepturus* was recently investigated in Seychelles with GPS devices, but their migratory movements after breeding and their non-breeding distribution remain poorly known. In order to investigate these aspects, thirty breeding adults, including 4 pairs, were caught in February-March 2020 at incubation stage on Aride Island, ringed and put back on their nest after a geolocator (GLS) was attached to the bird's ring (total weight < 2gr). These devices recorded the daily location and the activity of the birds (wet/dry) for up to two years, allowing to geolocate them with a limited precision of c. 180 km only. Specific periodic searches to recapture birds with geolocators were started on Aride after 8-9 months, in addition to the weekly routine tropicbird nest monitoring performed by the Aride Island Nature Reserve team across the island's plateau. An additional three birds were equipped in June 2021, two of which were found breeding again 8-9 months later, in February-March 2022. Only 45% of GLS were retrieved (the last one in August 2023) and the data from 12 GLS, representing an average of 329 ± 31 days of tracking per bird, were recovered and analysed. Following filtration of errors including around equinoxes, density kernels were calculated for 50 % and 90 % for each bird, and non-breeding tracks were identified. Results show a very wide dispersive migration of non-breeding birds across much of the Western Indian Ocean, and to the East almost up to Indonesia for some birds, with a maximum recorded distance from Aride of 4374 km (average: $2,523 \pm 246$) and an average distance from the colony of 1269 km +/- 167 km, well beyond the boundaries of the Seychelles EEZ, with wide differences between individuals. The estimated length of the non-breeding season was 126 +/- 19 days. Such a remarkable wide-ranging distribution out of the breeding season – spanning over 5000 km of latitude and 3000 km of longitude – reveals the difficulty to define conservation measures at a sufficiently wide scale to help protect this species, which has been declining on Aride over the last 20-30 years. By providing new data on the non-breeding movements of white-tailed tropicbirds, this study helps us to document migration strategy and at-sea distribution of this species, and to better understand its conservation management needs. Future research goals include increasing the sample size to further investigate the length of the non-breeding season, confirm the observed patterns, and determine potential sex differences and if the species' preference for deep waters during breeding persists during the non-breeding season.

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Investigating the feasibility and conditions for outdoor microalgae cultivation in Seychelles

Type: poster

Maria Rose¹, Shamira Payet¹, Lawrence Grant¹, Bas de Vos^{1,2}

Microalgae are crucial for the aquaculture industry because they are the initial step in the food chain for nearly all aquaculture species, thus provide them with vital source of lipids, proteins and vitamins. Most microalgae are produced indoors under controlled environment conditions in laboratories, which is highly resource intensive. However, farming microalgae outdoors in Seychelles is hypothesized to be cost-effective and more environmentally friendly due to abundant sunlight and ideal temperatures. The outdoor setting minimizes the need for sophisticated facilities which demand substantial investments, making this approach accessible to a broader range of farmers and aquaculture practitioners. The objective of the study is to determine if outdoor cultivation is feasible and what are the optimal outdoor conditions for growing microalgae, specifically looking at the right amount of light and temperatures. The selected microalgae species to be used include, *Rhodomonas salina*, *Isochrysis galbana*, *Tetraselmis spp.*, *Nanochloropsis Oculata* and *Chaetoceros muelleri*. A factorial experimental design will be employed, encompassing four treatments: shaded, unshaded, cooling system, and non-cooling system. Additionally, a treatment will be maintained indoors under standard conditions as a control. The growth rates of each microalgae species under varied conditions will be evaluated. A pilot trial where *Tetraselmis spp.* was cultured outdoors, with temperatures achieving 37°C, demonstrated high specific growth rates of 0.176 (day⁻¹). The outcomes of this study are expected to provide valuable insights into the feasibility of outdoor microalgae production in Seychelles and provide recommendations for their growing conditions. Moreover, the research will contribute to the development of sustainable practices in the aquaculture industry by identifying cost-effective and environmentally sound approaches for microalgae cultivation in Seychelles.

1 Seychelles fishing Authority, Mahe

2 GOPA, Hamburg, Germany

Using photogrammetry to assess coral restoration success in the Cousin Island Special Reserve, Republic of Seychelles

Type: talk

Saponari Luca¹, Fallati Luca², Bernardi Lucas², Dale Charlotte¹, Shah Nirmal¹

Coral reefs, characterised by their remarkable biodiversity and critical ecological functions, serve as the foundation of marine ecosystems. Built by colonies of coral polyps, these structures play a pivotal role in supporting a vast array of species and providing essential habitat. Apart from their ecological significance, coral reefs provide essential services such as coastal protection, tourism, fisheries, and pharmaceutical resources. However, these vital ecosystems face a multitude of threats, primarily due to human activities, including pollution, mining, destructive fishing, and climate change-induced coral bleaching. In response to these challenges, coral restoration projects have gained importance. Among the techniques employed, coral gardening, involving the propagation of coral fragments in nurseries before transplantation, is widely used. Effective monitoring is essential for assessing restoration outcomes, ensuring project success, and maintaining stakeholder support. Traditional methods are often time-consuming, with low accuracy and in need of training and practice for non-technical operators. This study focuses on the application of underwater photogrammetry and the use of Structure-from-Motion (SfM) and Object-Based Image Analysis (OBIA) as an efficient monitoring solution for assessing coral restoration outcomes over time. It includes the use of color enhancement algorithms to improve image quality, enhancing the accuracy of the OBIA, best practices for survey techniques and evaluation of low-cost improvements. The research is conducted in Cousin Island Special Reserve, Seychelles, and assesses the applicability and accuracy of these techniques for tracking coral restoration efforts. The findings are expected to offer valuable insights into the feasibility of underwater SfM and OBIA as a monitoring approach for coral restoration projects, aiding in the conservation of these invaluable marine ecosystems.

Keywords: Photogrammetry, Object-Based Image Analysis, coral, coral restoration, Seychelles

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Evaluating the effect of outplant size on health, growth and associated fauna for *Acropora muricata* in Cousin Island Special Reserve for the creation of an asexual broodstock

Type: poster

Saponari Luca¹, Damstra Demi², Dale Charlotte¹, Antoine Athina¹, Ramkalawan Sam¹, Shah Nirmal¹

In a time when coral reefs face growing climate change-induced threats like bleaching and other anthropogenic environmental stressors such as pollution and overfishing, it is imperative that we protect these valuable ecosystems. Coral restoration is a vital part of that effort. This study evaluates the potential of an 'asexual coral broodstock' method for *Acropora muricata* in a mid-water floating nursery in the Seychelles, aiming to optimize local coral restoration methods and reduce pressure on healthy donor reefs. This concept entails outplanting fragmented corals derived from colonies growing in the nursery, instead of whole colonies. This effectively increases the number of corals available for outplanting without increasing the need for donor material from healthy reefs. The effect of two different coral stocking methods (fishing line and rope) and two different outplant sizes (fragments and colonies) on the health, growth, and associated fauna of outplanted corals was assessed over a timeframe of five months, utilizing a fully crossed experimental design. Survival was high for all treatments highlighting no effect from size or stocking method. The analysis revealed that fragments grew equally fast as colonies showing the suitability of outplanting fragments derived by nursery-grown corals. Similarly, the stocking method did not significantly impact coral health or growth rates. However, outplanted fully-grown colonies performed better in attracting coral-associated fauna, highlighting potential effects on coral recovery. The outcomes support the viability of an asexual coral broodstock concept, underlining its potential for enhancing local restoration practices in Seychelles and suggesting its applicability to coral reef restoration efforts worldwide.

Keywords: *Acropora muricata*, coral, coral restoration, broodstock, Seychelles, outplanting methods

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Using Coral Bleaching Automated Stress Surveys (CBASS) technology to identify thermotolerant species of coral to inform coral restoration practices

Type: poster

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Coral reefs, among the most biodiverse ecosystems on the planet, are facing unprecedented threats due to climate change and human activities. Understanding and monitoring the resilience of corals is paramount for their conservation. Nature Seychelles aims to introduce a novel approach for assessing coral resilience using Coral Bleaching Automated Stress Surveys (CBASS) technology. CBASS integrates a simple concept with the most up-to-date information on temperature modeling to quantify stress responses in corals accurately. By incorporating CBASS into ongoing restoration, conservation and monitoring programs, restoration practitioners, researchers and conservationists can gain critical insights into the health and resilience of corals, facilitating more targeted and effective strategies for their protection in the face of ongoing global challenges. This innovative method quantifies the extent of coral bleaching, a crucial indicator of coral stress and resilience. In addition, CBASS facilitates the measurement of recovery rates following bleaching events, enabling a dynamic assessment of coral resilience over time. Results will reveal significant insights into the intraspecific and interspecific resilience variability of various coral species and their responses to environmental stressors from donor sites in use by Nature Seychelles and enable the identification of resilient coral populations that can serve as crucial sources for coral restoration and conservation efforts.

Keywords: CBASS, bleaching, coral, coral restoration, Seychelles

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Listening to the reef: assessing coral restoration efficacy using soundscape data and machine learning in the Cousin Island Special Reserve, Seychelles

Type: poster

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The climate crisis is a time of rapid ecological change characterised by global losses of coral populations and associated reef taxa. Restoration efforts are integral to conserving ecological function in highly-valuable coral reef ecosystems. Monitoring of restoration progress is crucial to improving practices and sharing knowledge. Successful monitoring of restoration progress, as well as ecological change more generally, requires comprehensive metrics that integrate a range of taxa and processes that contribute to reef function. Traditional methods are often limited to visual surveys which tend to be highly taxon-specific, labour-intensive, and limited in their ability to provide more than a snapshot of relevant ecological processes. Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM) provides an effective complement to visual surveys as soundscapes are representative of a wealth of ecological taxa and processes associated with reef function. However, the use of PAM in the context of monitoring coral restoration progress is still relatively novel. Little is known about the processes governing soundscape recovery, nor is it understood whether recovering reefs may exhibit recovering soundscapes. Therefore, this study examines (1) whether the soundscape of a site undergoing active restoration differs from adjacent reference reefs with relatively higher or lower coral cover, and (2) whether site-related differences in soundscape are consistent throughout diel and lunar cycles. Soundscapes were sampled in November 2023 at three sites around Cousin Island Special Reserve, Seychelles. Acoustic analysis followed two approaches: a Machine Learning (ML) driven ReefPerch model facilitated analysis of the entire soundscape, and manual listening quantified fish vocalisations. Results were approach-specific: the manual approach revealed the similarity in soundscape activity of the Healthy and restoration sites, while the ML approach clustered restoration and Degraded soundscapes together. Both approaches detected differences between the Healthy and Degraded soundscapes, in spite of their relatively narrow difference in coral cover. The results suggest that the restoration site may exhibit early signs of soundscape recovery, led by fish vocalisations, though this finding requires further work before it is generalisable due to the limited site replication in this study. The disagreement in approaches over the restoration site reveal that the ML analysis could not have been exclusively driven by fish vocalisations, highlighting a direction for future work to elucidate these alternative drivers. This study contributes to the young and evolving field of soundscape ecology in Coral Reef ecosystems, highlighting the relevance of PAM as a complement to visual surveys in monitoring the return of reef function through coral restoration.

Keywords: Mineral Accretion, MAT, coral, coral restoration, Seychelles

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Migration routes of Hawksbill turtles (*Eretmochelys imbricata*) nesting on Sainte-Anne and Mahé, with location and characterisation of their feeding grounds

Type: talk

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Seychelles hosts one of the five largest nesting populations of the "critically endangered" Hawksbill turtle remaining in the world. The absence of information regarding migratory patterns and the locations of feeding grounds for post-nesting females is an important conservation issues for this species. In this study, we tracked 10 females Hawksbill turtles nesting on Sainte-Anne and Mahé islands and analysed their post-nesting movements to learn more about their migratory habits and to locate of their feeding areas. The turtles were equipped with Argos satellite devices (Kiwisats 202 series) as part of a regional programme funded by EU and La Réunion/France. These tags were attached to the carapace using epoxy resin, this was done with the participation of the Seychelles Parks and Gardens Authority on Ste Anne. Argos data collected have been filtered by "SDA-filter" (Speed-Distance-Angle-filter). Three of the turtles travelled more than 750 km out of the Seychelles plateau. The longest migration was carried out by a turtle named 'Camille', with a distance of 1400 km from Ste Anne to Saya de Malha bank. The turtles monitored showed different migratory behaviours. All individuals used only one main feeding site. MCPs (Minimum Convex Polygon) and 50% kernel estimated foraging areas of Hawksbill turtles in this study were smaller than those reported in other studies. Four turtles foraged in average depths of less than 75 m. Environmental factors such as water temperature, current speed, bathymetry, and chlorophyll-a concentration influenced the positions of the turtles on the Mahé plateau. Reef habitats are the main habitat types occupied by the turtles for foraging. Indeed, reef habitats are very present on the Mahé plateau, with a dominance of: "Shelf patch reef complex" and "shelf barrier complex reef flat". The types of habitat that exist on the Mahé plateau are not well known, dequate foraging habitat has to be located and preserved. Further investigation into the specific habitat preferences of Hawksbill turtles would be valuable and should be pursued in future studies. Understanding the detailed habitat preferences of Hawksbill turtles would provide valuable insights for conservation and management efforts.

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Coral Reef Restoration Techniques & Lessons Learned by the Marine Conservation Society Seychelles

Type: poster

Rabia Somers, Nina Andrews

The Marine Conservation Society Seychelles is undertaking large-scale coral reef restoration in the Ste Anne Marine National Park under the regional project titled 'Restoring marine ecosystem services by rehabilitating coral reefs to meet a changing climate future' funded by the Adaptation Fund and implemented by the United Nations Development Programme. Since 2020, MCSS has selected 10 donor sites, established 8 ocean-based nurseries, cultured 12050 coral fragments in these ocean-based nurseries, outplanted 8498 coral colonies and rehabilitated 2460 square meters of reef area under the project. As a consequence, it has gained knowledge and experience in site, species and colony selection, nursery design construction and maintenance, translocation methods and pre-and post-translocation monitoring methods of rehabilitated areas, including the use of innovative techniques such as photogrammetry. MCSS thus proposes to give a talk and/or present a poster on these lessons learned, as well as present orthophotos and videos of the restoration sites.

Marine Conservation Society Seychelles (MCSS), Mahe, Seychelles

Red Alert for Southern Arica’s Blue Economy:The Need for Regional Cooperation for Sustainable Development

Type: talk

Donald L Sparks

Earth is facing a climate crisis. The UN Secretary-General, António Guterres, referenced the 2021 Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Changereport as “...a code red for humanity. The alarm bells are deafening, and the evidence is irrefutable”. While we have all seen images of cleared forests and large-scale strip mining, we are less aware that equally disturbing practices are taking place in the deep seas. For example, less than half of all key marine biodiversity areas are protected. Around the world, ocean dead zones (areas that lack enough oxygen to support marine life) are rising at an alarming rate, from 400 in 2008 to 700 in 2019. And less than 2% of national research budgets are allocated for marine science. The Southern and Eastern African regions are particularly vulnerable. For example, these regions are losing precious mangrove areas, which are vital for marine nurseries. Also, the cold Benguela Current that provides essential nutrients for Namibia’s fish industry is at risk of warming up, putting the country’s fishing sector in jeopardy. Many African countries’ fishing sectors are already threatened by illegal, unreported, and unregulated exploitation. This region has vast and important coastal and marine resources. These resources will need to be managed on both a national and regional level if they are to be used in a long-term, sustainable way. This discussion will examine the constraints and opportunities that the Blue Economy offers for southern Africa and what role the Southern African Development Community (SADC) has in fostering the sustainable use of its ocean and coastal resources. The hope is that such cooperation can turn code red into code blue.

Note: This abstract draws from my article in *African Arguments*, March 2022 and from my book, *Southern Africa’s Blue Economy: Regional Cooperation for Sustained Development* (Routledge Press, 2023).

The Citadel (Charleston, South Carolina, USA) and Management Center Innsbruck (Innsbruck, Austria)

Long term conservation proves that long lived species can be saved: the case of the Hawksbill turtle pop on Cousin Island Special Reserve

Type: talk

Chris Tagg¹, Alessia Lavigne², Daniel Hugelmann³, Brett Smith ³, Nirmal Shah¹

Cousin Island is an essential area for Hawksbill turtles with the highest numbers of nests of the inner island chain. There has been ongoing protection and monitoring for over 50 years. Current monitoring has been expanded to accommodate developing challenges caused by climate change driven erosion. The program has benefitted from technological advances in the form of electrical nest probes and cameras. Pioneering scientific methods have also been used on Cousin investigating egg fertility rates. At risk nests are now translocated with an introduced structured methodology. Investigating damage to nests caused by other digging females is of potential importance if there is increased predation from *Ocypode* spp. Responsible ecotourism is also stressed and its importance in social outreach and increased visibility of the turtles but also to modern day challenges faced.

Keywords: *Eretmochelys imbricata*, long-term annual monitoring, critically endangered, nest probing device, Chelonian fertility, Ecotourism, Cousin Island, Seychelles

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Marine Spatial Planning: Lessons learned in Algoa Bay, South Africa

Type: poster

Hannah Truter ¹, Anne Lemahieu ², Belinda Clark ¹, Bernadette Snow ^{1,3}, Mia Strand ¹, Nina Rivers ^{1,3}, Tegan Carpenter-Kling ¹, James Blignaut ^{1,4,5,6}, Rozanne Bester¹, Estee Vermeulen ¹, Jai Clifford-Holmes ¹, Amanda T. Lombard ¹

Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) has become increasingly important globally to sustainably manage ocean space while unlocking economic potential. MSP processes have gained traction in many developing countries in the Western Indian Ocean (WIO), including South Africa, where national MSP legislation has been published. In response to this legislation, we have established a research-based community of practice (The Algoa Bay Project - ABP) to develop a fine scale MSP for Algoa Bay in the Eastern Cape province, as a pilot study. The ABP has been ongoing since 2017 and will be completed in 2024. Since the inception of the ABP, we have learned many lessons regarding best practice for MSP in developing countries. We capture these lessons in an open-access online course (referred to as a “Massive Open Online Course” or MOOC). Here we share the MOOC with delegates of the conference from the WIO region, especially the Seychelles, where MSP is particularly advanced. We hope to learn additional lessons from the Seychelles and other WIO stakeholders, to improve the MOOC, and discuss how the MOOC lessons can be mainstreamed to assist MSP practitioners in the region as they develop their respective MSP processes.

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Methods to identify and solutions to prevent dFAD impacts on coral reefs

Type: talk

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Over the past few years, the impacts of derelict Fish Aggregating Devices (dFADs) on coral reefs have become a matter of discussion and concern. However, these discussions have often been based on observations rather than scientific research. To this end, in a collaborative project between a research institution, a tuna fishery company and a local NGO, we aimed at defining and testing a methodology that would allow assessing the potential impacts of dFADs on coral reefs. A non-invasive methodology was defined prior to fieldwork research in D'Arros island, Seychelles. Furthermore, we pre-identified the location of four dFADs locations in the area. For a period of two-weeks, we visited this island and conducted a pilot fieldwork-based research study around dFAD, testing and adapting the methodology so it would fit to the specificities of assessing dFADs-coral reef interactions. Due to this pilot project with a limited number of dFADs did not support solid statistical analysis, we additionally recorded the type of interactions between the different parts of the dFADs and the reef. This information, together with the feedback provided through a questionnaire survey distributed among members of the coral reef/fisheries research, fishery, competent authorities and NGOs communities, allowed us defining and proposing a series of measures that could help to prevent or reduce the impacts of dFADs on coral reefs. Echebaster, a tuna fishery company, has already implemented some of the measures proposed, such as the replacement of attractors used in the FADs to avoid their impact. Thus, the innovative research methods and the measures defined in this project should serve to progress towards the sustainability of the tuna fishery industry.

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Determining baseline information for the effective management of the Seychelles' small-scale octopus' fishery

Type: poster

Annie Vidot and Rodney Govinden

Octopus fishing has been traditionally practiced for many years within the western Indian Ocean. The Octopus fishery is one of the demersal fishery without a well-developed management plan in Seychelles. There are growing concerns over the sustainability of the octopus resource due to its ease of exploitation and the lack of appropriate management measures. Consequently, the octopus fishery is undoubtedly under considerable fishing pressure. There is a need for the Seychelles Fishing Authority to reconsider the management of this fishery. However, there is currently a lack of reliable scientific information and monitoring efforts on octopus catches to support the sustainability of this fishery. This study aims to establish baseline information about the socioeconomic state of the Seychelles small-scale octopus fishery. This will be achieved through investigating the social, economics, fishing operation and governance aspects of fishermen within this fishery. The study was undertaken through socioeconomic surveys whereby commercial and recreational fishers on Mahe, Praslin and La Digue were interviewed. A total of 50 fishers were targeted and currently 17 fishers has been interviewed on Mahe, 10 on Praslin and 5 on La Digue. The survey interview is currently ongoing. The results will be used to inform and review potential management measures to ensure the long-term sustainability of the octopus fishery.

Seychelles Climate Change and Adaptation Trust (SeyCCAT)
Seychelles Fishing Authority (SFA)

Optimizing rotifer (*Brachionus Rotundiformis*) aquaculture: impact of four microalgae species

Type: poster

Andrew Esparon¹, Lawrence Grant¹, Bas de Vos^{1,2}

Rotifers (*Brachionus rotundiformis*) are species of zooplankton which are a vital feed for the juvenile fish produced for the aquaculture industry. *B. rotundiformis* have a high reproduction rate, are nutritionally dense and are present throughout the water column, thus they provide an excellent high density feed for fish larvae.

Rotifers feed on microalgae, and the species of microalgae which they are fed will likely influence their production, due to variations in nutrient profiles between microalgae species. This study will examine what effect four species of microalgae *Rhodomonas salina*, *Isochrysis galbana*, *Tetraselmis* spp. and *Chaetoceros muelleri* has on the growth of rotifers. *B. rotundiformis* will be added to twelve one-liter sampling bottles, with three bottles treated to specific quantities of each of the four algal species. Aeration, constant light, and temperature will be provided over a 5-day period, during which the growth will be closely monitored. At the end of the trial, the algal cell density, rotifer abundance and rotifer fecundity will be quantified.

Our end results will indicate which of the four species of algae is more suitable for growing rotifers, thus enhancing the process of larval rearing. This valuable information will assist the production of fish larvae not only in the Seychelles, but also across the globe.

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